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THE EFFECTS OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON IMMIGRANTS, REFUGEES AND ASYLUM SEEKERS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION: FROM THEORY TO PRACTICE

Claudia Anamaria IOV¹

ABSTRACT:

THIS PAPER EXAMINES THE SPECIFIC WAYS IN WHICH IMMIGRANTS, ESPECIALLY SEASONAL WORKERS, REFUGEES AND ASYLUM SEEKERS HAVE BEEN AFFECTED BY THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND PRESENTS A VARIETY OF MEASURES TAKEN IN HOST COUNTRIES TO PREVENT AND MITIGATE THE EFFECTS OF THE PANDEMIC. IN THIS CONTEXT, WE WILL ANALYZE SPECIFIC SITUATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES, FOCUSING ON SOME WORRYING SITUATIONS FACED BY THESE CATEGORIES OF PEOPLE. OUR ATTENTION IS DRAWN TOWARDS THE ENTRY RESTRICTIONS IN SOME COUNTRIES THAT PREVIOUSLY ACCEPTED ASYLUM SEEKERS, AS WELL AS THE OBVIOUS AND HIDDEN FORMS OF EXCLUSION OF MIGRANTS FROM THE LABOR MARKET DUE TO RISING UNEMPLOYMENT AND THE EMERGENCE OF NEW FORMS OF DISCRIMINATION.

KEY WORDS: CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC, IMMIGRANTS, REFUGEES, ASYLUM SEEKERS.

INTRODUCTION

The Coronavirus pandemic (also known as SARS-CoV-2 or Covid-19) and the global crisis generated by it have affected society from all points of view, from the economic-financial, social, health and political, to the educational, demographic or migration fields. The SARS-Cov2 pandemic was not the first health crisis to affect the human freedom of movement, this restriction being one of the most common measures for disease control since the time of pre-modern epidemics. The novelty brought by the current pandemic is given by the fact that it brought a completely new human experience, marked by tons of hand sanitizer, soap and Zoom. Laptops, mobile phones and a Netflix subscription have become man's "best friends." Airlines cancel flight after flight, while states compete in updating green, yellow or red lists, changing the legislation on the citizens' daily travel or applying for a vaccination passport.

The pandemic has led to a change in migration rules, from a local to a global level, with profound, sometimes irreversible effects on immigrants, refugees and evacuated or displaced people, as a result of major events or natural disasters.

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We do not intend to create a comprehensive analysis of all the effects of COVID-19 on the human freedom of movement in this paper, but we will highlight some worrying situations faced by immigrants, especially seasonal workers, refugees and asylum seekers. Our attention is drawn towards the entry restrictions in some countries that previously accepted asylum seekers, as well as the obvious and hidden forms of exclusion of migrants from the labor market due to rising unemployment and the emergence of new forms of discrimination.

THEORETICAL IMPORTANCE OF THE PAPER

The theoretical importance takes shape by expanding the knowledge base, the paper presenting different theoretical approaches and relevant issues caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in the field of migration. While the problems caused by the pandemic to the HORECA field have been prominently analyzed during this period, the implications for immigrants, seasonal workers, refugees and asylum seekers have been largely marginalized.

In this context, the paper aims to analyze the impact of the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic on immigrants, seasonal workers, refugees and asylum seekers, by presenting specific situations.

RESEARCH METHODS

In order to elaborate the paper, we used the method of analyzing the specialized literature and the specific situations in different countries.

PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

The aim of the research is to examine the impact of the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic on immigrants, seasonal workers, refugees and asylum seekers. We will analyze specific situations in different countries, focusing on the image created on immigrants, as alleged carriers of the disease, in order to make a descriptive analysis of the implications of the pandemic on migration.

THEORETICAL BASIS

The pandemic first occurred in Wuhan, Hubei Province in China in late 2019, when an inaugural group of cases showing symptoms of "pneumonia of unknown cause" was linked to the Huanan food market. The first deaths from this infection in China began in January 2020, and researchers conclude that the virus spreads mainly among animals, but is known to evolve and infect humans as with the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and the Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS). The number of cases begins to increase on a daily basis in other countries like Thailand, South Korea, Japan, Taiwan, The United States of America, reaching Europe, where the harshest outbreak was in the Lombardy region, Italy. From that point on, the World Health Organization has issued a warning to all the states in the world to reduce unnecessary travel and test their population. After the WHO declared a state of pandemic on March 11th, 2020, the states took much more drastic measures and, depending on the incidence, one by one began to impose restrictions such as social distancing, wearing a protective mask, stopping recreational activities, as well as closing their borders, thus affecting whole sectors of the economy, especially tourism. Depending on the number of cases registered, the authorities decided to install quarantine for a determined period of time and home isolation, with the exception of Sweden. All these measures marked the beginning of a more significant global crisis than all other pandemics in history.

In order to slow down the transmission of the virus, EU leaders agreed on March 17th 2020 to reinstall controls at the internal borders of the Schengen area and to a coordinated temporary restriction of non-essential travel to the EU, which was applied until June 30th 2020² and affected especially refugees and asylum seekers. More precisely, on June 8th, 2020, more than 65,000 travel restrictions were issued for 220 countries around the world. The measure was taken in the context in which modern means of transport (plane, train, cars, ships,) allow long-distance travel in very short intervals of time, which favors the rapid transmission of the virus that has an incubation period longer than the duration of the journey, in various regions of the globe. This means that the disease occurs after the arrival in the state of destination. Travel restrictions and quarantine measures to limit the spread of the disease soon led to drastic reductions in traffic, especially by air³, causing colossal losses to transport companies.

In June 2020, the Council adopted a Recommendation regarding the temporary restrictions on non-essential travel to the EU and on the possible removal of these restrictions. The Recommendation was last updated on May 20th 2021 in response to ongoing vaccination campaigns by introducing certain exemptions for vaccinated people and by relaxing the criteria for restriction removal referring to third party countries⁴.

DISCUSSION

The new Coronavirus is currently one of the biggest threats faced by the world. The refugees, forcibly displaced people, asylum seekers and internally displaced people were among the groups that suffered the most from this pandemic. The share of refugees in the EU is 0.6% compared to the total population⁵.

According to statistics, as of April 4th, 2020, thirty-four countries with substantial resettlement of refugees have reported local transmission of the COVID-19 virus. Statistical data on the impact of COVID-19 on these groups are scarce, but the literature reveals that bureaucracy, poverty and discrimination threatened their well-being during the pandemic. For example, the measure of quarantine or solitary confinement at home could not be complied with by forcibly displaced people, refugees or asylum seekers because they do not have a home of their own, most of whom remained in the street without food, money, documents or clothes. Under these conditions, the guidelines of the World Health Organization (WHO) for protection against COVID-19 such as washing hands with soap and water, avoiding crowded spaces, wearing masks in public and social isolation when people show symptoms of illness⁶ are impossible to comply with inside refugee camps that are overcrowded, becoming real "outbreaks of infection".

In Italy, immigrants, refugees and asylum seekers face a mandatory quarantine process of two weeks and, even after those 14 days they will deal with little or no integration

²„COVID-19: călătoriile către UE”, Consiliul European, accessed October 30, 2021, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/ro/policies/coronavirus/covid-19-travel-into-the-eu/>.

³„Mobility transport and coronavirus”, European Parliament, accessed November 01, 2021, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/651908/EPRS_BRI\(2020\)651908_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/651908/EPRS_BRI(2020)651908_EN.pdf).

⁴„COVID-19: călătoriile către UE”, Consiliul European, accessed October 30, 2021, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/ro/policies/coronavirus/covid-19-travel-into-the-eu/>.

⁵„Statistics on the migration to Europe”, European Commission, accessed October 23, 2021, <https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life>.

⁶ “Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) advice for the public”, World Health Organization (WHO), accessed August 09, 2021, <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/advice-for-public>.

services due to restrictions on access to the labor market⁷. Paradoxically, they would have ensured the functioning of vital sectors during the pandemic, such as health, trade, agriculture and logistics. According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, migrants make up 24% of all doctors and 16% of auxiliary staff, such as care workers.

COVID-19 also highlighted barriers to accessing health care for these groups that do not have health insurance or money for treatment in private clinics. Their "luck", if we can call it that, is represented by the NGOs working in the field of assistance for the integration of refugees. LOGS Association - Group for Social Initiatives⁸, from Timișoara, Romania is one such organization, which, since 2019 promotes the integration of refugees and fights against human trafficking through the LOGS House projects for immigrants from Timișoara, the Regional Food Bank for immigrants or support (with clothes, medicines, food, blankets, English language courses) granted to the Quarantine Center and the Asylum Center, coordinated by the Timișoara City Hall.

With the economies affected by the pandemic, in the spring of 2020, some EU countries have taken exceptional measures on seasonal workers to support farmers who were at risk of being left with the harvest in the field. Germany accepted 4,000 seasonal workers (85% of whom were Romanians) to harvest asparagus and other seasonal produce, while Italy received 15,000 Romanians for agricultural work on farms in the north of the country, the epicenter of the pandemic. In this context, despite the mobility restrictions, on April 4th, 2020, the Romanian Government included a provision in the Military Ordinance no. 7 on lifting certain travel restrictions for seasonal workers, with the approval of the competent authorities of the destination state.

On the other hand, according to EU statistics, without migration, the European population would have shrunk by half a million in 2019, given that 4.2 million children were born and 4.7 million people died⁹. In 2020, the population of the European Union at 27 countries slightly decreased from 447.3 million to 447.0, interrupting a long growth led by a positive net migration. This time, the negative natural change (more deaths than births) outnumbered the positive net migration, most likely due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. In 2020, in the EU, there were 534,000 more deaths than in 2019, 550,000 more than the annual average of the period 2016-2019¹⁰.

It is difficult to assess the extent to which the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the population of immigrants, refugees or asylum seekers in the EU, as there is a lack of relevant statistics that can be obtained from refugee camps or immigrant neighborhoods. Movement restrictions and the urge to maintain social and physical distance make it almost impossible for researchers to collect this data. Under these conditions, the analysis is based on statistics regarding the number of COVID-19 cases registered by national health systems regarding testing and hospitalization. These statistics are incomplete, defective, as not many countries require personal data from patients, such as immigrant status or nationality for registration or

⁷ "Asylum Information Database, Country Report (AIDA): Italy" ,European Council on Refugees and Exiles (ECRE), Last updated: June 03, 2021 , <https://www.ecre.org/aida-2020-update-italy/>.

⁸ Asociația LOGS - Grup de Inițiativă Sociale [LOGS Association - Group for Social Initiatives] ,<https://grupullogs.ro/>.

⁹ „Statistics on the migration to Europe”, European Commission, accessed October 23, 2021, <https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life>.

¹⁰ „Population and population change statistics”, Eurostat Statistics Explained, accessed November 02, 2021 https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Population_and_population_change_statistics#EU_population_shows_a_slight_decrease_in_2020.

hospitalization. For example, the United Kingdom or the United States require the patient's ethnicity or race, so they can compile statistics on the number of sick immigrants compared to native-born children with ethnic minority backgrounds. The same happened in Portugal, according to the Estudo Instituto Saude Publica, in 2020, where 24% of the COVID-19 infections in Lisbon occurred in immigrants (mainly from Africa), while foreign births represent about 11% of the population of the Capital-City metropolitan area¹¹. On the other hand, in Italy, a country disproportionately affected by the first wave of the pandemic, according to data collected by the Istituto Superiore di Sanità, only 5% of cases of COVID-19 were related to foreigners¹². Experience urges us to exercise caution when using the number of cases reported at national level as a basis for argumentation, as the population testing strategy, as a measure to prevent the spread of the new virus, especially in the early stages of the pandemic, differs from one Member State to another. We must not forget that even in countries such as Italy, Germany or the United Kingdom, where the test rate of the population was high, the test rate among immigrants was very low, and the 14-day quarantine method without testing was used among today's refugees and applicants.

Another category of vulnerable people which was severely affected by the pandemic, are asylum seekers. In 2020, 471,300 asylum applications were registered in the EU, 32.6% less than in 2019 and 21% less compared to the level recorded in 2014 (530,600). Syrians remained the largest group of asylum seekers in the EU in 2020, (15.2%), while Afghans accounted for 10.6% of all new asylum seekers, Venezuelans 7.3% and Colombians 7%¹³. The decrease in the number of asylum applications must be correlated with the increase in the number of applications rejected by the requested countries in the context of the restrictions imposed by the pandemic. Following the implementation of social distancing as well as travel restrictions, voluntary agencies such as the Hebrew Migration Assistance Association, the International Rescue Committee or NGOs that help refugees placed in aid centers, have realized that their work will face new economic, social and psychological challenges posed by the situation of the pandemic. UN spokesman António Guterres recently highlighted the international community's obligation to support refugees and asylum seekers during the pandemic: "We all have a legitimate interest in ensuring that the responsibility to protect the world's refugees is shared equitably and that human mobility remains safe, inclusive and respectful of human rights and the international law regarding refugees"¹⁴.

Unfortunately, even now, as with other crises, today's refugees and applicants are proving to be extremely vulnerable to the direct and indirect effects of COVID-19. Their

¹¹ "What is the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on immigrants and their children?", Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, OECD, October 19, 2021, accessed July 07, 2021, <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/what-is-the-impact-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-on-immigrants-and-their-children-e7cbb7de/>.

¹² "What is the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on immigrants and their children?", Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, OECD, October 19, 2021, accessed July 07, 2021, <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/what-is-the-impact-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-on-immigrants-and-their-children-e7cbb7de/>.

¹³ „Asylum and migration in the EU: facts and figures”, European Parliament, Last updated July 13, 2021, <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/ro/headlines/society/20170629STO78630/azilul-si-migratia-in-ue-cifre-si-date>.

¹⁴ „UN chief underlines need to protect refugees and migrants in COVID-19 pandemic”, United Nations (UN) Department of Economic and Social Affairs, accessed October 27, 2021, <https://www.un.org/fr/desa/un-chief-underlines-need-protect-refugees-and-migrants-covid-19-pandemic#:~:text=%E2%80%9CWe%20all%20have%20a%20vested,Guterres>.

ability to avoid infection, to receive specialized medical care, to cope with the economic, social and psychological impact of the pandemic is very low due to the fact that they live in crowded settlements (camps or suburbs), have inadequate nutrition and perform hard work.

CONCLUSION

This pandemic has turned the lives of people all over the world upside down. A global crisis has overlapped many other "small", local, personal ones. SARS-CoV-2 has severely affected the global community, putting marginalized populations at high risk of getting COVID-19 and even losing the fight against it. The health crisis has affected many areas of activity and has left its mark on the phenomenon of migration, which by mid-2020 had been halved.

From the outbreak of the pandemic until mid-April 2020, countries around the world have operated in a state of emergency or have taken drastic measures to limit the spread of the virus, with effects on the immigration phenomenon in its entirety. Thus, as stated by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, migrants have been and remain the most affected by this pandemic. In these conditions, it is essential to take measures at local and national level to improve access to health care, education, integration, as well as economic and legal protections for immigrant communities.

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DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: A NEW MODEL OF ECONOMY AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN ROMANIA

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ABSTRACT

THE DIGITALIZATION PROCESS OF SOCIETY INVOLVES THE ACCELERATION OF THE WAY WE LIVE OUR LIVES, A DIRECT EFFECT OF IT IS THE INCREASE OF THE SPEED WITH WHICH DECISIONS ARE MADE. THE TERMS "DIGITALIZATION" AND "DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION" ARE ALWAYS UNDERSTANDED AS TWO UMBRELLA CONCEPTS THAT COMBINE BOTH TECHNOLOGICAL CHANGES AND THOSE WHICH APPEAR IN SOCIETY ON A LARGE SCALE.

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION REFERS TO THE ACCELERATED PROCESS, WHICH IS CARRIED OUT ON A GLOBAL SCALE OF TECHNICAL ADAPTATION AS A RESULT OF THE DIGITALIZATION OF INDIVIDUALS, SOCIETY AND NATIONS, WHICH CAN BE PERCEIVED SIMILAR TO GLOBALIZATION.

BOTH THE ADMINISTRATIVE AND THE ECONOMIC PROCESS ARE IMPOSSIBLE TO MANAGE WITHOUT THE USE OF DATA AND INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES, GIVEN THE FACT THAT, IN AN INTERCONNECTED WORLD, IT OCCUPIES MORE AND MORE SPHERES, WHILE ALSO CREATING NEW OPPORTUNITIES FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.

ALSO, GLOBALIZATION, TRANSFORMATION OF FINAL CONSUMER BEHAVIOR AND ACCESS TO INFORMATION RADICALLY REMODELS THE GLOBAL ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL SYSTEM. AN EFFICIENT DIGITAL ECONOMY CAN OPEN OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE CREATION OF NEW BUSINESS MODELS AND A NEW DATA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM BOTH IN THE PRIVATE AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION SECTORS.

KEYWORDS: DIGITALIZATION, DIGITIZATION, DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, the economy has been transformed by revolutionary inventions, and the "digital economy" is a concept that emerged in 1995, a year considered a benchmark in the production of information technology equipment.³ The idea for digital services started

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³ O. Kravchenko, M. Leshchenko, D. Marushchak, Y. Vdovychenko, S. Boguslavskaya, „ The digitalization as a global trend and growth factor of the modern economy” published in 2019, available at <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20196507004> accessed on 09.09.2020, 1-5.

in the 1990s, when certain industries turned to media for advertising campaigns. Also in the early 1990s, the first 2G cellular network appeared in Finland. In recent times, the emergence of social media platforms has led to a change in the way a business is promoted.

Digital transformation involves rethinking old processes and transforming them into new, faster, more efficient and sustainable processes and decisions. Daniel Schallmo defines the digital transformation of modern business as a process that acts from the individual level to the level of networks of actors, fundamentally changing business models.⁴ Transformation involves the use of new technologies to deliver services. This process requires skills that allow data collection and exchange, as well as the ability to analyze and evaluate options, which are then used to initiate new processes.

Digital transformation is facilitated by increasingly accessible technology, thus becoming an instrument of the modern economies of the 21st century, when sectors with a high level of digitalization are experiencing the fastest economic growth. According to the literature, digitalization involves building a network of all sectors of the economy and society, which is why we can put an equal between the digital transformation and the transformation of the economic and administrative environment. The spread of know-how, knowledge and technological expertise is growing and has, first and foremost, an impact on the world economy, with transnational companies facilitating the spread of innovation around the world.

The primary challenge of the theoretical framework derives from the transition from the static world, in its physical form, and the digital world, unseen, which requires certain specific skills and abilities to be able to improve organizational relationships in this ecosystem.

Technological systems are developed by humans being a reflection / materialization of the essential needs of civilization, becoming indispensable to society, which validates the statement made by Platon who said that "necessity is the mother of invention." The emergence of technology in everyday life has created a domino effect, influencing each other, society indirectly contributes to the creation of new technologies based on meeting essential needs, new technologies change the way society behaves and functions, in the end affecting the evolution of society itself.

At the macro scale, society can use technology to survive, to evolve and achieve higher levels of global processes, and to increase social efficiency. At the same time, at the micro scale, technological evolution changes human behavior to the level at which it impacts the development of the body of individuals.⁵

In our paper, we will try to define the concept of "digitization" and "digital transformation", to identify the characteristics of digitalization, to see what digitization entails from a normative point of view both at European and national level, to analyze the evolution and features of the new type of administration system adapted to the digital age. Management in the digital age or digital leadership does not consist in leading an organization in the digital age, but rather in having those skills needed to stimulate technology and innovation and harmonize them with the human factor.

⁴ Daniel Schallmo & Christopher A. Williams & Luke Boardman, 2017. "Digital Transformation Of Business Models — Best Practice, Enablers, And Roadmap," International Journal of Innovation Management (ijim), World Scientific Publishing Co. Pte. Ltd., vol. 21(08), 1-17.

⁵ D.J. Wardynski, „Technology and Society: How Technology Changed Our Lives”, published on *Brainspire*, october 2019, available at <https://www.brainspire.com/blog/technology-and-society-how-technology-changed-our-lives> accessed on 09.09.2020.

This paper proposes an evaluative approach to what digitalization means at European and then national level, compared to the level of training and education of the general population and then correlated with the skills of local government representatives. As research methods we will use both qualitative research in analyzing the works that address our topic of interest, but also quantitative methods in order to complete a questionnaire applied at the level of local administrations of different sizes. We will analyze the extent to which the digital age poses challenges in terms of leadership and organizational management, especially in the field of public administration.

At the same time, going beyond the theoretical framework, in our case study we will try to determine how digitization influences the creation of a digital strategy at the level of local administrations. Based on the questionnaire applied to a sample of territorial administrative units, we will see how the symbiosis between technology and the human factor is created and how this process contributes to the improvement of relations between the administration and citizens.

DIGITALIZATION: CHALLENGES AND TRANSFORMATIONS

Saul Berman analyzed digital transformation and its effects on business models, encouraging leaders to focus on two complementary activities: using digital technology for greater collaboration and customer interaction, and reshaping customer values to transform the entire business model.⁶ Bounfour also proposes the following definition: "digital transformation is a new development of digital tools, systems and symbols inside or outside organizations".⁷ The Swedish government, recognized for its performance in this field, explains digitalization as the "catalyst, facilitator and engine of society's development in the coming decades." Brennen and Kreiss base their definition on social life: how human interaction has evolved from traditional methods such as letters, phone calls, to digital methods such as e-mail, chat and social media, digital essentials items.⁸

In recent years, all states in the European area have made progress both in terms of the development of communications infrastructure and in terms of public access to this infrastructure. For example, the European signal coverage on mobile phones, more precisely the percentage of the population living in areas with a cellular signal, is close to 100%, of which 98% are in 3G areas. Thus, the market for mobile telephony and telephone service providers has seen an increase in profits. However, there is still a visible gap between urban and rural areas.⁹

The Brookings report focuses on how digitalization has an impact on people, as "digitalization is transforming the world of work", as mentioned in the report "acquiring digital skills has become a prerequisite for individual, industrial and regional success" which ultimately changes people's jobs.¹⁰ In the literature a clear distinction is made between digitization and digitalization. Digitization is a process of converting information from the physical environment into data in virtual space while digitalization involves the use of technology and the enhancement of digitization by exploiting digital opportunities to improve

⁶ Berman, Saul J.. "Digital transformation: opportunities to create new business models." *Strategy & Leadership* 40 (2012): 16-24.

⁷ Bounfour, Ahmed. (2016). From IT to Digital Transformation: A Long Term Perspective: 11-29.

⁸ S.J. Brennen, D. Kreiss Digitalization - K.B. Jensen, R.T. Craig, J.D. Pooley, E.W.Rothenhuhler (Eds.), The International Encyclopedia of Communication Theory and Philosophy, John Wiley & Sons (2016), 1-11.

⁹ Report "Digital trends in Europe 2021", produced by International Telecommunication Union.

¹⁰ Report to the Metropolitan Policy Program in Brookings, Mark Muro et. all, ,, Digitalization and the American workforce ", 2017, 5-15.

business processes or increase the quality of life among the general population. Digital transformation is then defined as a process used to restructure economies, institutions and society at a systemic level. The large number of opportunities generated by digitalization puts pressure on institutions to analyze or rethink their current strategies and on the systemic and early identification of new opportunities, which requires continuous adaptation by decision-makers in these institutions.

As digitalization becomes more important, it becomes an area of strategic importance that needs to be managed at the supranational level. Thus, a digital strategy proposed by the European Commission becomes indispensable.

The digitalization of the public sector, implicitly, also imposes difficulties for citizens, depending on their level of training in interacting with online platforms, because a service that was previously provided by a civil servant becomes a self-made one, which can raise problems among the population, especially among the elderly population.

Digitalization is both a development opportunity and a necessity.¹¹ In this context, the European Commission is developing a policy of training European citizens to acquire the necessary digital skills, promoting initiatives such as the digital agenda and the skills agenda for Europe.

The economic crisis of 2007-2009 highlighted various structural problems of the Union and the need for a strategy and long-term goals to ensure a rise in living standards and at the same time the need to bring European countries back on the path to smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. The Digital Agenda for Europe was one of seven pilot initiatives proposed by the Union under the Europe 2020 Strategy, drawn up in 2010 at the end of the recession, with the aim of defining the key role that the use of information and communication technology will have to play in achieving the objectives of the strategy. In essence, technology allows us to address fundamental challenges, providing a better quality of life. The Juncker Commission said the Digital Single Market Strategy was one of the ten priorities, committing a € 61.3 billion fund. The digitalization of the single market helps to break down barriers and create cross-border markets by changing the way consumers and suppliers interact. However, there is also a problematic part of the issue of digitization: the degree of digitization is not uniform at Member State level, and in terms of regulations we cannot talk about optimization, which can have a negative impact on the final consumer.

Regarding the digitalization of public services at EU level, we can see a trend of increasing the degree of digitalization and interaction of citizens with public authorities through online sites / platforms. From this point of view, in 2018 Romania was on the last place in the European Union, only 12% of the total population uses digital public services, this low percentage highlights on the one hand the lack of these types of services, and on the other hand, the absence of citizens' basic digital skills.¹²

DIGITAL EUROPE

Digital Europe should reflect the best version of the Union: open, fair, diverse and democratic. The development of Industry 4.0 and the creation of the digital single market is a priority on the EU's agenda, meaning that the Union is expanding its legal support to boost economic activity, including: "European Digital Agenda", "European Broadband: Investing

¹¹ Alina Avram, „Digitalizare serviciilor în statele membre ale Uniunii Europene” published in Journal of World Economy of the Romanian Academy, Vol. 12, Nr. 1, on 2020, 49-52.

¹² Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, "A Digital Agenda for Europe", 2010.

in Digitally Driven "Growth", "Towards a thriving Data-Driven Economy", "Information society", "The age of Artificial Intelligence: towards a European strategy for Human-Centric Machines". According to these documents, digitalization also has social implications, yet we live in a world where there are still problems such as poverty and social exclusion. Thus we must keep in mind that the higher the level of digitalization, the lower the risk index of poverty and social exclusion of the population.¹³

A recent report by the United Nations reaffirms that the data circulating in the online space is the basis of the decision-making process, so the role of digital technology is becoming increasingly clear. The pace of human evolution demonstrates that only those who understand digital power can thrive. At the Digital Summit in September 2017, European leaders discussed the issue of accelerated digital competition in the European single market. The priority of the European Union is summed up in the following phrase: "a suitable Europe in the digital age". Another key objective of the strategy is to make Europe climate neutral by 2050. Thus, the European approach is based on three pillars:

I. TECHNOLOGY THAT WORKS FOR THE BENEFIT OF PEOPLE

Investments in research and innovation must be pooled within Europe to increase interconnectivity between countries, promoting the digital transformation in public administrations being a Union goal. Connectivity is the cornerstone of transformation, it is the foundation that allows data transfer and cooperation around the globe. In order to meet these goals and achieve the EU 2025 targets, appropriate infrastructure investments at Member State level are included in the new multiannual financial framework of the EU.

The implementation of reforms and the intensification of investments in research and development, together with the implementation of new technologies has the potential to increase the gross domestic product by up to 14% by 2030, also contributing to creating new jobs. In addition to the investment side, the real digital transformation starts at the level of the general population but also of business owners who must trust digital tools as safe.

Vulnerability in the online space increases in direct proportion to the level of interconnectivity, which is why it is necessary to establish consistent rules for companies, mechanisms to protect the exchange of information and ensure operational cooperation between Member States and the Union, while building a synergy between civil cyber resilience and cyber security law enforcement. Citizens need to be confident in the technology itself and in the way it is used, especially when it comes to Artificial Intelligence, meaning that the European Commission is presenting a White Paper on Creating Ecosystems of Excellence and Trust in this area, based on European values.¹⁴

In the general view of the European Union, education and training in digital skills is the key to digital transformation. As technology enters in our professional and private lives, digital literacy has become a prerequisite for effective participation in today's society, process automatization produces changes beyond the technological dimension.¹⁵

¹³ Aleksy Kwilinski, Oleksandr Vyshnevskiy, Henry Dzwigol, „Digitalization of the EU Economies and People at Risk of Poverty or Social exclusion”, in Journal of Risk and Financial Management, 2020.

¹⁴ WHITE PAPER Artificial Intelligence - A European approach focused on excellence and trust Brussels, 19.2.2020 COM (2020) 65 final accessed at https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/commission-white-paper-artificial-intelligence-feb2020_ro.pdf on 26.07.2021

¹⁵ Aleksy Kwilinski, Oleksandr Vyshnevskiy, Henry Dzwigol, „Digitalization of the EU Economies and People at Risk of Poverty or Social exclusion”, in Journal of Risk and Financial Management, 2020.

II. A fair and competitive digital economy

The digital economy is defined as part of an economic outcome derived exclusively or primarily from digital technologies with a business model based on digital goods or services. The development of the digital economy can be described, in broad terms, as the process by which information technologies, such as the Internet or other communication tools, change economic and social relations, in a way that reduces a number of barriers in economic relations, or in some cases, completely removes them. According to Thomas Friedman, new technologies have the ability to unite the world by forming their own strong bonds through a combination of the following processes: production, research and marketing, and control over these processes through the latest technological tools. The society we live in is an informational one, and knowledge and information are the main inexhaustible and renewable resources.¹⁶

Ensuring a level playing field is essential in the digital age and the rules that apply offline must be transposed into the online environment, in order to gain the consumer's trust in the first place.

III. An open, democratic and sustainable society

Citizens have the right to reliable technology, where what is illegal offline, is also illegal online, since ethical and social rules must apply equally. In recent years, the Union has focused on creating an open, fair, inclusive and people-oriented virtual space through its General Data Protection Regulation and its rules for cooperation between platforms and companies. The rules applicable to digital services across the Union need to be strengthened and modernized and the illicit sale of dangerous or counterfeit goods and the dissemination of illegal content are issues that need to be addressed in the online environment at least as effectively as in the offline environment. A universally accepted public electronic identity is necessary for every consumer to have access to the data provided in the online environment in order to use products and services safely. A reliable online environment is the key to democracy and cultural diversity.

This digital component is the key to achieving the Union's ambitions, proposed in the Green Deal and goals for sustainable development. Digital solutions can advance the circular economy and at the same time reduce the social footprint on the environment of products placed on the European Union's market.¹⁷

The European Digital Strategy proposes a vision that covers all the challenges involved in cyberspace and emphasizes the fundamental role of a strong data ecosystem, a system that promotes agility and innovation in the system of governance by regulating working ways and tools. The results of this strategy will be, on the one hand, a commission prepared to use all digital tools in collaboration with Member States, and on the other hand the successful implementation of the strategy, materializing in creating new digital solutions for European Commission policies, based on real data, but also of a secure virtual space. This strategy can be seen as the Commission's response to the European Council's call for full governance in the digital space to serve as an example. This means a fundamental change in the way the Commission works, so that it uses all the tools that follow exactly the needs of the people. Essentially, the staff will have access to tools that add value to the quality of work, which ultimately means the delivery, to citizens, of services or products that ensure a

¹⁶ Thomas L. Friedman, *Lexus și măslinul: cum să înțelegem globalizarea*, București, Editura Fundației PRO, 2001, p.35.

¹⁷ Comunicare din partea Comisiei Europene, „Shaping Europe's digital future”, 2020.

better life or the simplification of cumbersome bureaucratic processes. Some objectives proposed by the strategy in order to implement this vision are:

- Support the Commission's priorities and political activities with secure, state-of-the-art digital solutions;
- Provide the Commission with high-quality, reliable, borderless digital public services, implementing its policies at a EU level, facilitating the free flow of data and stimulating the digital single market;
- Enable the transformation of the Commission and maximize its role in policy making by exploiting the potential of Commission data;
- Make the Commission a world-class “open administration” - an institution open to collaboration, innovative and agile;
- Ensure that the Commission's IT assets are secure, that unauthorized access to, or use of information is prevented and that the institution is protected from cyber attacks;
- Ensure the resilience of the Commission by ensuring the security, efficiency and effectiveness of its digital infrastructure and portfolio of digital services.¹⁸

DIGITAL ROMANIA

The state of crisis generated by the current pandemic of COVID-19 underlined the importance of digital assets in all fundamental areas, starting with education, the economic environment and last but not least for what public administration means. Basic and advanced digital skills support education and savings, enabling work to continue through networks and connectivity. Thus, digitalization plays a key role in crisis management and an important role in economic recovery, reinforced by the Council and the European Commission, which are committed to structuring recovery support in line with the dual transition to climate neutrality and resilient digital transformation.

For a solid recovery it is necessary to implement 5G technology and very high-capacity networks, digitalization of enterprises and public administration and implicitly the development and learning of digital skills. Consulting the report on the Digital Economy and Society Index, we can see that Romania ranks 26th out of the 27 member states of the European Union.

This situation is caused by the slow progress made in general, but also by the evolution of domestic policy, as the instability of governments has had a negative impact. Our country has the best results only in terms of connectivity, being on the 5th place in the EU, due to the high use of very high-speed broadband and the wide availability of very high-capacity fixed networks, especially in urban areas, but nevertheless, in terms of digital public services and the use of internet services, Romania's performance is the lowest among the member states of the European Union.

In 2012, Romania adopted the National Strategy on the Digital Agenda for Romania 2020 in which four areas of action are defined, but the achievement of the established objectives has not been evaluated.

Two Government Decisions from 2020 provide:

- GD no. 89/2020 the organization and functioning of a new body, the Authority for the Digitalization of Romania, which takes over the activities and structures of the Ministry of Communications and Information Society;

¹⁸ Comunicare din partea Comisiei Europene, Strategia Digitală, „A digitally transformed, user-focused and data-driven Commission”, 2018.

- GD no. 90/2020 abolishes the Ministry of Transport and the Ministry of Communications and Information Society and creates a new entity, the Ministry of Transport, Infrastructure and Communications.

The results of this 2020 report must be corroborated by the pressure on digital infrastructure and services during the pandemic and the immediate action taken by other EU Member States. Regarding the coverage of very high-capacity fixed networks, Romania suffers in terms of the digital divide between urban and rural areas: 82% in urban areas (EU average being 86%) and 39% in rural areas (EU average being 20%).

In terms of human capital, Romania ranks last in the Union in terms of the level of basic digital skills, as less than a third of people aged between 16 and 74 have at least basic skills, and only 10 % of the population is above the elementary level.

There are several government-run projects aimed at improving digital skills levels across the country, but the results are limited. But we must keep in mind that precisely these digital skills are essential for capitalizing on the benefits of digitalization both in the school environment and in the workplace. The low level of use of the variety of online services reflects the lack of trust in digital technology.

We must be aware that it is precisely these digital skills that are essential for capitalizing on the benefits of digitalization both in the educational environment and in terms of public administration and the field of work.¹⁹

The main impediment to the digitization of the public and private environment, as well as the successful use of these services, is the lack or insufficiency of digital skills among citizens. According to the European Commission, digital skills are defined as "safe, critical and responsible use of technologies for work, leisure, learning and communication, consisting of: information and knowledge, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, security and problem solving. This situation is an alarming one because it draws attention to the lack of theoretical development of the field and highlights the knowledge gaps that citizens face."²⁰

The need for continuity in all areas and the 2020 pandemic accelerated the digital literacy process given that technology was brought to the fore.

In this context, the Romanian Digitalization Authority has the role of establishing technical standards and regulations in the field of e-government, information society and interoperability, which become mandatory throughout the public administration with the following responsibilities: the main state authority with responsibilities in implementing strategies and policies in the field of digital transformation and the information society; coordination of public authorities in the elaboration and implementation of national sectoral strategies for the digital transformation of Romania; elaboration of public policies regarding the establishment and development of innovation centers and business incubators, technology transfer centers and digital innovation; lays down technical standards and regulations in the field of e-government, the information society and interoperability which become mandatory throughout the public administration; last but not least, it will exercise control of state authority over compliance with domestic and international regulations.²¹

¹⁹ Report of the European Commission on the Digital Economy and Society Index in Romania (DESI), 2020.

²⁰ Sorin Șandor, Simona Creța, Tiberiu Fechet, "Digital competences among the Romanian population" published in the Transylvanian Journal of Administrative Sciences, Nr. 2, 2020, 132-147.

²¹ Government Decision no. 89 of January 2020 on the organization and functioning of the Romanian Digitalization Authority, published in the Official Gazette in February 2020.

Perhaps the most important initiative proposed by the Romanian government aimed at accelerating the process of transformation and digitalization of public administration, is included in the National Recovery and Resilience Plan. This plan is drawn up as part of the recovery and resilience mechanism that the European Union is proposing as financial support in the context of the crisis caused by COVID-19 and is intended to accelerate the implementation of sustainable reforms and related public investment in the Member States.

Digitalization is just one of the factors that determine economic growth along with other tools to standardize data processing and storage at the level of central public administration and coordination between public institutions. The low level, or even lack of these services indicates a systemic problem. Although Romania has started the digitalization of public institutions, the degree of their use in practice is very low due to the lack of digital cooperation at inter-institutional level. In order to respond to the recommendations of the European Commission on economic recovery, promotion of the green transition and digital transformation, Romania needs to introduce flexible, reusable and interoperable tools. Among the measures to reduce the administrative burden is the creation of the government cloud for migration and integration into existing data structures of all available data so that the real-time provision of online services is supported.²²

As highlighted in national or European documents, the McKinsey Digital Report on the group of countries in Central and Eastern Europe, emphasizes once again that the technology-based economy can become an engine of economic growth in Romania, the economic potential based on the benefits of digitalization being estimated at 42 billion euros of additional revenue by 2025, generating an increase in gross domestic product by about 20%.

According to the report, Romania has a solid foundation on which digitalization can be strengthened, given that in the period 2012-2016 Romania's digital economy grew by 10.8% per year, a growth almost four times faster than that of the states in the "Big 5" group (the top five economies in the EU), in addition, the digital infrastructure is of high quality

For Romania to reach its potential, it needs the involvement of policy makers by promoting the adoption of technology, both in the public and private sector, supporting workers in the process of qualification and requalification through various programs, given that the most pressing issue is the lack of digital skills among adults, creating opportunities for innovation and start-up programs. The same analysis points out that by 2030, 54% of workplace activities can be automated using only existing technology.²³

Lucky Belder said that it is necessary to address the entire life cycle of technology, from design to implementation and control in order to have an overview of how the digitalization process can be regulated in relation to the values of a democratic society.²⁴

There must be a direct proportional relationship between the level of technological development and the development of a legislative framework at state level. Given the spread of digitalization horizontally, internet access in society, it is necessary to regulate cyberspace, not only from the perspective of government institutions, but also the private sphere, here we refer mainly to the "giants" in the world of technology because they control how the tools they make available to the general public work. The state, as a political entity or form of

²² National Recovery and Resilience Plan, presented by the Ministry of European Investments and Projects in April 2021.

²³ Jurica Novak et. al., „The rise of digital Challangers. How digitalization can become the next growth engine for Central and Eastern Europe. Perspective on Romania”, in the McKinsey Group Digital Challangers Report, 2018, 7-31.

²⁴ Belder Lucky , „The digitization of public” in Culture and International Economic Law, 2015, 175-190.

organization perceived by democratic societies, exercises control of the force and justice on its territory in order to protect the rights and interests of its citizens, but when we talk about virtual space, especially after the emergence of the blockchain, of the digital market, the state loses control because it is not able to exercise it in this space.

According to Schrepel, this shortcoming is counterbalanced by states with the emergence of a new ecosystem he calls "Lex Cryptographia" in which states do not ensure respect for fundamental rights, but technology, a system in which the law must be perceived as an ally rather than a possible threat.²⁵

The challenge here is for those who build the legislative framework because it is their responsibility to find the ways and tools to persuade users to comply with legal requirements, because this system is in a dimension outside of justice.

Lex Cryptographia is a series of new legal principles, a body of laws that authors such as Wright and Fillipi suggest should be considered by the authorities.²⁶

The public sector plays an important role in transformation by using digital technology to make processes and services faster and easier for both institutions and citizens. An analysis of the labor market is needed, in order to establish the role of the education system and the need to develop skills and talents according to the structure of the labor market, but also taking into account the changes that are taking place globally. We can say that the transformation starts from education, so the solution is to ensure the standard digital infrastructure in all educational institutions and support the transformation through teachers. They can integrate digital tools into their online teaching that will ultimately increase student performance compared to the traditional education system because it will be adapted to today's reality. The proactivity and flexibility of citizens in this regard can materialize in new opportunities. Authorities can support the citizen in this whole process, in different ways: improving the ecosystem for start-ups and digital innovation opportunities and, finally, can support retraining and improving the quality of work.

LOCAL GOVERNMENTS IN THE DIGITAL AGE

Most organizations, public or private, are in the process of adapting, seeking and exploring the digital environment for their benefit and that of employees, and a digital transformation strategy serves as a central concept to integrate full coordination, prioritize the transition to digital and implement transformation. The digital strategy is developed in parallel with the economic one, it is built from different perspectives, depending on the objectives pursued. From a citizen-centered perspective, the strategy focuses on transforming products, processes and organizational aspects. A digital transformation involves creating a plan that supports the management team in managing the transformations that occur as a result of technology integration.

There is still no "recipe for success" with all the steps to follow, but only some examples of good practice that can be role models. Strategy planning is a process of defining strategy as well as deciding on the resources that are allocated. While procedural issues govern the development, implementation and evaluation of digital transformation, the

²⁵ X. Groussot, A. Zemskova, E. Gill-Pedro, „ Towards General Principles 2.0: the Application of General Principles of EU Law in the Digital Society” published at Lund University legal research paper series, nr. 2, in November 2019,p. 3-6, 9, 18.

²⁶ Wright Aaron, De Filippi Primavera „Decentralized blockchain technology and the rise of Lex Cryptographia”, 2015, pp. 2-6. available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2580664, accessed on 06.10.2020.

strategy defines what they should consist of. Several studies have identified four dimensions from which the strategy can be viewed, among which we identify certain common elements:

- use of technology: the institution's attitude towards new technologies and the ability to exploit them. The IT area, which has a key role, is desirable for the institution to succeed in creating its own technological tools;
- changes in value creation: the strategy also has an impact on the values of the institution, depending on how much technology deviates the core activity of the institution, offers opportunities to expand and improve services.
- structural changes: it is a basis for new operations and refers to those variations in the configuration of the institution;
- financial aspects: the capacity of the institution to finance the transformation efforts, on which the strategy depends.²⁷

According to the European Commission, the digital strategy is the application of information and technology in a governmental or private organization to provide added value to the parties involved, but also to society as a whole, as defined in the organizational vision. In general terms, the strategy must be feasible, add value and sustainable. Although digital strategy suggests a strong focus on technology, digitalization is ultimately about organizational evolution and how it is managed by people.

Therefore, through this case study we aim to identify the level of digitalization and the existence of digital strategies at the level of several local governments, meaning that we applied a short questionnaire, dedicated to people who are part of the management team at the local government level. From a strategic point of view, the digital transformation generates benefits both for citizens and public institutions, as well as for private actors that contribute to the economic development of the city.²⁸

As can be seen in chart number one, following the distribution of the questionnaire, we received 17 responses from different territorial units, as follows: 8 County residence municipalities; 4 Commune; 3 Municipalities and 2 Towns.

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

²⁷ Christian Matt, Thomas Hess, Alexander Benlian, „Digital transformation strategy” în Business & information Systems Engineering, Vol. 57, 2015, 339- 341.

²⁸ Strategia de dezvoltare digitală a municipiului Cluj-Napoca, 2021.

The challenges of digital transformation are realized by 14 respondents and only recognized by 3 of them. Thus, it can be stated that the vast majority of the territorial administrative units analyzed are in transition to become more digital.

Chart 2. Awareness on digital transformation

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

As a development tool, all territorial administrative units, especially those at the level of cities and county seat municipalities, develop their development strategies on fundamental areas, including IT and e-government. Thus, according to the respondents, out of the 17 territorial administrative units, 15 answered that they are fully aware of the fact that the development strategy must include, be based on the digital transformation and 2 respondents are aware of this (Chart no.3).

Chart 3. Development strategy and digitalization process

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

Regarding the objectives aimed at improving or obtaining the digital transformation process, according to chart number 4, thirteen respondents answered that they set the objectives and the necessary actions to achieve them and 4 of the respondents have set objectives but no action to achieve these objectives.

Chart 4. Awareness of digitalization objectives

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

When asked about improving the relationship between administration and citizens, from a digital perspective, all respondents said that this process has significantly improved the relationship between citizens and administration and that this digitalization process also simplifies the work of officials.

Chart 5. Relation between administration and citizens

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

Chart 6. Work of officials

In terms of regional competition, regarding the level of digitization, seven of the territorial administrative units hold an evaluation or an analysis on this subject/ issue/ matter. Nine of the respondents are in the process of evaluating the regional level of digitization and 1 nor has nor is in the process of assessing such information. (Chart no.7).

Chart 7. Level of digitalization

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

As we said above, management in the digital age, consists in having those skills necessary to stimulate technology and innovation and harmonization with the human factor. Thus, it seems that respondents say that the organizational culture and the process of digital transformation are or are trying to be harmonized and the roles and responsibilities are well defined within the institutions.

Chart 8. Organizational culture

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

Chart 9. Roles and responsibilities

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

Chart 10. Employees and digitalization strategy

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

As mentioned, digital skills have become a prerequisite for individual success and education and training in digital skills is the key to achieving or improving the process of digital transformation. However, only thirteen of the seventeen respondents said they invest in developing digital skills for their employees.

Chart 11. Employees' digital skills

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

Regarding the online services implemented at the level of the territorial administrative units, on the first place is the payment of online taxes and fees, sixteen territorial administrative units having implemented such services. Other implemented online services refer to: complaints, online applications, submission and issuance of online documents, transmission of online meetings.

Chart 12. Online services

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

Finally, we tried to see what the biggest obstacles are in carrying out this digitalization process, from the perspective of public administration. Thus, in addition to insufficient budgets, issues related to digital skills and education in this regard, respondents identified legislation, resistance to change and the human resource component as the biggest obstacles in the process of digital transformation.

Chart 13. Obstacles in the digitalization process

Source: author's representation with data collected using the questionnaire

CONCLUSIONS

Globalization, the evolution of information technology and the emergence of new technologies, as well as the effect among the population, have created a domino effect, influencing each other. Indirectly, society has contributed to the development of these emerging technologies, based on meeting basic needs, and these new technologies change the way society behaves and functions, ultimately affecting the evolution of society itself.

The digital age, also called the fourth industrial revolution, offers an essential role for decision makers in the field of local administration. In order to take advantage of the

opportunities that come with the implementation of new technologies, decision makers must have the necessary skills to exert influence and the ability to implement a strategy with a positive impact on the process of digital transformation.

The digital transformation strategy represents the central concept for the integration of the entire coordination, prioritizing the transition to digital and implementing the transformation, being complementary to the local development strategy.

In order to have a perspective of the daily reality, we made a questionnaire, dedicated to local public administrations to identify the level of digitization and according to the results, administrations have taken steps towards the digital transition, or have already implemented a series of measures and tools dedicated to digital transformation. For the most part, decision makers understood the essence of digitalization and took the necessary steps to develop a strategy, and in the case of county seat municipalities, there are already implemented tools and programs to improve employees' digital capabilities.

The most important obstacles identified in the digitization process, refer to legislation, resistance to change and lack of digital skills, both in terms of human resources and in terms of the general population, because only 10% of the population has digital skills above the elementary level. In conclusion, the literacy process is the first step in achieving digitalization at all levels. The digital transformation affects everyone's daily life, we face its challenges in the public system, at work or through the effects that digitalization has on the economy by acting as a catalyst in the case of the national economy.

It is necessary to have a close bond between the level of technological development and the updating of the national legislative framework, both from the perspective of predictability and from the perspective of ensuring the general security framework in the cyber and digital field.

Regarding the subsequent dimensions of research, we think that it would be useful an analysis of the level of digitalization of the Romanian business environment as well as the analysis of the interconnection between the economic dimension and that of the public administration.

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PERSPECTIVES ON SEAPOWER AND INTERNATIONAL SYSTEMS. THE CASE OF ROME AND CARTHAGE

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ABSTRACT:

THIS PAPER DEALS WITH PERSPECTIVES ON SEAPOWER AND INTERNATIONAL SYSTEMS, FOCUSING ON SOME OF THE FUNDAMENTAL TRENDS WHICH CAN BE ENCOUNTERED IN THE EMERGENCE AS WELL AS THE EXPANSION OF OPEN MARITIME POLITIES. A LOOK AT THE ROMANO-CARTHAGINIAN CONFLICTS IN THE MEDITERRANEAN WILL SHOW THE MANNER IN WHICH THE SEA AND SEAPOWER INFLUENCED THE POLITICS, CULTURE AND STRATEGIES OF BOTH POLITIES, WHILST ALSO AFFECTING THE EXISTING INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM. SIGNIFICANTLY, ROME AND CARTHAGE PROVIDE US WITH THE CASE STUDY OF TWO POLITIES IN SOME ASPECTS, COULD BE QUITE SIMILAR IN OTHERS. THUS, ROME OFFERS THE EXAMPLE OF A CONTINENTAL POWER WHICH UNDERSTOOD ITS GRADUAL CONQUEST OF THE SEA IN MILITARY TERMS AND OF A SOCIETY WHICH, IN VICTORY AND EXPANSION, COLLAPSED IN ON ITSELF AND EVENTUALLY BECAME A HEGEMON OF THE MEDITERRANEAN-CENTRIC INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM. BY CONTRAST, CARTHAGE, ORIGINALLY A MONARCHY AND THEN A REPUBLIC, WAS ALSO A COMPARATIVELY OPEN SOCIETY, A WEALTH-BASED OLIGARCHY AND MARITIME POWER WHICH WAS FORCED BY ROMAN PRESSURE TO TEMPORARILY BECOME CONTINENTAL, IMPERIAL, AND THEN RETURN TO ITS MARITIME ROOTS AND BECOME YET MORE OPEN AND DYNAMIC UNTIL ITS FORCEFUL INTEGRATION IN THE NEW ROMAN-LED INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM.

KEY WORDS: SEAPOWER, INTERNATIONAL SYSTEMS, ROME, CARTHAGE.

INTRODUCTION

This paper considers the importance of revisiting and integrating historical case studies into contemporary political science as well as international relations debates, focusing mainly on the role of seapower as a complex tool of statecraft in a highly competitive international system. Firstly, such an approach is all the more important as history, political science and international relations theory have sufficient common ground for interdisciplinary endeavours². Moreover, the question of seapower and the advantages typical of what one may call open maritime polities remains relevant in the digitally-dominated 21st

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² See Geoffrey Roberts, "Theory and the Narrative Turn in IR", *Review of International Studies* 32/4 (2006): 703-714.

century for a number of reasons, starting from the fact that most of the global trade is still dependent on maritime transport, that global communications make use of underwater cables, and, among others, that strategic maritime checkpoints will likely contribute to rising navalism and securitization.³

A fundamental division between somewhat more rigid continental hegemonies and somewhat more innovative maritime polities can be observed⁴, yet one must also consider nuances. To take a classic example, conservative, rural, land-centred Sparta defeated maritime, mercantile, innovative Athens, but remained trapped by a regional mindset demanded by its unique social system. Yet when its short-lived hegemony ended in defeat, Sparta attempted to radically reform its society and especially its military – surprisingly much more so than supposedly innovative Athens. By comparison, the more conservative, mostly rural, and land-centred Rome defeated the more maritime and mercantile Carthage. Supplanting its position in the Western Mediterranean, Rome underwent a series of dramatic economic, social and ultimately political transformations in the process, which came to affect the entirety of the Mediterranean-centred international system. Although rarely military essential, the manifold uses of seapower were nonetheless the key for maintaining both of these imperial systems. It arguably also provided important lessons – as well as convenient but inaccurate myths – about the competitive advantages of continental and maritime states, and, perhaps, of the role of institutions in affecting power balance in international systems to later generations of statesmen, historians, and political scientists.

The cases of Rome and Carthage are important to consider in this respect as some of the paramount symbols of competitors in an international system – from the ancient world to the contemporary one. The method employed in the article is that of an interpretative synthesis regarding the nature of Roman and Carthaginian polities on one hand, and the complex impact of seapower in international relations on the other. Significantly, the examples of Rome and Carthage provide us with the remarkable case-study of two polities which were shaped in different ways by maritime politics and seapower and which, while fundamentally different in some aspects were otherwise extremely similar.

ROME AND CARTHAGE: A TEST OF STRENGTHS

Despite the willingness of its patricians to compromise on certain social issues, the society of ancient Rome during the 3rd century BC was dominated by a primarily militaristic, landed oligarchy. This mostly remained the case even as its conflicts with Mediterranean powers made its elites truly discover the value of the sea and international trade. Rome eventually built its international system on the ready willingness of the state to employ its martial might, intervening first throughout Italy and then across the Mediterranean in a remarkable display of “empire by invitation” – often in the name of restoring local liberties but in actuality ensuring the submission or integration of other polities into the Roman system. For instance, the Romans would quickly exploit the situation of city-states like the trading power of Rhodes or the Achaean League, using arbitration, alliances, or outright provocations to ensure that the Roman state would impose its dominance throughout the eastern Mediterranean. That the Roman-led system was anything but liberal can be deduced from the very different meanings a term such as *fides* (fidelity) could have for the Romans on

³ See Geoffrey F. Gresh, *To Rule Eurasia's Wave. The New Great Power Competition at Sea* (New Haven and London: Yale University Press, 2020).

⁴ See Andrew Lambert, *Seapower States. Maritime Culture, Continental Empires and the Conflict that Made the Modern World* (New Haven and London: Yale University Press, 2018).

one side – who understood it as the submission of a foreign power to Roman aims – and for the Greeks on the other, who treated it more like a form of alliance and friendship.⁵

Certainly, Rome dominated other Latin polities and then Italy through a network of alliances, yet these alliances were mostly built on the victories Rome had won against its erstwhile enemies. To be sure, the Romans were quite remarkable in their ability to unify the elites of the Italic peoples. Even more impressively, this was a feat which they would manage to replicate in various regions around the Mediterranean, particularly through their unusually lax attitude towards the granting of citizenship, though also as a result of pressure felt during the Latin and Social Wars respectively. Having said this, the outstanding feature of the Roman state was its comparatively inclusive nature and ability to create a lasting political order through the gradual participation of conquered territories into Roman politics, with peripheral elites flocking to the capital. Thus, many Roman commanders originated from conquered Italic peoples. In any case, even if the Roman political order could selectively be more inclusive than, for instance that of Greek city-states – which were notorious for their inability to form stable large-scale polities comparable to monarchies – it was still built to a large extent on the Roman ability and desire to use martial might.

Traditionally, the Roman and Carthaginian states have tended to be considered as existential rivals and fundamental opposites in terms of social organisation – a quintessential land power and a quintessential seapower. However, their evolution in an interconnected Western Mediterranean world and ultimately their military interactions show a different picture, namely, one of somewhat mirrored imperial polities. Hoyos compares the state of Roman and Carthaginian politics, arguing that the Romans had on the whole a more open system – with “no Roman family or coterie of friends able to dominate it for decades or largely exclude opponents from policymaking” – a style of politics which apparently could also be found in other republics, such as Tarentum, Athens, or Rhodes, and, partially 4th and 3rd century Syracuse, where democratic politics occasionally surfaced in an otherwise closed and autocratic system.⁶ At the same time, this perspective perhaps underemphasizes the great transformations of the Carthaginian system from a sea state monarchy to an oligarchic republic and finally to an increasingly democratic republic from the Second Punic War onward, as the state returned to its strongly maritime roots.

In any case, by the middle republic, Roman plebeians themselves were divided into at least three major subgroups, including “a destitute rural proletariat”, “independent and self-sufficient peasant farmers in the countryside and artisans in the city”, and “rich and prominent families” which aspired to a status equal to that of the patricians.⁷ Through a long process mixing agitation and confrontations, the plebeian groups eventually achieved legal equality and the access to the highest offices. By contrast, the Barcid supremacy seemingly enabled a curious turn in the Carthaginian politics. Thus, the Barcids in Iberia would depend upon support of collaborators in their homeland and which, in the close of the Second Punic War, led to the increased opening of the Carthaginian political system. Rome would gradually evolve in the opposite direction towards an all-encompassing monarchy, as “Julius Caesar’s career path would reverse Hannibal’s”.⁸ After all – the inclusion of other elites aside

⁵ Sarah H. Davies, *Rome, Global Dreams, and the International Origins of an Empire* (Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2020).

⁶ Dexter Hoyos, *Hannibal’s Dynasty: Power and politics in the western Mediterranean, 247–183 BC* (London and New York: Routledge, 2003), 207.

⁷ Gary Forsythe, *A Critical History of Early Rome. From Prehistory to the First Punic War* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2005), 158.

⁸ Hoyos, *Hannibal’s Dynasty*, 208.

– if one follows Polybius, Rome would *become* less democratic than its great rival, Carthage. As Quinn rightly shows, rather than truly stressing their fundamental differences Polybius believes that Rome and Carthage are at different points in a similar imperial trajectory.⁹ In the Polybian understanding of natural institutional change – that is, growth, zenith, and then decline towards mob-rule – Carthage had passed her zenith during the Second Punic War, as the “masses” influenced policy rather than “the best men” as in the case of the Roman Senate:

By the time they embarked on the Hannibalic War, however, the Carthaginian system had become worse than that of Rome. Everything—every physical body, every political system, and every realized action—naturally goes through successive phases of growth, prime, and decline, and in every respect things are at their best during their prime. This explains why at that time a qualitative gap had opened up between the two states. In so far as Carthage had grown strong and successful before Rome, by the time in question it had already passed its best, but (in constitutional terms, at any rate) that was precisely the period of Rome’s prime. That is, while in Carthage the common people had by then become the dominant political force, in Rome this was still the Senate. Since policy was decided in Carthage by the masses and in Rome by the best men, Roman policies would prevail. Hence, even though the Romans met with decisive defeats, in the end, thanks to sound decision-making, they defeated the Carthaginians in the war.¹⁰

If the origins of Carthage as a city-state with a limited hinterland made it reliant on merchants and maritime trade, the overall image changes in the following centuries. Thus, it is important to mention that Carthaginians nonetheless included no known political figures which were predominantly merchants, with maritime commerce being combined with the wealth generated by agricultural estates and mines – somewhat similarly to the Roman elites – and with the citizen assembly gaining increasing amounts of power.¹¹ As the permanent Carthaginian fleet is recorded later in Carthaginian history¹², this might partially explain the long-lasting dominance of landed interests over purely maritime ones. Moreover, Carthage always had a much smaller citizen core, a result of the somewhat limited number of Phoenicians, who were nonetheless likely united culturally by the sea. In comparison, Rome was subject to migration from neighbouring hill tribes almost from the onset of its history, which likely contributed to its culture of quickly integrating new elites as it expanded over the centuries.

As a Phoenician colony, Carthage quickly became an interstitial economic nodal point and the centre of an increasingly palpable maritime hegemony across the Western Mediterranean. Lambert interprets the Carthaginian state as relatively open society for its time, yet – crucially – also representing undergoing a transition from the status of a seapower state towards a continental empire. In other words, “Carthaginian strategic culture reflected a commercial/maritime focus, a concern for stability and prosperity over conquest and territory, the combination of wealth and a weak manpower base that emphasised the need for allies and mercenaries, and above all a willingness to compromise to preserve the state”.¹³

At the same time, the traditional focus on Roman exceptionalism when it came to conflicts is convincingly nuanced by Eckstein, who argues that it was the Roman openness towards new methods and people, along with their ability to integrate them into a stable structure – rather than an exceptionally aggressive nature. Following Mommsen, Eckstein

⁹ Josephine C. Quinn, “Translating Empire from Rome to Carthage”, *Classical Philology* 112 (2017): 314.

¹⁰ Polybius, *The Histories* (transl. R. Waterfield). (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010), 6.51.

¹¹ Dexter Hoyos, *Carthage. A Biography* (London and New York: Routledge, 2021).

¹² Nathan Pilkington, *The Carthaginian Empire. 550-202 BCE* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2019).

¹³ Lambert, *Seapower States*, 83.

believes that the ability to create a well-integrated polity gave Rome “exceptional advantages in scale of resources and in control over those resources” in the “competition against large but fragile dynastic empires, or against small and hence limited city-states or mere tribal groupings” – advantages which, alongside the martial nature of the Roman state, led to its long-standing success.¹⁴ While linking the supposed unique Roman aggressiveness to international relations theory and the admittedly widespread nature of militarism in the societies of the ancient world, Eckstein’s important work can be somewhat excessive in downplaying the nature of Roman militarism, perhaps somewhat losing sight of the fundamental, sacral importance of war for the Romans. Recent works have re-evaluated such perspectives, acknowledging that the Romans sometimes acted exceptionally aggressively in exploiting the existing international system, while other times preferring not to interfere.¹⁵

Moreover, one of the essential reasons for Roman success can be found in their many military colonies which acted as ever more distant points of defence for the political centre and allowed assimilation of the Italics to be possible in the first place.¹⁶ Thus, when compared to the militarism displayed by its Italic and Hellenistic rivals, the remarkable determination to achieve victory manifested through Roman militarism was nonetheless of an altogether different intensity. Nonetheless, despite the differences separating their mostly continental and mostly maritime societies, Roman and Carthaginian elites seem to have had a similar perception of themselves as representatives of a universal empire, which contrasted with the newer Hellenistic models based around more or less limited, clearly defined borders.¹⁷

As Strauss puts it, the regular, close contact between two great cities of the Western Mediterranean made them see their own most dangerous characteristics in each other, with the states being mirror images rather than polar opposites.¹⁸ Thus, both states “shared an ethos of aggressive armed expansion”, both had mixed, oligarchical regimes which alternatively dominated or struggled with the wider populace, and both were controlled by landed aristocrats who were nonetheless also reliant on commerce, even as Carthaginian elites were considerably more maritime oriented than the Roman ones.¹⁹ Both societies gradually expanded beyond the interconnected, yet localised rivalries found throughout the Mediterranean-centric international system. The Carthaginians began to break with their centuries-long policy of remaining mostly restricted to the coasts, expanding into the mainland, whilst the Romans would vigorously push beyond the borders of the Italic peninsula. This expansion was decisively influenced by the experience of the First Punic War, yet it was likely also a result of internal political and social pressures and changes.

The First Punic War was characterised – to an extent – by Roman dominance on land and Carthaginian dominance on the sea, with both powers proving their capability to adapt to this.²⁰ Of course, the overall military situation was more complex, with each side suffering reversals in the area of their greatest strengths. This was the case when Romans were

¹⁴ Arthur M. Eckstein, *Mediterranean Anarchy, Interstate War, and the Rise of Rome* (Berkeley: University of California Press 2006), 257.

¹⁵ See Davies, *Rome, Global Dreams, and the International Origins of an Empire*.

¹⁶ Stephen Oakley, “The Roman conquest of Italy”, in *War and Society in the Roman World*, ed. John Rich and Graham Shipley (London and New York: Routledge, 1993), 9-37.

¹⁷ Quinn, “Translating Empire from Rome to Carthage”, 317.

¹⁸ Barry S. Strauss, “The War for Empire: Rome versus Carthage”, in *Great Strategic Rivalries. From the Classical World to the Cold War*, ed. James Lacey (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016), 83.

¹⁹ Strauss, *The War for Empire: Rome versus Carthage*..., 83.

²⁰ Strauss, *The War for Empire: Rome versus Carthage*..., 86-87.

suddenly matched in land warfare by Hamilcar Barca during the later stage of the war. It also happened to the Carthaginians during the first half of the war, when they were outmatched by the Roman fleets and their tactics of turning naval battles – traditionally determined by ramming and missile fire – into battles of assaulting and overwhelming enemy ships with marines.

The conflict can be said to have been as much one between institutions as it was between armies and resources. Initially, the Carthaginian institutions sustained the proven strategy of holding on to fortified Sicilian settlements, expecting that the conflict would be similar in conduct to the Sicilian wars of the previous centuries. However, the willingness of the Roman republic to continuously mobilise vast resources and its sheer tenacity of absorbing losses which would have broken the back of most other states, eventually made it clear that Carthage faced an enemy like no other throughout its long history. That is, they now faced a militant republic with a remarkably stable state structure, able to withstand immense pressure brought on by internal turmoil and military defeats. To top it off, the Roman martial culture was also a factor, as Polybius observes:

At sea, as one would expect, the Carthaginians are better trained and equipped, because naval expertise has long been ingrained there. In fact, they have more to do with the sea than anyone else in the world. The Romans are far better at land-based operations, however. The land army is their overriding concern, whereas the Carthaginians completely ignore their infantry, and take only a little more interest in their cavalry. The reason for this is that the Carthaginians use foreign mercenaries, whereas the Roman army consists only of domestic troops and Roman citizens. In this detail especially, then, the Roman system is plainly superior, since while Carthaginian freedom always depends on the commitment of mercenaries, the Romans depend on their own valour and on the support of their allies. So even if they lose in the early stages, the Romans, unlike the Carthaginians, turn defeat into overall victory: their country and their children are always directly at stake for them, so their emotions remain high and they continue fighting with passion until they get the better of the enemy. Hence, even though their naval expertise falls well short of that of the Carthaginians, as I have already said, the valour of their troops brings them victory in the end. Of course, experience is a major factor in naval warfare, but it is the commitment of the crews that invariably tips the scales towards victory.²¹

This was not only due to the sacrifices the Romans were willing to make, but also due to their determination in winning the seas from the Carthaginians, which they eventually did – in some of the greatest naval battles in human history in terms of the number of participants. Indeed, they famously landed a force in Africa which came close to completely defeating the Carthaginians before itself being decisively defeated with the help of a mercenary Spartan officer. Just as dramatically as the tides had shifted with the near-annihilation of the Roman army in Africa, the outmanoeuvring and destruction of most of the Roman fleet accomplished by admiral Adherbal at Drepana in 249 suddenly revived Carthaginian fortunes. Moreover, a number of successful naval operations and storms eradicated the remainder of the Roman fleets, threatening to undo the entire Roman effort over the past years, with the talented general Hamilcar Barca arriving in Sicily and Carthaginian forces raiding the southern Italian countryside. At the same time, the Carthaginian strategy shifted towards a simultaneous – and successful – expansion of its African hinterland, possibly as a means to support its existing war against Rome, who had proven an alarming ability at militarising seapower for most of the conflict. Nonetheless, this

²¹ Polybius, *The Histories*, 6.52.

meant that the Sicilian front was suddenly somewhat less important. After all, a commander as resourceful as Hamilcar Barca had to begin his campaign by neutralising a potential mutiny among the mercenaries in service of Carthage.

The idea of a certain kind of Carthaginian passivity or quietism has been increasingly challenged in the last few decades, including Rawlings²², and Eckstein²³, the latter linking this perception of passivity more to clichés regarding Eastern torpor and mercantile, even antisemitic tropes. Rawlings shows how the Carthaginian navy as a whole was a complex tool which clearly embodied the manifold complexities of seapower, including a simultaneous blending of military, commercial, and political fields, which ultimately made possible imposing and maintaining a true thalassocracy in the Western Mediterranean. At the same time, Rawlings makes it clear that the Carthaginian reputation for timidity towards armed conflict is unfounded.²⁴ This is especially noteworthy considering the often-facile connection of socially relatively open maritime powers with peaceful commerce, rather than with their historical propensity for piracy – and sometimes with military operations as well.

In turn, Devereaux points to the great costs and strategic challenges faced by Carthage in the First Punic War. Thus, Devereaux shows the fundamental geographic and economic constraints faced by Carthage in Sicily in comparison to Rome, with the former always in need of an expensive fleet to project its power on the island – and on a longer sea-crossing too – while the latter did not require this in order to sustain military operations.²⁵ Indeed, the fact that Carthage was able to sustain the war for such a prolonged period and recover from the Roman attack on its heartland as well as taking back command of the seas during the last phase of the conflict, shows remarkable resilience and determination, rather than passivity or quietism.

While Polybius emphasizes the mutually exhausting nature of the conflict for both Rome and Carthage, he argues that the Punic will to fight alone remain unchanged, with peace only possible due to the inability to supply the Sicilian army after the destruction of its supplies-laden fleet.²⁶ Hamilcar remained undefeated in the field and, significantly, Carthage demonstrated that it had not actually exhausted the entirety of its military potential during the Mercenary War. That the state possessed a remarkable capacity for recovery was demonstrated first in the Mercenary War and especially in the Iberian conquests soon masterminded by Hamilcar and his successors. Thus, the Barcid dominance in Iberia arguably created a somewhat separate, imperial proto-state which was technically part of the Carthaginian republic yet matching its African dominions in size and strength.

The Roman response after the end of the First Punic War is perhaps telling regarding the Carthaginian potential. Lambert links renewed Roman hostility and the conquest of Corsica and Sardinia to the political rise of Hamilcar Barca and the “inclusive, levelling politics” of the Popular Assembly to the detriment of the Council of Elders in the closing stage of the Mercenary War, arguing that Carthaginian citizens had considerably more political power than Roman citizens.²⁷ While there is no direct evidence to back the claim that more inclusive politics – or, in any case, the relative decline of the existing oligarchic

²² See Louis Rawlings, “The Carthaginian Navy: Questions and Assumptions”, in *New Perspectives on Ancient Warfare*, ed. Garret Fagan and Matthew Trundle (Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2010), 253-287.

²³ See Eckstein, *Mediterranean Anarchy*, 163.

²⁴ Rawlings, “The Carthaginian Navy” 285-287.

²⁵ Bret Devereaux “Strategy and Cost: Carthaginian Naval Strategy in the First Punic War Reappraised”, *Historia* 69/4 (2020): 475-477.

²⁶ Polybius, *The Histories*, 1.62.1.

²⁷ Lambert, *Seapower States*, 90-91.

elite – brought about the sudden, decisive hardening of Roman attitude, there is arguably no reason to completely reject this hypothesis out of hand.

Likely drawing on the lessons of the war, the Barcid imperial proto-state in Iberia took a more active approach with regards to recruiting allies rather than mercenaries as well as in the relatively rapid expansion of their territories. Indeed, Barcid Iberia had the potential to become a continental system of alliances just as Rome had in Italy – the difference being that Barcid Iberia was linked by a family, whereas the Italic peoples were bound by the Roman Republic. Another difference was the fact that this Barcid imperial project took place far from the Carthaginian political centre and thus was subject to logistical difficulties and the danger of being isolated – as the Second Punic War showed through Scipio’s campaign. Thus, by taking Sicily, Sardinia, and Corsica, the three strategic islands on its western flank, Rome would permanently prohibit Carthaginian naval presence from truly threatening the Italian heartland. Carthage would never recover its maritime pre-eminence and would instead shift towards the continental strategy of the Barcids, which was employed highly effectively in Iberia and then famously in Italy by Hannibal. Yet, crucially while Rome created new buffer regions around its core lands, Carthage was forced to seek new resources even further from its capital than Sicily had been. This structural-strategic imbalance would tell during the later conflict, which progressively swung in Rome’s favour despite the enormous pressures on its alliance-system. Somewhat ironically, it was only after the disastrous Second Punic War that the sea appears to have become a central focus of the Carthaginians once again, ensuring remarkable prosperity.

Lambert²⁸ and Le Bohec²⁹ argue for the importance of the possible conflict between the Roman imperial system and the more open, democratic governments of the ancient world – with Lambert particularly focused in pursuit of this dichotomy. And while Lambert’s attempts to link Carthage to the legacy of other seapowers is perhaps forced, it is certainly the case that seapower was the key to the survival of what appears to have been an increasingly open society. Thus, in Lambert’s interpretation:

The resilience of Carthaginian seapower culture reflected the critical role of maritime commerce in the life of the state, the enduring Phoenician heritage and the growing awareness of their connection with other seapowers, past and present, not least Athens. After a brief dalliance with Macedonian military glory, armoured manpower and elephants, Carthage returned to maritime trade and manufacturing. The Carthaginian economy recovered quickly after the Second Punic War; trade and agricultural exports made the city rich, funding a fresh round of major civic works. These grand projects symbolised the success of post-war reconstruction; they represented Carthage, and included the great naval harbour, a defiant statement of wealth and pride, built by the popular Assembly of a revived state. The circular harbour combining scale, elegance and power humbled the shipsheds of thalassocratic Athens, and stood ready to house, service and sustain a mighty naval force. The fleet, which the Romans had so publicly destroyed, was the ultimate symbol of Carthaginian power. The sheds tantalised and bewitched the imagination of all who arrived at the city by sea.³⁰

Le Bohec, echoing Gilbert Charles-Picard, admits that while written sources pointing to this hypothesis are few, it likely represents the single most important reason for the Third Punic War and the destruction of both the maritime city-states of Carthage and Corinth in 146

²⁸ See Lambert, *Seapower States*.

²⁹ Le Bohec, “The ‘Third Punic War’: The Siege of Carthage (148-146 BC)”, in *A Companion to the Punic Wars*, ed. Dexter Hoyos (Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 2011), 431-432.

³⁰ Lambert, *Seapower States*, 99.

and the equally harsh treatment and destruction of the famous Iberian fortress of Numantia in 133.³¹ In other words, by these acts of cruelty, the Roman elites pre-emptively intimidated any other city-states or alliances with similar ambitions of independence from Roman supremacy:

In more recent times the Romans, when they went in pursuit of world empire, brought it into being by the valour of their arms, then extended its influence far and wide by the kindest possible treatment of the vanquished. So far, indeed, did they abstain from cruelty and revenge on those subjected to them that they appeared to treat them not as enemies, but as if they were benefactors and friends. Whereas the conquered, as former foes, expected to be visited with fearful reprisals, the conquerors left no room for anyone to surpass them in clemency. Some they enrolled as fellow citizens, to some they granted rights of intermarriage, to others they restored their independence, and in no case did they nurse a resentment that was unduly severe. Because of their surpassing humanity, therefore, kings, cities, and whole nations went over to the Roman standard. But once they held sway over virtually the whole inhabited world, they confirmed their power by terrorism and by the destruction of the most eminent cities. Corinth they razed to the ground, the Macedonians (Perseus for example) they rooted out, they razed Carthage and the Celtiberian city of Numantia, and there were many whom they cowed by terror.³²

Moreover, by the first century BC, the Roman regime would become increasingly authoritarian and absolutist, exemplified by the desire of the state to go as far as control even religious communication during great calamities or victories.³³ This, along with a tightening grip on the wider Hellenistic world, and the replacement of existing democracies with oligarchies or with direct Roman control, underlined the transition towards the clearer authoritarianism of the Augustan restoration and its imperial successors. Thus, in wresting control of the sea from the Carthaginian state, Rome was firmly set on the path of a universalising vision, which brought about a new globalised community in a heterarchic international system built of overlapping spheres of obligations, authority, and autonomy.³⁴

CONCLUSION

Thus, the image of a purely maritime, mercantile polity defended only by mercenaries being decisively defeated by a purely continental, agrarian polity defended only by citizen-leaves, remained profoundly influential, for all of its inaccuracies. For over two millennia, the contrast between the supposedly fundamentally different polities of Rome and Carthage continued to shape language, symbols, and even political actions taken in the international arena.³⁵ Lastly, the cases of Rome and Carthage prove illuminating for a series of enduring facets of international relations and of the importance of the multidimensional nature of seapower. The outcome of this conflict was a new imperial system which would encompass the later Mediterranean-centric maritime order. In turn, it would greatly influence the dynamic Western ocean-centric maritime order of the last five centuries.

³¹ Le Bohec, "The 'Third Punic War'", 431.

³² Diodorus Siculus, *Library of History* (transl. F. R. Walton) (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1957), 32.4.4.

³³ Jörg Rüpke, *Pantheon: A New History of Roman Religion* (transl. D. M. B. Richardson) Princeton and Oxford: Princeton University Press, 2018), 101.

³⁴ See Davies, *Rome, Global Dreams, and the International Origins of an Empire*.

³⁵ See Quinn, "Translating Empire from Rome to Carthage".

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CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING SOME INFLUENCES OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON THE FIELD OF EDUCATION IN THE ROMANIAN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT:

THE FIELD OF EDUCATION HAS UNDERGONE SIGNIFICANT CHANGES WITH THE EMERGENCE OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC EARLY IN 2020. ALL HUMANITY HAS HAD TO ADAPT TO THE NEW REALITY IMPOSED BY THE CREATED STATE OF AFFAIRS. GIVEN THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION AT THE SOCIETAL LEVEL, INCLUDING THE SECURITY PERSPECTIVE, THE COMPETENT NATIONAL AUTHORITIES, BUT ALSO THE ACTORS INVOLVED IN THE EDUCATION PROCESS, HAD TO ADOPT MEASURES TO ADAPT THE SUBSEQUENT ACTIVITIES OF THE EDUCATION PROCESS TO THE REALITIES OF THE NEW PANDEMIC. FOR THE MOST PART, AT LEAST UNTIL THE BEGINNING OF THE SCHOOL / UNIVERSITY YEAR 2021-2022, EDUCATION HAS BEEN TRANSLATED INTO VIRTUAL SPACE, AT ALMOST ALL LEVELS OF REPORTING. THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE NEW EXISTENTIAL REALITY WERE NOT THE MOST FAVORABLE, DUE TO AN ACCUMULATION OF FACTORS OF VARIOUS NATURE. THE OPINIONS OF SPECIALISTS IN EDUCATION SCIENCES, AS WELL AS OF MOST OPINION FORMERS OR THOSE DIRECTLY INVOLVED IN THE EDUCATIONAL ACT (TEACHERS / PUPILS / STUDENTS), HIGHLIGHT MAJOR SHORTCOMINGS IN TERMS OF ITS PURPOSE. THE DECLINE IN THE LEVEL OF EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE CAN ONLY BE WORRYING, THE EFFECTS HAVING AN IMPACT INCLUDING THE SECURITY OF THE COUNTRY, AS LONG AS EDUCATION IS A NATIONAL PRIORITY AND IS PERCEIVED AS A DIMENSION OF NATIONAL SECURITY.

KEY WORDS: EDUCATION, PANDEMIC, ONLINE, SECURITY, SOCIETY.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology used to present and highlight the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the field of education in Romania is of a qualitative nature, the scientific approach being purely theoretical. The authors' study starts with the highlighting of the importance of education on the characteristics of social life, analyzed also from a security perspective, later highlighting the way in which the measures adopted by state authorities to limit the effects of the pandemic on the population affected the educational act as a whole. For the relevance of the approach, in order to perform a more concise and concrete analysis,

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we used the selective method of data from internal or external bibliographic sources, in the fields of medical sciences, education sciences, political sciences, public diplomacy and security sciences.

GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT EDUCATION. ROLE AND NECESSITY

Discussions about education have been a concern of the media and opinion formers in recent decades (including the authors of this study³), being a matter more than natural if we start from the premise that education is the multitude of activities carried out at the societal and individual level for the formation of human personality, in accordance with the interests of society and its expectations of human involvement, depository of a consistent body of knowledge, in developing and imprinting an upward trajectory of society, as a natural desideratum of what evolution is as a whole.

The fundamental dimension of the concept of education is teaching, which is given an essential role in today's society, precisely because it is an essential pillar meant to train the individual, in multiple forms. The level of education of citizens is, in fact, a mirror of the level of culture and civilization of a nation. The interaction between the „teacher” and the „learner” is the main element that contributes to the training of the individual, to the formation of human capital of society, because the „teacher” is able to contribute to the development and capitalization of the abilities with which each individual is born, because he *„cannot become a man unless he is educated”*⁴.

It is unanimously acknowledged that modern society wants educated individuals, able to face the challenges posed by the unprecedented and sometimes uncontrolled processes caused by the complex phenomenon of globalization on a global scale. The realities of recent decades have shown that throughout the world, regardless of geographical position, level of economic development of states or type of government (democratic or authoritarian), sex or religion, citizens have understood the role and need for education as a whole for the evolution of the individual and society, being willing to invest in education, in learning, detaching themselves from customary practices that have not allowed for centuries, certain categories of the population, especially women, access to knowledge, especially since education must *„prepare people for the kind of society that does not exist”*⁵ so far.

Education, learning and knowledge (in everyday language, „school”) have become resources of power for many of the state entities that have realized the need for the educated citizen in society and have invested heavily in this field, Nelson Mandela's statement that *„education is the most powerful weapon that you can use to change the world”*⁶, being more than edifying in this sense. Prof. PhD. Radu Munteanu, former rector of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, stated that *„School is a great enterprise of the spirit which, in the end, lets us understand that, although we all live under the same sky, we do not all have the*

³Cătălin, Peptan, Adriana, Peptan, „Considerations regarding the role of online teaching-learning methods in current society”, Annals of the „Constantin Brancuși” of Târgu-Jiu, Education Sciences Series, No. 2/2020; Silvana, Peptan, „Risks and threats to Romania's national security in the postCOVID-19 period”, Dissertation, master „Global Security Studies”, West University of Timișoara, 2021. In the present study, some aspects that are the object of the mentioned works are taken over / updated / reprocessed.

⁴Vasile, Metu, Education, necessity in human development, available at <https://ziarullumina.ro/actualitate-religioasa/stiri/educatia-necesitate-in-dezvoltarea-omului-38897.html>, accessed: 24.04.2021.

⁵Edgard, Faure, *Learning to be*, (Bucharest:Didactic and Pedagogical Publishing House, 1974), 54.

⁶Adriana, Toma, From the Wisdom of Nelson Mandela. 10 tips to follow, available at <https://revistacariere.ro/inspiratie/din-intelepciunea-lui-nelson-mandela-10-sfaturi-demne-de-urmat>, accessed: 31.03.2021.

same horizon. The school must generate competencies by processing the information of instruction and training, which will allow the articulation of the acquired skills with the commands of the moment⁷.

Such an approach has allowed, in recent years, many countries in the world, which almost half a century ago were almost nothing in terms of knowledge determined by the education of their own citizens, to make essential progress in regarding the evolution on the scale of importance, from multiple points of view, at planetary level.

On the other hand, the phenomenon of globalization, allowing the free movement of people, has been able to contribute to facilitating the migration of a large number of people from poor countries, with a low level of development, to economically developed countries with high-performing education, thus facilitating their access to knowledge. The great American or Western European universities are attended by students from all over the world, the knowledge acquired through learning, as a dimension of education, can be accessed by more and more people and subsequently disseminated in the countries of origin of the „learners”.

Through such practices, humanity as a whole evolves, because an educated individual will be able to respond to the needs, challenges or situations he will face, regardless of the particularities of the geographical area in which he will act, identifying optimal solutions and thus giving value to the classical functions of education, selection and transmission of information and knowledge from society to the individual, development of the biopsychic potential of the individual and its preparation for integration and manifestation in societal life.

There are two very important current dimensions of education, in the context of the exceptional dynamics of security threats that characterize the contemporary world. First of all, the dimension of science education, which requires innovative, critical thinking, capable of using the achievements of science to facilitate everyday life and acquire social responsibility, which allows the individual to know the world around him, knowing that science has been the basis of all technological processes that offered the possibility of knowledge in all fields of activity. It should be noted that, since 2007, the European Commission has recommended „moving from science education mainly through deductive methods” to „science education through inductive methods”, arguing that Europe's long-term ability to „innovate the quality of research will decrease too(...), and the acquisition of skills needed in all areas of life, in a society increasingly dependent on the use of knowledge, is under increasing threat⁸. Secondly, it must be argued that education contributes substantially to the individual's attainment of the 'status' of freedom, from multiple points of view (social, political, cultural or economic), in accordance with the horizon of expectation and its possibilities. In a global world, characterized by multiple conditionalities, the possibility of the free manifestation of the individual to capitalize and enhance his abilities is directly proportional to the degree of knowledge acquired through conscious actions aimed at increasing his level of education.

As a corollary, we could say that education contributes to what we generically call „socialization” in the global world, by transmitting and receiving the multiple values of social communication.

⁷Interview given to the author on 15.09.2021.

⁸The map of science education based on investigation in Europe, available at <https://ceae.ro/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/raport-IBSE-web-3.pdf>, accessed: 15.09.2021.

AN APPROACH TO EDUCATION FROM A SECURITY PERSPECTIVE

In recent decades, education has been in a process of transition, undergoing several reforms, which aim to develop the educational process and adapt it to the trends and peculiarities that shape the world in which we live. The aim was to conceptualize an education system prepared for the transformations in the technological sphere (emphasis on digitalization), social, security or economic, which, at the same time, would promote and support national interests. Frequently, education has been seen as a tool of „soft power”, through which a state seeks to assert itself and strengthen its position on the international stage, so that education and culture have quickly become the most effective tools through which a state can achieve its interests by focusing on advancing human development.⁹

As is well known, another pillar of particular importance to the state is national security¹⁰, which aims to protect the state and counter any threat to it, while protecting national interests. Being multidimensional, multidirectional, but also multifunctional, national security has also been subject to continuous development, ensuring national security becoming a responsibility of both the state and citizens, emphasizing the idea of civic spirit. The multidimensional character of national security must be reflected in a security strategy in which the dimension of education, research, but also of culture has an important role, the development of these dimensions representing, in fact, the essential element of national security.

Therefore, an attempt will be made to make explicit the link between education and national security. Both education and the national security of a state are two defining aspects in order to build a society based on welfare and security, between the two aspects there is a direct link, both being interconnected. The absence of a strong link between education and national security can have a major negative impact on all dimensions of national importance (including: political, economic, socio-cultural, etc.), and can be, at the same time, the catalyst for risks and vulnerabilities to the address of a state. At the same time, in order to avoid the occurrence of such manifestations against a state, substantial and constant investments in education are needed to increase the national level of literacy, the quality of education being a key factor in the resistance of populations to misinformation, a phenomenon that can affect significantly the security of a state.

In this context, in order to ensure national security, education must be a priority area which is to be given due attention by state decision-makers in order to give applicative valences to this status.

The importance of education is regulated in the Romanian Constitution¹¹, the fundamental law of the Romanian state, where, in art. 32 is recorded „The right to education”, through which the state guarantees and ensures the right to education for its citizens. Romania also has the National Education Law no. 1/2011, in which, once again, the Romanian state assumes the responsibility to ensure its citizens the right to education

⁹ Aidarbek, Amirbek; Kanat, Ydyrys, „Education And Soft Power: Analysis As An Instrument Of Foreign Policy”, in *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, (Vol. 143, 2014), 514-515.

¹⁰ Law no. 51/1991 on the national security of Romania, Published in the Official Gazette of Romania, number 163/07 August 1991. Article 1 states: „The national security of Romania means the state of legality, balance and social, economic and the policy necessary for the existence and development of the Romanian national state, as a sovereign, unitary, independent and indivisible state, to maintain the rule of law, as well as the climate of unrestricted exercise of fundamental rights, freedoms and duties of citizens, according to democratic principles and norms established by the Constitution”.

¹¹The Romanian Constitution, available at <https://www.constitutiaronaniei.ro/art-32-dreptul-la-invatatura/>, accessed: 16.03.2021.

throughout their lives, the law having as vision the promotion of an education system based on „values, creativity, volitional capacities and action capacities, fundamental knowledge, skills and abilities of direct utility, in the profession and in society”¹².

The National Strategy for National Defense is the main tool through which Romania strengthens its national defense planning, providing the strategic framework through which are organized and coordinated activities aimed at defending the country and national security. The National Strategy for the Defense of the Country for the period 2020-2024, emphasizes the concept of extended national security, in which an important role belongs to education, being called „vital area” for the country, so that the strategic document aims to ensure a balance between national security and various fields, such as education, health and the economy, but also the modernization of these fields, by ensuring a sustainable and efficient development.¹³

Note: At the international level, we meet organizations, institutions and structures that have implemented policies and adopted laws in the field of education, which highlights the importance of this field for society as a whole. The United Nations has adopted both the Declaration of the Rights of the Child and the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, in which States parties have an obligation to ensure the right of children to education and training.¹⁴

Another international institution that has addressed this issue is the European Union, which has adopted a complex legislative package on education and research¹⁵, the right to education being enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, art. 14 referring to ensuring the right to education of any person.¹⁶

TEACHING, LEARNING, ASSESSMENT DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

The educational process, conceived as the direct or indirect interaction between teacher and student, is traditionally characterized by its direct nature and the interdependence of the two partes involved in all three of its main actions: teaching, learning and assessment. For centuries, these three actions have been carried out in the classroom, through the physical presence of the „teacher” and the „student”, regardless of the form of education: preschool education, primary education, lower secondary education, upper secondary education, non-university tertiary education (arts and crafts schools, apprenticeship schools, post-secondary education), higher education (undergraduate, master's and doctoral programs), although in recent decades, globally, especially in terms of education forms of distance learning have been successfully implemented. The medical constraints imposed by the pandemic caused by the new SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus, since the beginning of 2020, have required major transformations in the global education process, including in the case of Romania, but what was noted was precisely the different degree of implementation of these transformations at

¹² National education law no. 1/2011, available at <https://lege5.ro/gratuit/geztsobvgi/legea-educatiei-nationale-nr-1-2011>, accessed: 16.03.2021.

¹³ National Strategy for the Defense of the Country for the period 2020-2024, available at https://www.presidency.ro/files/userfiles/Documente/Strategia_Nationala_de_Aparare_a_Tarii_2020_2024.pdf, accessed: 17.03.2021.

¹⁴ Onița, Burdeți, The right to education, in documents of international law and Romanian law, available at <https://tribunainvatamantului.ro/dreptul-la-educatie-in-documente-de-drept-international-si-drept-romanesc/>, accessed: 17.03.2021.

¹⁵ This legislative package can be accessed at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/summary/chapter/1501.html>.

¹⁶ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, available at <https://fra.europa.eu/ro/eu-charter/article/14-dreptul-la-educatie>, accessed: 17.03.2021.

the level of the states of the world, some states (as was our country) rushing to close the educational units and translate the subsequent activities in the online space, while others, among which countries with a rich democratic experience, continued the teaching activities in the classic version, „face to face”, regardless of the medical risks to which teachers and pupils / students were subjected, giving weight, thus, to the national priority of education.

The public rhetoric towards such a situation was diverse at international level and, implicitly, in the Romanian space, highlighting beneficial and problematic aspects of both ways of approaching the educational process in the postCOVID-19 period. As the points of view are so diverse, it is very difficult to conclude pertinently which of the variants is advisable in the conditions of the present pandemic, and on what coordinates the state decision-makers should be located regarding the future decisions related to the educational process as a whole. In such a context, differing views are expressed, including the quality of education and the „performance” of the „actors” involved, although most voices believe that online education has not proved to be a successful solution during the pandemic.

In order to be able to express some ideas as close as possible to the daily reality, regarding the analyzed subject, it is necessary to make a short x-ray of the three actions subsequent to the educational process, respectively teaching, learning, assessment.

In a general sense, teaching is the qualified action carried out by teachers with the role of transmitting the message with psycho-pedagogical value, which aims to give birth and stimulate specific learning behaviors, such as knowledge reception, cognitive processing, assimilation, internalization and their behavioral application as skills or means of solving certain problematic issues they face throughout life. In the modern sense, teaching also refers to the set of „*actions and operations*” necessary for the transmission of knowledge.¹⁷

Learning is specific to the human being and requires a psychic activity of acquiring knowledge through actions led by a teacher, which have as effect: the assimilation, internalization and capitalization of the educational curriculum in its various forms. It is seen as „*any new acquisition, which manifests itself as a change in the behavioral sphere, as a result of practice*”¹⁸.

Assessment is a complex activity related to the educational process through which information on learning outcomes is „collected, processed and interpreted”, depending on its objectives and purpose, according to a set of predetermined criteria. It is a process of self-regulation that must be seen as an „*application moment of learning*”, with an educational, selective, diagnostic and prognostic and feedback function.¹⁹

Experts in the field have long focused on the particularities of instructional-educational activity, concluding that their purpose is to obtain skills and performance in accordance with educational purposes, and this requires methods and means specific to each of the dimensions of the educational process.

The teaching-learning-assessment methods known in the literature are, on the one hand, the traditional ones (didactic presentation, didactic conversation, demonstration, working with the textbook, exercise, homework), and on the other hand the modern ones

¹⁷ The teaching-learning-evaluation relationship, available at <https://www.rasfoiesc.com/educatie/didactica/Relatia-predareinvatareevaluar43.php>, accessed: 15.03.2021.

¹⁸ The teaching-learning-evaluation relationship, available at <https://www.rasfoiesc.com/educatie/didactica/Relatia-predareinvatareevaluar43.php>, accessed: 15.03.2021.

¹⁹ The teaching-learning-evaluation relationship, available at <https://www.rasfoiesc.com/educatie/didactica/Relatia-predareinvatareevaluar43.php>, accessed: 15.03.2021.

(algorithmization), problem solving, didactic game, programmed training, discovery learning, computer assisted learning, etc.).²⁰

With reference to modern methods, especially computer-assisted learning, in this chapter some assessments will be made regarding the impact of the pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus on this field, being known that in the last year the teaching process was translated largely into cyberspace.

Even before the beginning of the pandemic, the specialized media had contradictory discussions about the advantages and disadvantages of the two ways of approaching the issue previously brought into discussion. If the methods in the first category are said to have in the center of concern the interest in mastering the content of teaching, the essential role belongs to the teacher, the student being seen only as an object of training that is subject to the transmission and assimilation of a large volume of knowledge in a short time, not allowing their creative thinking, the methods of the second category emphasize the prioritization of students' personality, stimulating them in to discover new knowledge and giving rise to the intrinsic motivation of learning, the teacher being the one who has the role of enhancing the student's motivation for such behavior.²¹

Although humanity is at the beginning of the third millennium, in which the results of the discovery of science and technology are more than obvious, a large part of societal activities taking place through „technical tools”, global education, but especially the Romanian one has been put in front of a unique situation, respectively the replacement of the direct interaction, „face to face”, between teacher and student, with the interaction in the virtual space, resorting to online education. Starting with preschool education, all forms of education, in many cases including doctoral and postdoctoral, have replaced classrooms or amphitheatres with „virtual rooms”, trying to adapt to the particularities imposed by medical restrictions specific to the new pandemic. In fact, the entire global society has been marked by a sudden migration to online communication and distance work, using intensively platforms such as Moodle, Skype Professional, Zoom Professional, Google Meet or Google Classroom, as well as many other applications, much more specialized, to increase interactivity and easy access to operation with data and information of interest to all categories of people, including students.

Despite all the efforts made by the actors involved in the educational process, who started from the premise that „*the transition to online involves more than meetings through audio-video platforms or topics sent through messaging applications*”²², the problematic aspects manifested to the full like any novelty activity, the causalities being multiple, both objective and subjective, being determined to a large extent by the lack of basic skills in the use of online means, both by a large part of students and of teachers, an explicable issue if we take into account the Eurostat statistics for 2019 which show that 43% of Romanian citizens aged 16-74 had low digital skills, which ranks our country in first place in the European

²⁰ Constantin, Cucos, *Pedagogy*, (Iași: Polirom Publishing House, 1996), 84-96.

²¹ Ionela-Gina, Iacob, Comparative study between traditional and modern methods used in the teaching-learning process, available at <https://edict.ro/studiu-comparativ-intre-metodele-traditionale-si-moderne-utilizate-in-procesul-of-teaching-learning>, accessed on 24.03.2021.

²² Florian, Bogdan; Sebastian, Ţoc „Policy notes: Education during the pandemic. Answers to the endless crisis of the Romanian educational system ”, 2020, p. 13, available at http://www.snsa.ro/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Policy-note-educatie_final.pdf, accessed: 10.09. 2021.

Union in this chapter. Also on the last place we are in the situation of young people aged 16-24, only 56% of them with basic digital skills or above basic level.²³

In this context, the experience gained in more than one year of education in the online space allows us to draw some conclusions (based on some studies in the field²⁴), as follows:

- Online education has reconfigured society's perception of the educational act, starting from the problematic aspects born with the pandemic that led, inevitably, to the paradigm shift in the relationship between school and family. In the heart of the school and the family, the student became the „link” between school and family, causing the latter to become aware of the importance of the teacher on the social scale and to participate more actively in supporting him in carrying out specific activities, with immediate benefits for the student and family. Retains the attention, in this sense, the point of view expressed by Prof. PhD. Florin Dragan, rector of the Polytechnic University of Timisoara: *„Staying at home kept them (students - na) in the same area of the family, with a certain feedback from parents who could see if they attend classes, in a more controlled environment”*²⁵.

- The category of efforts made to streamline the implementation of online education and increase its attractiveness includes counseling activities carried out by teachers, with the role of arousing students' interest in the educational process in this delicate period of time caused by the pandemic. It is worth mentioning the point of view expressed by Associate Prof. PhD. Mădălin Bunoiu, vice-rector of the West University of Timișoara, according to which: *„Counseling is a major problem in university education and we tried to compensate, so at the level of the first year of study we have a counseling discipline”*²⁶. Some recent specialized studies conducted at Babeș-Bolyai University in Cluj-Napoca conclude that *„undergraduate students are more affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, and female students tend to be slightly more anxious than male students, but, as a whole, the pandemic has a negative impact on all students”*²⁷.

- The online activities required additional efforts from teachers who, being faced with a unique situation, had to reconfigure the educational process, on all three dimensions of it, teaching, learning and assessment. They participated in interactive activities that allowed the exchange of ideas and good practices, in webinars held in different formats. Prof. PhD. Mircea Miclea, former Minister of Education, stated: *„If we do not use this crisis to rebuild the teaching-learning process, the crisis came in vain, for the school in Romania. Three things are essential in teaching any discipline: a) what you teach (...); b) how you teach (...) and c) with what attitude you teach (...)”*²⁸.

²³The strategy regarding the digitalization of education in Romania, available at <https://www.edu.ro/sites/default/files/SMART.Edu%20-%20document%20consultare.pdf>, accessed: 15.03.2021

²⁴Genoveva, Farcaș, Online learning or distance learning?, available at <https://tribunainvatamantului.ro/20/20/04/13/invatare-online-sau-invatare-la-distanta>, accessed: 24.06.2020.

²⁵ Bogdan, Podar, The dropout rate from Romanian Universities has dropped dramatically. What students say, available at

<https://stirileprotv.ro/educatie/rata-de-abandon-din-cadrul-universitatilor-din-romania-a-scazut-drastic-ce-spun-studentii.html>, accessed: 15.03.2021.

²⁶ Bogdan, Podar, The dropout rate from Romanian Universities has dropped dramatically. What students say, available at

<https://stirileprotv.ro/educatie/rata-de-abandon-din-cadrul-universitatilor-din-romania-a-scazut-drastic-ce-spun-studentii.html>, accessed: 15.03.2021.

²⁷ Daniela, Cotoranu; Simona, Claudia, Creța; Octavian, Moldovan, „The psychological impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on students at Babeș-Bolyai University”, in the Transylvanian Journal of Administrative Sciences 1 (48) / 2021, 49.

²⁸ Mircea, Miclea, Tomorrow's school, available at <https://www.edupedu.ro/mircea-miclea-scoala-de-maine/>, accessed: 15.03.2021.

- E-learning has led pupils and students to focus more pragmatically on self-assessment of their potential and to pay more attention to the educational act, which has contributed, among other things, to lowering school dropout in some universities. Regarding the West University of Timișoara, the vice-rector Mădălin Bunoiu states that in the last year the dropout rate decreased to 9% in the first year of study, compared to about 30% in 2018, and Valentina Vasile, master student at Babeș -Bolyai University from Cluj -Napoca claims that: „*It has become much more convenient to be able to attend classes without actually going to college. We didn't have to pay the rent, the food and all the related expenses*”²⁹. Such a situation is more than commendable, if we take into account the fact that specialized studies show a high incidence of mental health disorders for people who have been directly affected by the effects of the pandemic (see quarantine and isolation of people infected with the new coronavirus)³⁰, highlighting the combined efforts of students, their families and educational institutions to optimally manage the adverse effects of the pandemic.

- Online education has some peculiarities that can be assimilated as advantages, both by teachers and students, such as time flexibility and optimal management of time resources, superior physical and emotional comfort, students' access to educational resources or easy access of parents to the educational act, etc.

Many of the higher education units have „customized” their schedules according to the students' possibilities, knowing that many of them are involved in other lucrative activities. The rector of the West University of Timișoara, Prof. PhD. Marilen Gabriel Pirtea, recently stated that: „*We use online platforms for asynchronous communication with students, each professor must have materials organized on these platforms, to be accessible to all students at any time*”³¹. In this context, the initiative of some universities to conclude partnerships with television stations with national coverage, which allowed the transmission in video system of teaching activities and certain conferences / round tables on topics of interest to Romanian society, is noteworthy. However, some experts in educational psychology believe that, at least in the first period after the beginning of pandemic, academic institutions have focused „*mainly on the transfer of educational content in the digital world and less on the methods of teaching and delivering knowledge online*” such a practice being categorized as a „*measure of organizational agility*”³².

- Supporters of modern teaching methods see the online as a means of achieving fundamental changes in the field of education and not an end in itself. They argue that developments in recent decades in the field of IT&C allow the change of classical methodologies circumscribed to the educational process, and through the diversified, widespread use of multiple modern techniques are likely to generate a higher level of the educational process as a whole.

- On the other hand, many of the specialists in the field of education in Romania appreciate that online education has reached its limits during the pandemic. Prof. PhD. Ioan

²⁹ Bogdan, Podar, The dropout rate from Romanian Universities has dropped dramatically. What students say, available at <https://stirileprotv.ro/educatie/rata-de-abandon-din-cadrul-universitatilor-din-romania-a-scazut-drastic-ce-spun-studentii.html>, accessed: 15.03.2021.

³⁰ Gabriela, Marinescu; Cristina, Maria, Stoica, „Education and the socio-cultural context in the spread of the Covid-19 virus”, in Economics, Social and Engineering Sciences Year 4, No.1-2 / 2021, pp. 201-204.

³¹ UVT, Culture is the capital!, available at <https://www.uvt.ro/ro/blog/la-uvt-cultura-e-capitala/>, accessed: 15.03.2021.

³² Svetlana, Rusnac, Attitudes towards online university education during the pandemic, Conference on contemporary concerns of criminology, law and psychology in pandemic conditions, (Chisinau, 2020), 36.

Aurel Pop, president of the Romanian Academy, considers online education as a „breakdown solution”, necessary in the difficult time in which the Romanian society is currently, the essence of traditional education being the ideational message transmitted „from person to person”, stating: *„I see this solution as a necessary emergency solution in these times when we cannot see our pupils and our students face to face, but this is not a long-term solution. School, since it was better organized, from the Greeks and the Romans, requires the presence of the teacher, face to face with those for whom the message of the school is intended. (...) The human message is passed from person to person”*³³.

It should also be noted that online education has limits of applicability in certain areas, such as the medical field. Prof. PhD. Dan Poenaru appreciated that: *„In the last year, due to the pandemic we are in, the instructive-educational process has undergone great changes. Personally, I opt for the traditional way of carrying out the educational process, due to its important role of socialization, integration and direct training of the student. (...) Medicine is a practical profession. It is taught in the presence of the master, near the patient's bed and in the operating room. The individual study has an important role in the training of the doctor, it is necessary to be practised all his life. Virtual education cannot provide the doctor with quality instruction. This also leads to the dehumanization of the medical act. A valuable doctor is not trained if he does not have a master he wants to imitate. Medical education must also include many aspects of ethics, such as compassion for the sick person, exemplary dedication and hard work”*³⁴.

- Some specialists in the field of education sciences highlight the major shortcomings of teaching and learning activities, determined by objective aspects, such as: lack of a computer / tablet / mobile phone in case of a large number of pupils or students; major shortcomings in the field of digital skills, in the case of students and teachers; difficulties in accessing internet networks in particular; difficulties in carrying out educational activities after a program mediated by digital resources.³⁵ Professor Ștefan Vlaston, specialist in educational sciences, at the beginning of the 2020-2021 school year spoke about the need to return to the classic form of „face to face” education, in the context in which a very large number of students, especially from rural areas, do not have access to online forms of education, stating: *„Things are rather bad regarding online courses in Romania, because, according to a Government document, one million students do not have access to online schooling. That means a third of students can't go to school”*³⁶. On the other hand, there is a degree of discomfort of teachers involved in online education, due to poor knowledge in the field that generates technical problems in technology-assisted teaching, limited available technology or some internal barriers, *„including here computer anxiety, fear of technology and sometimes inadequately defined roles, as they may sometimes find that their role is just to teach, seeing the ICT component as something separate, which simply adds to their daily tasks, overloading an already saturated schedule”*³⁷.

³³Eugen, Coroianu, Online education - the education of the future?, available at https://www.rii.ro/ro_ro/invatamantul_online_invatamantul_viitorului-2616544, accessed: 24.03.2021.

³⁴ Interview given to the author on 15.04.2021.

³⁵ Florian, Bogdan; Sebastian, Țoc „Policy notes: Education during the pandemic. Answers to the endless crisis of the Romanian educational system ”, 2020, 9-14, available at http://www.snsa.ro/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Policy-note-educatie_final.pdf, accessed: 10.09. 2021.

³⁶ Cristina Morozan, Why does the online school not work, available at https://adevarul.ro/educatie/scoala/denu-functioneaza-scoala-online-1_5fbbf2f15163ec42712c37ed/index.html, accessed: 15.03.2021.

³⁷ Cristina, Venera, Tartavurea et al., „Online teaching tactics and the effectiveness of the educational process during the COVID-19 pandemic”, *Amphitheater Economic*, 22 (55), 920-936.

• The quality of the didactic act carried out in the online education variant experienced a significant setback, the decision-makers having to adopt urgent measures to counteract the decline of the Romanian school. Prof. PhD. Sorin Câmpeanu, Minister of Education, in February 2021, stated: „*The quality of the educational act has decreased greatly, for structural reasons, online teaching, and for circumstantial reasons, such as difficult access to technology. Both causes have caused great losses that must be recovered as much as possible*”³⁸.

• The assessment activities subsequent to the educational process are difficult in the online implementation variant (both in the case of oral and written evaluation), sometimes they are marked by subjectivism and formalism, being able to generate diagnoses, forecasts, hierarchies and erroneous feedback processes, with negative consequences on the finality of the act itself. The lack of possibilities to correctly monitor the assessment in the online version may also lead to fraud of this activity, due to the associated risks, such as risks associated with technology, risks associated with the assessor risks associated with the evaluated person or risks associated with family members or other persons involved in the evaluation process.³⁹ Eloquently is the case registered at the Faculty of Law within the University of Bucharest, where a massive group of students defrauded the evaluation process, the documentation of these illegal activities resulting in the proposal to expel about 45 students. Prof. PhD. Răzvan Dincă, the Dean of the Faculty, stated that he found: „*the scale of the phenomenon and at the same time the organization of students, who took advantage of the pandemic and the online examination system by creating parallel communication groups in which they jointly solved exam subjects*”⁴⁰.

• Remaining with the analysis in the same space of the quality of the teaching act, it should be noted that the COVID-19 pandemic had totally detrimental consequences on the results obtained by high school graduates at the national baccalaureate exam in the summer of 2021. The assessments coming from the pre-university environment, found in the public space, showed a more than worrying degree in terms of the level of assimilation of knowledge by students, although, paradoxically, the results obtained in the simulation of the baccalaureate exam conducted in March 2021 were better than in the previous year. Although the data provided by the relevant ministry show a degree of pass rated of 73.9%, compared to the number of graduates enrolled in the exam, (higher than the previous year), if you take into account the total number of high school graduates in school year 2020-2121, the degree of passability is more than worrying, being about 55%, it being similar to the one registered at the National Evaluation. It should be noted the very large number of high schools that registered zero pass rate level at the baccalaureate exam, these being mainly in rural areas or

³⁸ Sorin Câmpeanu, after the online school: The quality of the educational act has decreased a lot (...), available at

<https://www.hotnews.ro/stiri-educatie-24588504-sorin-cimpeanu-calitatea-actului-educational-scazut-foarte-mult-pierderile-sunt-mari-foarte-mari-greu-crezut-vom-putea-recover-all.htm>, accessed: 16.03.2021.

³⁹ Maria, Eliza Dulamă (coordinator), *From theory to practice in online evaluation*, (Cluj – Napoca: Cluj University Press Publishing House, 2020), 84-85.

⁴⁰ Students who cheated in law exams were expelled. The Rector of the University of Bucharest, in agreement with the proposal, available at <https://www.digi24.ro/stiri/actualitate/social/studentii-care-au-fraudat-examenele-de-la-drept-au-fost-exmatriculati-rectorul-universitatii-bucuresti-de-acord-cu-propunerea-1461150>, accessed: 16.03.2021.

small urban areas, where there were major dysfunctions of the educational process during the pandemic.⁴¹

Beyond the degree of pass rate of students to the two forms of assessment previously presented, it should be mentioned the decrease of grades obtained by students, even in the context of acceptable degree of difficulty and reasonable level of demand of assessors, Professor Cristina Tunegaru highlighting some of the causes of this state of affairs: *„These children went through everything: new programs, outdated textbooks, new exam subjects, almost a year and a half during the pandemic”*⁴².

Analyzing the particularities of the online learning process, from the point of view of its advantages and disadvantages, it could be concluded that online training must become a way to complement the methods of achieving traditional education, to reach the highest possible level of the parameters of the educational process. Prof. PhD. Mircea Miclea claims that: *„future solutions will be blended-learning, mandatory integration of online solutions with face-to-face learning. The world we live in and the minds of our students (digital natives) demand this”*⁴³.

Thus, online education was the emergency solution adopted at national level in the context in which the COVID-19 pandemic covered the entire national territory and was the only possibility of interaction between teachers and pupils / students during the state of emergency or in the situation of quarantine of some rural or urban localities.

In conclusion, we consider it opportune to present the point of view of academician Ioan Păun Otiman regarding online education: *„In American universities, <<distance education>>, in fact, virtual or online education began in the years 1990-1995. The expansion of virtual education or distance learning has been facilitated by computer networks and the Internet. The fact that, from that period, the computer became a working tool that is in every laboratory, in every office, led to the possibility to take the teaching process out of the amphitheater and the works and seminar room, and the documentation from the library. The lecture hall, seminar or laboratory have been transformed into a huge virtual space interconnected between the student and the teacher's office, from where the courses are broadcast, the practical works are simulated on the computer, homework and projects are executed and seminars are made, as well as online exams etc.*

Distance learning has essentially changed university pedagogy and methodology. The teacher and the student no longer see each other face to face, but dialogue through the computer. The teacher transmits the topic to him, the student executes it and retransmits it to the teacher, he corrects it and retransmits it to the student to see, in a transparent way, what he did right or wrong and how the mistakes are corrected.

Distance learning has emerged as a social necessity and an opportunity for students most interested in their own training. Distance learning students, occupying certain jobs, which they do not want to leave to go full-time student (resident) in university, and the job description at work, constantly changing and expanding, requiring new knowledge, they they

⁴¹Ștefan, Vlaston, Comments on the results from Bacalaureate 2021, available at https://adevarul.ro/educatie/scoala/comentarii-asuprarezultatelor-bacalaureat-2021-1_60e2ddc45163ec4271c5be60/index.html, accessed: 05.08.2021.

⁴² Lavinia, Ioniță, National Evaluation 2021: Dramatic decrease in the number of averages of 10 compared to last year, available at <https://ziare.com/scoala/rezultate-evaluarea-nationala/medii-nota-10-evaluarea-nationala-2021-1687614>, accessed: 05.08.2021.

⁴³ Mircea, Miclea, Tomorrow's school, available at <https://www.edupedu.ro/mircea-miclea-scoala-de-maine/>, accessed: 15.03.2021.

are much more interested in completing their studies, compared to young baccalaureates. From the appreciation of American teachers, it results that their current students are very attentive to their own qualification, but those in distance education, from this point of view, are ahead of everyone. Distance learning, to a large extent, has also changed the informational supports of the course, projects, works, almost all the informational support is electronic.

So, online education, which we have adopted and are now practicing, out of necessity, in the entire education system from kindergarten and doctoral schools, constrained by the Coronavirus pandemic, the Americans have discovered and practiced, in certain well-defined and defined circumstances, for almost three decades.

If until the pandemic, online education (virtual or distance) was practiced on a small scale (both in Romania and in Europe), now it has become a pedagogical system, out of necessity, generalized, at all levels of education, as I said before, from kindergarten to doctoral and postdoctoral school. We will see the results in a while.

But for me, one fact is certain. The teaching and education process is not just a simple system of transmission, of circulation of information from sender to receiver. The process is much more complicated, it has a much more complex chemistry.

When you address the child, the young person, you look him in the eye and you realize if you have made yourself understood, accepted. The way the student receives you, gives the whole measure of the quality of education. At least that's how I understood and I understand the teacher-pupil, teacher-student relationship⁴⁴.

POSSIBLE RISK FACTORS AND THREATS TO NATIONAL SECURITY INTERESTS IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

From a security perspective, the change of the paradigm regarding the educational process in the last year and its translation mainly in the online version, as a result of the conditions imposed by the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus, can generate risk factors for the Romanian society, with impact on the state of security as defined in Law no. 51/1991 on the national security of Romania, such as:

□ affecting the interests of Romania's national security in terms of „state of balance and social stability, necessary (...) for the climate of unrestricted exercise of the fundamental rights, freedoms and duties of citizens”⁴⁵, whereas the lack of education, generated in any way, can affect the individual's ability to contribute to the achievement of the objectives of society as a whole, being known that any modern society can develop only in a climate of stability necessary to perform the functions of the state, in the interest of the citizen.

□ diminishing the access to education, guaranteed by the Romanian Constitution⁴⁶, of an important number of young people (from all forms of education), as a result of the impossibility to access the online platforms for objective or subjective reasons exposed in the previous chapters;

□ as the educational process is a process of knowledge achieved through the action of transmitting information, the impossibility of achieving correct information of all young people through online platforms is a violation of legal provisions regarding the right to

⁴⁴ Interview given to the author, on 20.04.2021.

⁴⁵ See the definition of national security in Law no. 51/1991 on the national security of Romania.

⁴⁶ See the Romanian Constitution, TITLE II - Fundamental rights, freedoms and duties – e.g. equality in rights, right to information, education, expression, health care, work and social protection, healthy environment, etc.

information⁴⁷ and may be one of the risk factors for the security interests of our country, in the context in which an informed and educated person can contribute effectively to the development and progress of society;

The possibility of materialization of the risk factors previously presented may be likely to constitute threats to the national security of Romania, in accordance with Law no. 51/1991 regarding the national security of Romania, art. 3, letter (f), which can be assimilated to acts of: „*degradation or disuse of structures necessary for the proper conduct of social life*”, the role of the field of education for the evolution of a nation is well known.

CONCLUSIONS

After the beginning of COVID-19 pandemic, Romanian society experienced exceptional changes in all areas, difficult to accept by most burdened citizens, and thus, by the effects of an unending transition after the fall of the communist regime and the establishment of democracy. The field of education, marked by fundamental structural transformations in the last three decades, has been, perhaps, the most affected by the new pandemic that has covered the entire planet since 2020.

The impact of the new pandemic was major on the field of education in Romania, being able to reconfigure, first of all, the operational architecture at the level of all forms of education, with not very favorable consequences for the quality of activities and for their finality. This state of affairs is found despite the efforts made at national level by all actors directly or indirectly involved in the educational process (authorities, teachers, pupils and students, family, society). During this period, teachers, faced with a unique situation, reconfigured the entire educational process (teaching, learning and assessment) and found the resources for a different kind of interaction with pupils / students, supported by their family members.

The translation into the online environment of teaching activities (to a large extent), for reasons of medical security, could not replace the traditional education, face to face, being likely to contribute to affecting the quality of education in Romania, which was already on a downward curve in recent years.

Even in these circumstances, online education has contributed to the overall achievement of the purpose of education, that of forming the personality of the individual, in accordance with the interests of society.

As the horizons of overcoming the COVID-19 pandemic (which at the time of writing this study -September 5, 2021- proves to be very aggressive) are not yet clear, the state authorities together with specialists in the field of education will have to identify optimal solutions for managing the situation created so that the adverse effects on the education of young people are as small as possible.

Globally, the world will have to reinvent itself in order to coexist with new threats, the pandemic in which we find ourselves being considered, both by security experts and the medical world, a security threat to humanity.

⁴⁷ In the Romanian Constitution, at art. 31, the Right to information is specified; „1. *The right of the person to have access to any information of public interest may not be restricted.* (2). *Public authorities, according to their competences, are obliged to ensure the correct information of citizens on public affairs and on issues of personal interest.* 3. *The right to information shall be without prejudice to measures to protect young people or national security*”.

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ASSESSING THE CHANGES IN STATISTICAL PROPERTY OF SELECTED STOCK MARKETS BEHAVIOUR BEFORE AND AFTER COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT:

THIS RESEARCH PAPER FOCUSES TO CAPTURE CHANGES IN STATISTICAL PROPERTY BEFORE AND AFTER THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC IMPACT. WE COLLECTED SAMPLE DATA FROM JANUARY 2018 TO SEPTEMBER 2021 FOR TWO RANDOMLY SELECTED STOCK MARKETS, SUCH AS: BELGIUM (BRUSSELS STOCK EXCHANGE) AND INDONESIA (JAKARTA STOCK EXCHANGE). THE MAIN OBJECTIVE OF THIS PAPER IS TO TEST CHANGES IN NORMALITY PATTERN CONSIDERING AUGMENTED DICKER FULLER TEST AND TO DEMONSTRATE CHANGES IN RETURN PLOTS USING LOESS FITNESS, AND WITH ESTIMATED DENSITY PLOTS. THE COVID 19 PANDEMIC HAD A SIGNIFICANT EFFECT ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF STOCK MARKETS, WHILE THE GLOBAL ECONOMY HAS BEEN SEVERELY AFFECTED.

KEY WORDS: GARCH FAMILY MODELS, VOLATILITY PATTERNS, COVID-19 PANDEMIC, LOESS FITNESS ANALYSIS, STOCK MARKET

INTRODUCTION

The recent pandemic has impacted entire economic sectors across the world. Most of financial markets (whether emerging or developed) are not excluded from such impacts. We consider sample of small but emerging financial markets from Europe and Asia to demonstrate whether there is impact over statistical property due to global pandemic. The purpose of selection of smaller financial markets is to capture identify whether such

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pandemic impact also reflects in the markets where comparative trading and volume of trading is lower. We randomly selected two stock markets from Europe and Asia with comparatively lower volume of trading to capture changes in volatility during the period of COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, we selected data from January 2018 to September 2021 daily closing index for a pair of randomly selected stock markets, which are the following: Belgium (Brussels Stock Exchange) and Indonesia (Jakarta Stock Exchange).

Recent pandemic has impacted all financial markets of the world up to some or more extent. Many developed and emerging financial markets from Asia, Europe and America have faced pandemic situations including Dow Jones, FTSE100, SSE, NSE etc. are some of financial markets with very high volume of activity. We focus on sample with comparatively low volume of activity and demonstrate impact of shocks on selected stock markets.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Spulbar and Birau (2018) have conducted a complex empirical study and examined the behavioral dynamics of some emerging stock markets like: Romania, Poland, India and Hungary for the selected period January 2000 to July 2018. The empirical findings revealed that there is no long-term causality and efficient market hypothesis has been rejected for all three forms of efficiency, inclusive for weak-form efficiency. Trivedi et al. (2021) investigated volatility spillovers and correlation between certain European stock markets, like: Spain, UK, Germany, and France (developed stock markets) and Poland, Hungary, Croatia and Romania (emerging stock markets) using GARCH (1, 1) family models for the sample period January 2000 to July 2018. Moreover, Spulbar et al. (2019) analyzed the existence of volatility patterns, causality and international contagion between a cluster of developed stock markets, such as: USA, Canada, France and UK based on GARCH (1, 1) model for the selected time period January 2000 to June 2018.

Ejaz et al. (2020) suggested that emerging stock markets are characterized by more attractive investment opportunities based on global diversification opportunities compared to developed stock markets. Ghasemi et al. (2021) discussed the importance of sustainable development and highlighted that sustainable criteria include economic, social, and environmental issues. Palma-Ruiz et al. (2020) concluded that sustainable and responsible investing (SRI) represents a main strategy which intends to cover both financial return and social good. Meher et al. (2020) argued that sustainable investment is strongly related to the concept of sustainable investing, based on environmental, social and governance (ESG) scores. In addition, Chiappini et al. (2021) indicated that the current global health crisis known as COVID-19 pandemic encouraged research studies on sustainable investments and stock market shock, but the empirical findings remain still inconclusive.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper focuses on the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on stock markets volatility pattern. We consider randomly selected a European and Asian financial markets i.e. Financial Market of Belgium and Indonesia. The study on sample indicates impact on statistical property of financial market returns (closing returns) changes with extra-ordinary news impact. Daily closing returns from 1st January 2018 to 30th September 2021 considered for the study. First we convert series returns into log returns to overcome unit root problems.

Log conversion is applied as follows:

$$r_t = \ln\left(\frac{p_t}{p_{t-1}}\right) = \ln(p_t) - \ln(p_{t-1})$$

ADF regression process is managed as follows:

$$\Delta y_t = c + \beta \cdot t + \delta \cdot y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

ADF process is managed as follows:

$$(1 - L)y_t = \beta_0 + (\alpha - 1)y_t - 1 + \varepsilon_t$$

Symmetric GARCH (1, 1) model is applied as follows:

$$h_t = \omega + \alpha_1 u_{t-1}^2 + \beta_1 h_{t-1}$$

Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedastic is a generalized version of ARCH model by Engle. GARCH (1, 1) processes 1 ARCH effect and 1 GARCH effect. Processing mean and variance equations is another important step in the econometric approach.

The mean equation is applied as follows:

$$r_t = \mu + \varepsilon_t$$

Mean equation indicates sum of average return denoted by (μ) that is returns of asset in time (t), and residual return denoted by (ε_t).

The variance equation is applied as follows:

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \alpha \varepsilon_{1t-t}^2 + \beta \sigma_{1t-1}^2$$

Variance equation assumption process assures that value of constant is higher than 0, following the value of $\alpha + \beta$. The GARCH (1, 1) model represents symmetric model that is extensively used to estimate volatility in time series returns.

EMPIRICAL RESULTS

Considering no constant and no trend impact; $\Delta y_t = \gamma y_{t-1} + v_t$. Result property for BEL, specimen for Belgium financial market considering 4 lags and (BIC) criterion indicates asymptotic p-value 0.6879 where, 1st-order autocorrelation coefficient for e: 0.006 and lagged differences: $F(2, 943) = 13.180$ [0.0000]. The sample test obtained with 946 observations and indicates presence of unit root in the series returns, indicating non-stationary impact.

Further changing property with trend and with constant $\Delta y_t = \alpha + \gamma y_{t-1} + \lambda_t + v_t$ indicates asymptotic p-value 0.08417 where, 1st-order autocorrelation coefficient. for e: 0.005, and lagged differences: $F(2, 942) = 14.358$ [0.0000] with same observations. Both of the process passes through $(1-L)y = b_0 + (a-1)*y(-1) + \dots + e$.

The stock market of Indonesia such as (JKSE) Jakarta stock exchange processes with same model property considering 939 daily observations provides results (with no constant-no trend) asymptotic p-value 0.6682, where 1st-order autocorrelation coefficient for e: 0.058. However, considering constant and trend impact it suggests asymptotic p-value 0.7669. Where 1st-order autocorrelation coefficient for e: 0.061, indicating unit-root null hypothesis $a=1$.

Belgium_KPSS, T = 948, Lag truncation parameter = 12, Test statistic = 0.0869059, the fitness is not significant as it appears at 10%, 5% and 1%, the Critical values; 0.348, 0.462 and 0.743 making P-value > .10. Considering the same value, the Jakarta stock markets

provides, $T = 939$, Lag truncation parameter = 10, Test statistic = 0.0961884, Critical values; 0.348, 0.462 and 0.743 respectively.

Table no.1 Belsley-Kuh-welsch Collinearity diagnostics

Variance proportions				
lambdacondconstd_1_BELC~ d_1_JKSE~				
1.251	1.000	0.000	0.375	0.375
1.000	1.118	1.000	0.000	0.000
0.749	1.292	0.000	0.625	0.625

lambda = eigenvalues of inverse covariance matrix (smallest is 0.74925)

Conditional = condition index

Note: variance proportions columns sum to 1.0

According to BKW, $cond \geq 30$ indicates "strong" near linear dependence, and condition between 10 and 30 "moderately strong". Parameter estimates whose variance is mostly associated with problematic conditional values may themselves be considered problematic.

Count of condition indices ≥ 30 : 0

Count of condition indices ≥ 10 : 0

There is no evidence of excessive collinearity found in selected Belgium (Brussels Stock Exchange) and Indonesia (Jakarta Stock Exchange).

Fig.1 Belgium (Brussels Stock Exchange) and Indonesia (Jakarta Stock Exchange) time-series plot
 Source: Author's computation using daily closing data from 1st January 2018 to 30th September 2021

Graphical presentation (see fig.1) demonstrates the movement of Belgium and Jakarta financial markets. Before COVID-19 pandemic impact Belgium stock market appears with much bullish trend from trading level 3240 to approaching over 4200, and the pandemic impact is clearly visible that shows straight down trend resulting more than 42% of market capitalization during the pandemic period. However, Jakarta stock market appears to have minor corrections and movements seems lower than the mean before the pandemic impact. The pandemic sketches and draw straight downfall in market capitalization from about 6300 to almost 4100 level resulting more than 33% loss of market capitalization. We found that compared to Belgium stock market, Indonesian stock market reacted lesser in terms of market capitalization loss during the same time-period. Interestingly, the market recovery also appears rapid and more aggressive in thee case of stock market of Belgium while having more correction and slow recovery at Jakarta Stock Exchange.

The comparative graph pattern with Loess FIT for Belgium and Indonesia stock emarkets represents the following impact:

Fig.2 Loess fitness plot for Belgium (Brussels Stock Exchange) and Indonesia (Jakarta Stock Exchange)
Source: Author's computation using daily series returns of selected period

Loess test property provides visible impact where returns from Jakarta Stock Exchange scattered and plotted with no relationship (no correlation found) with the financial market movement of the Belgium stock exchange. However, it indicates that there was no

relationship between movements of each financial market during selected period. The fitted residuals indicated with a line in the Fig1 property where most of the residuals have lower volatility sketches and have even amount of shocks that reflected the market movement in same direction. However, we tested correlation and found that there is no significant correlation between Belgium and Indonesian stock markets. Belgium market has more scatter plot compared to Indonesian stock market.

Fig.3 Estimated density plot for Belgium (Brussels Stock Exchange) and Indonesia (Jakarta Stock Exchange)
Source: Author's computation using daily closing returns from selected financial markets

Considering the pattern represented in above graph indicates that both of the market have different upside pattern, before the impact of COVID-19 pandemic. This aspect also includes different magnitudes of corrections whereas after the impact of COVID-19 pandemic both of selected stock markets attempted to bearish pattern.

Table 2 Descriptive statics property

	Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Dev	Skewness	Ex. Kurtosis
BELClose	4.6503e-005	0.013287	-2.0351	23.417
JKSEClose	-8.8217e-006	0.011332	-0.047846	9.4674

Source: Statistical property of selected financial markets

Belgium financial market is having the highest degree of investment risk as the kurtosis creates higher leptokurtic impact compared to Jakarta Stock Exchange for the covered period. The degree of standard deviation indicates almost similar i.e. 0.013 for Belgium and 0.011 for Indonesia, however, the mean return indicates negative return for Indonesia stock exchange and we can see positive mean return for Belgium stock exchange for the selected time period. It indicates that despite of higher degree of standard deviation merely 0.02, Belgium financial market has generated positive returns for investors during the January 2018 to Sep 2021 compared to negative returns for Jakarta Stock Exchange.

Table 3 GARCH computation main statistics

	Descriptive Statistics		
	Const	omega	alpha beta
BELClose	0.000253	5.8180e-06	0.134 0.8455
JKSEClose	0.00031	9.84361e-06	0.150 0.758

*P-value for conditional mean equation not significant for 10%, 5% and 1% significance level for both of the selected financial markets.

** P-Value for conditional variance equation fitted at significance level of 5% and 1% respectively for omega and alpha & beta respectively for both of the selected financial markets.

Source: Author's computation

Fig.4 GARCH (1, 1) forecast for Belgium (Brussels Stock Exchange) and Indonesia (Jakarta Stock Exchange)
Source: Author's computation

Generalized autoregressive model, GARCH (1, 1) model was used to estimate the volatility for Belgium and Jakarta Stock markets. The model did not fit to any of market considering the mean equation property and does not have any strong significant fitness for any of selected financial markets. Variance equation fitted at significance level of 1% and 5% indicating higher alpha and lower beta for Jakarta stock market compared to higher beta and lower alpha for Belgium stock market. Both of the stock markets are having lower volume of trading compared with other emerging and frontier financial markets. We have selected stock markets with comparatively lower volume to capture changes in two different stock markets volatility where the volume of activity and trading is lower. We found that there is no significant evidence of correlation between both of these markets suggesting no transmitting effect of news from one market to another market. Though the mean equation did not fitted to any of the selected financial markets, we have attempted to forecast both of the markets using GARCH (1, 1) model suggests that Jakarta stock market of Indonesia will have stable movements and the graphical pattern for Belgium indicates that market will have bullish trend at the same future time-interval.

CONCLUSION

This research study demonstrates changes in statistical property of financial market series returns during the period of COVID-19 pandemic. It indicates that during the pandemic impact, the selected two emerging financial market have no significant correlation before the COVID impact and found significant pattern of moment while markets are falling due to pandemic impact. The normality test considering with constant and trend and without constant and trend provides how market behaved abnormally during the pandemic period. The results from the GARCH (1, 1) suggest that there is no significant evidence for fitness for mean variance for both of the selected markets. However, it the degree of alpha is higher and beta is lower for Belgium stock market compared to higher degree of beta and lower degree of alpha in Jakarta stock market for the selected period. We found that during the pandemic period, Jakarta Stock market reacted least volatile and resulted comparative less financial market capitalization loss than the Belgium stock market. We conclude that there is no correlation between selected two lower volume financial markets for the selected period, GARCH (1, 1) is not fitted for any of selected financial markets, with higher degree (0.02) of standard deviation, while the stock market of Belgium exhibits positive mean returns.

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STRES MANAGEMENT FOR A GOOD PANDEMIC LIFE IN SMES

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ABSTRACT:

SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES ARE VITAL FOR THE ECONOMY. THAT'S WHY IT IS VERY IMPORTANT TO SUPPORT THEM TO OVERCOME ALL MAJOR OBSTACLES, AND THE COVID PANDEMIC IS ONE OF THESE OBSTACLES. STRESS WAS PRESENT IN ORGANIZATIONS AND BEFORE THE PANDEMIC, BUT IT GENERATED NEW STRESSING FACTORS: SOCIAL ISOLATION, FEAR OF ILLNESS, IN ADDITION TO THOSE ALREADY EXISTING: THE UNCERTAIN FROM THE FIELD OF COMPETENCE, TAKING OVER THE RESPONSIBILITIES OF SICK COLLEAGUES, IMBALANCE CREATED BETWEEN PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL LIFE. THE PAPER PRESENTS THE EFFECTS OF THE PANDEMIC COVID-19 ON EMPLOYEES IN SMES BUT ALSO ON ENTREPRENEURS, OWNERS OF THESE SMES, AND SHOWS THE IMPORTANCE OF IMPLEMENTATION STRESS MANAGEMENT IN SMES AND BEYOND (PRINCIPLES ARE AVAILABLE IN ANY ORGANIZATION AND EVEN PERSONAL LIFE), TO OVERCOME THIS PERIOD IN WHICH WE ARE ALREADY FACING THE FOURTH WAVE OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC.

KEY WORDS: COVID-19 PANDEMIC, SME, STRESS, STRESS MANAGEMENT, STRESS FACTORS

1. INTRODUCTION

The coronavirus pandemic is stressful for many people, the fear, the unforeseen fear can become overwhelming. Applying stress management will help us all get through this period more easily².

Stress is a challenge, it can release unsuspected energies, but it can also make us sick, exhausted. It is like an epidemic, which can affect anyone and spreads very quickly. But what happens when the COVID-19 pandemic overlaps with the already stressful situations, present even before the pandemic. The situation becomes difficult to control, difficult to balance and difficult to overcome, once installed. It is best to prevent, reduce the effects of stress once installed, by implementing stress management.

Stress management is represented by a set of management techniques and associated activities.³

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²<https://www.medicover.ro/despre-sanatate/coronavirus-se-vindeca-noi-trebuie-sa-ne-gasim-echilibrul,323,n,525>

The COVID-19 pandemic occurred in December 2019 in the Chinese city of Wuhan, spreading rapidly around the world. More and more people were getting sick, more and more employees could no longer work. In order to prevent the spread of the disease, it was necessary to wear surgical masks, social distance, work from home, social isolation. With the discovery of vaccines and the vaccination of the population, it was believed that the pandemic was over and that we would return to the normal life lived before the pandemic. We were wrong, though. We are living the fourth wave of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has already begun with entire localities in quarantine, schools where teaching is done online, employees working from home, social distancing in open public places, limited participation in events taking place in inside, wearing a protective mask, watching us everywhere for fear of getting sick.

The SME sector was one of the most affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, worldwide.⁴ Knowing the contribution of SMEs to the European economy⁵, ambitious policies are needed to overcome this critical period of the Covid-19 pandemic, through policies that promote innovation, internationalization and networking, life-saving, progress-generating connections⁶.

However, we must work to be able to live decently, to raise our children, to be an example, a motivation for others. The COVID-19 pandemic came to supplement the stressors that already surrounded us before the pandemic.

We further present the situation of SMEs at European level but also the situation of Romanian SMEs in pandemic, what stress management means and what are the benefits of its application in organizations and beyond.

2. STRESS MANAGEMENT IN SMES, IN THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Confrontation with stress is always a topical issue⁷. The atmosphere in the world, in the economy is more tense than ever, amplified by the COVID-19 pandemic, which brings with it the fear of getting this disease COVID-19, caused by the new coronavirus called SARS-CoV-2⁸.

People feel overwhelmed by stress, watched, disappointed, hurried. The pressure on employees' shoulders is increasing (sometimes they have to take over the tasks of their colleagues who are sick with COVID-19 and not only). The pressure of deadlines, the large number of conferences he has to attend, the change of time zone, all these can make stress

³ Borcoși, Corina Ana, *Stress management applied in the university environment - for a quality life in a pandemic, The dialogue of multicultural discourses*, Section: Social Sciences, (The Alpha Institute for Multicultural Studies: Tîrgu Mureș, 2020), 205-210

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⁸ World Health Organization - Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/question-and-answers-hub/q-a-detail/coronavirus-disease-covid-19>

become a danger to the company's activity, affecting the health of employees, their performance, all reflected in the performance of the organization.⁹

The stress-generating factors for SMEs, in general, but also generated by the COVID-19 pandemic are:

- COVID-19 illness of employees;
- the general fear of the pandemic and the fear of COVID-19 disease;
- separation from family, especially to be quarantined¹⁰;
- insufficient appreciation for the work submitted, especially when it is carried out online;
- disregard;
- lack of trust in managers, in colleagues, especially if the employee-employer physical interaction is also missing;
- unclear aspirations;
- lack of means of action, due to lack of mobility, limited mobility, generated by the pandemic;
- lack of personal time management, especially when you can participate online in several events and work at the same time on a short-term project;
- absenteeism from work, now due to COVID-19;
- too much volume of requirements at the same time.

The excess of information, of challenges was accentuated in the pandemic (ways of transmitting the disease, vaccination and negative effects, causes of illness, how to better protect ourselves).

Consistently setting priorities in life and at work is becoming increasingly difficult to achieve today.

Financial uncertainty, the fear of losing the current job, of losing your business as an entrepreneur is increasingly present in the lives of employees, entrepreneurs¹¹.

Increasing demands at work, if not met 100%, the employee "can say goodbye to work"¹², which makes the stress at work very high.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a major impact on European SMEs. In many, but not all SMEs, sales fell, are supply disruptions, etc., are delays in making payments, are loss-making operations. The impact of the pandemic was different in each European country, but also depending on the industry to which the company belongs. The industries in which SMEs have been most affected by the pandemic are:¹³

- ✚ accommodation activities and food services" (decrease of the added value of SMEs by 37.8%);
- ✚ transport and storage" (decrease in the value added of SMEs by 16.1%);
- ✚ administrative and support service activities" (decrease of the value added of SMEs by 13.3%);

⁹ Schröder, Jörg-Peter., Blank, Reiner, *Managementul stresului: recunoașterea și combaterea eficientă a situațiilor stresante*, (Buncuești, Editura All, 2011), 34

¹⁰ Legea nr. 136 din 18 iulie 2020 (*republicată*) privind instituirea unor măsuri în domeniul sănătății publice în situații de risc epidemiologic și biologic

¹¹ Scholz, Nicole - Mental health and the pandemic, EPRS | European Parliamentary Research Service, July 2021, 7

¹² Schröder, Jörg-Peter., Blank, Reiner, *Managementul stresului: recunoașterea și combaterea eficientă a situațiilor stresante*, (Buncuești: Editura All, 2011), 36

¹³ European Commission - ANNUAL REPORT ON EUROPEAN SMEs 2020/2021, July 2021, available at https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/news/12597/annual-report-on-european-smes-2020-2021/?no_cache=1&cHash=a9eb2e5bfa8a6ec41e05c97cc81a420c, accessed 07.09.2021

✚ 'production' (decrease in the value added of SMEs by 9.8%).

European SMEs have found solutions to mitigate the effects of the pandemic¹⁴: temporary interruption of activity, access to various support programs, available at national level, for the payment of employees' salaries, reduction of working hours, reduction of the number of employees, use of digital tools to be able to operate online, orientation towards online sales.

Regarding the Romanian SMEs in the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of newly established enterprises decreased by 18.09% compared to 2019.¹⁵

Fig. no. 1 Measures taken by entrepreneurs in the first part of 2020

Source: Ovidiu Nicolescu (coordonator), Stefan-Florin Corcodel, Petre Simion Cezar, Ciprian Nicolescu, Uritu Daniel, Cristof Camelia - Carta Albă a IMM-urilor din Romania din 2020

Romania has approximately 500,000 SMEs, 99% of all companies in the economy. In April 2020, close to the onset of the pandemic in Romania, from an average of 12,000-14,000 newly established companies per month, it had reached only 2,500 newly established SMEs¹⁶.

The Romanian authorities will support the economy this pandemic year as well¹⁷.

To cope with the stressors of the COVID-19 pandemic, Romanian SMEs have resorted to measures such as: technical unemployment for employees, deferral of taxes, deferral of rent payments, access to subsidized loans, deferral of payment of loans to banks and other measures, as they are presented in Fig. no 1.¹⁸

¹⁴ European Commission - ANNUAL REPORT ON EUROPEAN SMEs 2020/2021, July 2021, available at https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/news/12597/annual-report-on-european-smes-2020-2021/?no_cache=1&cHash=a9eb2e5bfa8a6ec41e05c97cc81a420c, accessed 07.09.2021

¹⁵ <https://www.zf.ro/supliment-zf-imm-2021/radiografia-imm-urilor-din-romania-cate-au-aparut-si-cate-au-20106569>

¹⁶ <https://www.zf.ro/supliment-zf-imm-2021/radiografia-imm-urilor-din-romania-cate-au-aparut-si-cate-au-20106569>

¹⁷ Banca Națională a României - România – Zona Euro Monitor. O redresare economică dificilă a început, lupta cu pandemia continuă, Nr. 6 | An 3 | 2021, 10

¹⁸ Ovidiu Nicolescu (coordonator), Stefan-Florin Corcodel, Petre Simion Cezar, Ciprian Nicolescu, Uritu Daniel, Cristof Camelia - Carta Albă a IMM-urilor din Romania din 2020

Many entrepreneurs, many SMEs have been affected by the pandemic, because SMEs have fewer resources than large enterprises. The challenges they have had to face are ¹⁹:

- ❖ delays in paying customers;
- ❖ lack of access to support from state authorities;
- ❖ uncertainty of the economic, social environment;
- ❖ concerns about one's own health, that of the family, of the employees;
- ❖ limited social contact;
- ❖ isolation;
- ❖ limited state support;
- ❖ decreasing the mental well-being of entrepreneurs.

The uncertainty and stress that accompanies this pandemic reduces the ability of entrepreneurs around the world to withstand all the challenges they face.²⁰

The researchers, questioning more than 5,000 entrepreneurs from 23 countries, concluded the following ²¹:

- 39.7% of entrepreneurs feel high levels of uncertainty for their own business;
- 57.7% of entrepreneurs are concerned about their health and family;
- only 32% of entrepreneurs received support, 28% receiving financial support;
- 48.8% of entrepreneurs were affected by social distancing from the pandemic, by working from a distance;
- 61% of entrepreneurs saw their business threatened, the SME in pandemic, the stress affecting the care for oneself, for the employees, for the business in general;
- 50% of entrepreneurs have found enough time to recover from the stress of work.

Stress can make anyone sick at any age. Illnesses can be: aggression, nervousness, sleep disorders, but also serious illnesses: depression, stomach pain, back pain, burnout syndrome ²². But stress can be avoided, diminished, by applying Stress Management, which involves the use of specific methods and techniques by which stress symptoms are recognized and treated appropriately or, the easiest and lowest cost option: preventing the onset of stress, so that diseases are avoided.

Only if we are healthy can we create added value, can we build successful businesses, can we help our fellow men, especially in this period of health crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic.

The application of Stress Management starts from knowing the causes of stress, from acquiring knowledge about time management, learning relaxation techniques, individual counseling. Time management is important for stress diminution. Positive thinking, which involves looking at any difficult situation with optimism, with confidence that we will solve it. A healthy lifestyle will help us cope with the stressors, which are more and more,

¹⁹ Ute Stephan, Przemysław Zbierowski, Ana Pérez-Luño and Anna Klausen - Entrepreneurship during the Covid-19 Pandemic: A global study of entrepreneurs' challenges, resilience, and well-being, KBS Covid-19 Research Impact Papers, No. 4, 2021

²⁰ Ute Stephan, Przemysław Zbierowski, Ana Pérez-Luño and Anna Klausen - Entrepreneurship during the Covid-19 Pandemic: A global study of entrepreneurs' challenges, resilience, and well-being, KBS Covid-19 Research Impact Papers, No. 4, 2021

²¹ Ute Stephan, Przemysław Zbierowski, Ana Pérez-Luño and Anna Klausen - Entrepreneurship during the Covid-19 Pandemic: A global study of entrepreneurs' challenges, resilience, and well-being, KBS Covid-19 Research Impact Papers, No. 4, 2021

²² Schröder, Jörg-Peter., Blank, Reiner, *Managementul stresului: recunoașterea și combaterea eficientă a situațiilor stresante*, (Buncuești, Editura All, 2011), 41

especially in this endless pandemic. Knowing and applying relaxation exercises at work helps us whenever we feel stressed.²³

Applying Stress Management in SMEs, helps employees, entrepreneurs and brings profitability to the companies in which it is applied. Leads to organizational change as²⁴:

- ✓ correlation of employees' capabilities with the required work to be submitted;
- ✓ clear responsibilities for each employee;
- ✓ good communication between employees, but also between them and managers;
- ✓ adequate resolution of conflicts.
- ✓ management of measures regarding the spread of the virus in a pandemic;
- ✓ application of time management;
- ✓ implementing knowledge management, encouraging employees to knowledge, education;
- ✓ facilitating access to medical services.

CONCLUSIONS

SMEs are the backbone of the global economy. The COVID-19 pandemic, through the major stress it has generated around the world, has made the work of entrepreneurs, which is extremely demanding in general, increasingly stressful. The stress of the work of entrepreneurs must not go unnoticed, because if it is not removed or at least mitigated it can lead to exhaustion. We do not forget the fact that the survival and development of any SME in this world is based on a physically and mentally healthy entrepreneur and employees, optimistic, confident in the future.

The application of Stress Management starts from knowing the causes of stress, from acquiring knowledge about time management, learning relaxation techniques, individual counseling. Time management is important for stress relief. Positive thinking, a healthy lifestyle will help us cope with the stressors, which are more and more, especially in this endless pandemic. Knowing and applying relaxation exercises at work helps us whenever we feel stressed.

Applying Stress Management in SMEs, helps employees, entrepreneurs and brings profitability to the companies in which it is applied. It leads to beneficial organizational changes, but most importantly, it prevents the onset of stress and significantly reduces the effects of stress once installed.

²³ Borcoși, Corina Ana, Managementul stresului – metode și tehnici de combatere a stresului, Annals of the „Constantin Brâncuși” University of Târgu Jiu, Letter and Social Science Series, Supplement 3/2017, 145-150

²⁴ Borcoși, Corina Ana, *Managementul stresului – metode și tehnici de combatere a stresului...*, 145-150

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BRIEF CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE SPECIFICITY OF TRADE RELATIONS BETWEEN CONSUMERS AND TRADERS REGARDING TRAVEL TOURIST SERVICES

Elise-Nicoleta VÂLCU¹

ABSTRACT:

THE RESERVATION OF TOURIST PACKAGES OF TRAVEL SERVICES AND ASSOCIATED TRAVEL SERVICES CONFERS WELL-DEFINED RIGHTS TO CONSUMERS IN ADVANCE, DURING THE RESERVATION AND THROUGHOUT THE VACATION.

IN THE FOLLOWING, WE MENTION SUCH RIGHTS CONFERRED TO THE CONSUMER: THE RIGHT TO PRE-CONTRACTUAL INFORMATION, THE RIGHTS DERIVING FROM THE RESPONSIBILITY OF THE OPERATOR / ORGANIZER FOR THE PROPER FUNCTIONING OF THE TRAVEL SERVICES INCLUDED IN THE PACKAGE, RESPECTIVELY THE RIGHT TO PROTECTION IN CASE THE ORGANIZER ENTERS INSOLVENCY PROCEEDINGS. THE TOURIST PACKAGES PURCHASED BOTH ONLINE AND THOSE PURCHASED FACE TO FACE, FROM THE MERCHANT WHO ACTS AS AN ORGANIZER OF TOURIST PACKAGES, ARE CONSIDERED.

THESE RIGHTS ARE REGULATED BOTH BY THE LEGISLATION OF THE EUROPEAN UNION BY DIRECTIVE (EU) 2015/2302² REGARDING THE PACKAGES OF TRAVEL SERVICES AND ASSOCIATED TRAVEL SERVICES AS WELL AS BY THE INTERNAL TRANSPOSITION NORM, RESPECTIVELY ORDINANCE NO.2 / 2018 REGARDING THE PACKAGES OF TRAVEL SERVICES AND ASSOCIATED TRAVEL SERVICES, AS WELL AS FOR THE MODIFICATION OF SOME NORMATIVE ACTS³.

KEY WORDS: PACKAGE OF TRAVEL SERVICES, INFORMATION, GUARANTEED LOANS, TERMINATION, LIABILITY

I. INTRODUCTION

In accordance with Article 26 (2) and Article 49 TFEU, the Internal Market of the European Union comprises an area without frontiers in which the free movement of services, goods and the freedom of establishment recognized to nationals are ensured.

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²Directive (EU) 2015/2302 of the European Parliament and of the Council on travel packages and associated travel services, amending Regulation (EC) No 2006/2004 and Directive 2011/83 / EU of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Council Directive 90/314 / EEC, published in the Official Journal of the European Union, L series, no. 326 of 11 December 2015

³Ordinance no. 2/2018 regarding the packages of travel services and associated travel services, as well as for the modification of some normative acts, published in the Official Gazette no. 728 of August 23, 2018

We consider necessary the presence of an adequate national legislation, respectively GO no. 2/2018, harmonized with the union legislation regarding the rights and obligations deriving from the contracts regarding the service packages, in order to support the single union market.

This ordinance establishes the legal framework regarding commercial contracts that have as object packages of travel services and associated travel services concluded between travelers as consumers and traders⁴.

For a better understanding of the specifics of the legal relationship established between the trader and the traveler, as defined by this norm, we consider it opportune to clarify the appropriate terms.

Thus, within the meaning of the ordinance, “trader” means any public or private person who acts, including through another person, for purposes related to his commercial, business, craft or professional activity in connection with contracts the object of this ordinance, as an organizing travel agency, an intermediate travel agency, a trader that facilitates an associated travel service or as a travel service provider ”.⁵

For the generic title of “trader”, specific to commercial relations, the legislator uses the concept of “travel agency”, defining it as the economic operator that holds a valid travel license under the law and which, as the case may be, functions as an *organizing travel agency* or *intermediate travel agency* as follows:

- a) When it behaves as a *travel agency* organizing its commercial activity, it is limited to selling or offering for sale packages either directly or through another trader;
- b) When it behaves as an *intermediate travel agency*, we must identify the presence of an organizing agency, so that the tourist packages will be sold to the traveler by the former, but under the conditions set by the organizing travel agency. “

As mentioned above, the commercial relationship ends between *the trader-travel agency*, on the one hand and *the traveler*, on the other hand. The text of the ordinance defines the term *traveler* as any person who concludes a contract or who has the right to travel based on a *contract regarding the package of travel services*.

Article 2 point 12 of the normative act clarifies the concept of “package” as the combination of at least two different types of travel services intended for the same trip or vacation, if one of the following conditions is met:

- a) The respective services are combined by a single trader and we have, therefore, in view a single contract regarding all the services;
- b) The respective services are purchased based on several contracts concluded separately with several suppliers and which meet the following conditions:
 - b1) were selected before the traveler accepted the payment;
 - b2) are promoted or sold under the name of "package" or under a similar name;
 - b3) are purchased from different merchants by booking online on behalf of the traveler, the payment details and email address being sent from the merchant with whom the first contact is concluded to the other merchants and contractually it is concluded with the latter no later than 24 hours after confirmation of booking the first travel service.

⁴“ This ordinance does not apply to: a) packages and associated travel services that last less than 24 hours except in situations where they include overnight accommodation; b) travel packages and services associated with the facility occasionally and on a non-profit basis and only to a small group of travelers; c) packages and associated travel services purchased for the organization of a business trip, concluded between a trader and another natural or legal person acting for reasons related to his commercial activity, business, trade or profession. ”, see in this meaning, art.2 paragraph 2 of Government Ordinance no.2 / 2018

⁵ See art.3 paragraph 2 point 4 of Ordinance no.2 / 2018

The categories of services regulated by this ordinance are classified as follows:

- i) *Travel service*, which represents:
 - i.1) passenger transport
 - i.2) accommodation (other than residence)
 - i.3) car rental, etc.

Associated travel service which involves the existence of at least two types of travel services purchased for the same trip or holiday, which is not a package and which involves several contracts concluded separately with individual travel service providers if at least one of traders facilitates one of the following options:

- ii.1) the traveler selects and pays separately for each travel service;
- ii.2) the traveler purchases, in a personalized way, an additional travel service with a second trader, within 24 hours at the latest since the confirmation of the reservation of the first travel service with a first trader.

II. THE RIGHTS TRAVELERS / CONSUMERS BENEFIT FROM, WITHIN THE CONTRACT REGARDING THE PACKAGE OF TRAVEL SERVICES

A. *Before concluding the commercial contract for travel services, the travel agency is obliged to provide the traveler with standard information, such as:*

- a) The destination / destinations of the trip, the itinerary, and in case the accommodation is included, the number of nights included;
- b) Means of transport / its characteristics, places, dates and times of departure / return;
- c) Location / main characteristics (example, tourist classification according to the norms of the destination country / meal services offered / excursions, visits included in the agreed price / language in which information about services will be provided at the destination of the holiday / identification data of the organizing agency or of the intermediate agency, as the case may be (phone number, email address, etc.))
- d) The total price of the package including commissions, fees, penalties, additional costs, and when these cannot be reasonably established, prior to the conclusion of the contract, the agency is obliged to provide unequivocal indications on possible additional costs / payment methods (advance and schedule payment of the balance or any financial guarantees to be paid by the traveler)
- e) General information regarding the travel documents / deadlines for obtaining visas.
- f) Information regarding the possibility of the traveler of unilateral denunciation at any time before the beginning of the execution of the contract, concretely identifying the payment of penalties / unilateral denunciation of the travel agency.

Thus, according to the provisions of Article 13, if the traveler terminates the contract or withdraws before the start⁶ of the execution of the package, he may be obliged to pay to the travel agency a *termination penalty* which must be proven to be adequate and justifiable. In practice, in most cases, contracts provide for *reasonable standardized termination penalties* depending on the time of termination of the contract, before the execution of the package.

If no standardized penalties are expressly provided, their value is to be calculated in relation to the package price.

⁶ The moment of starting the execution of the package represents the moment of starting the execution of the travel services included in the package; see in this sense, art.3 point 9 of Government Ordinance no.2 / 2018

At the request of the traveler, the travel agency has the obligation to justify the amount of penalties calculated and applied as an effect of the termination of the contract before the execution of the package.

By way of derogation⁷, the traveler has the right to terminate the contract before the start of the execution of the package without paying any termination penalty in case of "unavoidable and extraordinary circumstances" that occur at the destination... and which significantly affect the execution of the package... ", Such as in the case of serious security issues at the destination which are likely to affect the package, etc. In the latter case, the traveler has the right to a full refund of the package price without being able to request additional compensation⁸.

The travel agency also has the right to unilaterally terminate the contract and implicitly to reimburse in full the cost of the package without being obliged to pay compensation in the following cases:

- The number of persons registered for the execution of the package is less than the minimum number inserted in the required contract and the agency notifies the traveler about the termination of the contract but not later than:
 - a) 20 days before the start of the package, if the trip lasts more than six days;;
 - b) 7 days before the start of the package, if the trip lasts between two and six days;
 - c) 48 hours before the start of the package, if the trip lasts less than two days;
- The agency cannot perform contractually due to "unavoidable and extraordinary" circumstances exemplified above.

Both in case of *refund*, as a result of the unilateral denunciation by the traveler with retention of penalties by the travel agency, and in case of *full reimbursement* of the value of the package to the traveler, the obligation to pay falls within the agency within 14 days from termination of the contract regarding the package of travel services.

- g) Information regarding the minimum number of persons necessary for the services in the package to be able to be executed with the mention of the consequences "per a contrario";
- h) Information regarding the optional or compulsory insurance to cover the costs of assistance, in case of illness, accident or death, etc.

In addition to the rights enjoyed by the traveler, above-mentioned, he has the right to request information from the travel agency regarding:

- The identification elements (name, registered office) of the responsible entity regarding its protection in case of insolvency;
- Name, address, telephone number, email address of the local representative of the travel agency, to allow the traveler an effective collaboration with him, requesting assistance if necessary or to report any non-compliance notified during the execution of the package.⁹
- Information on alternative dispute resolution (ADR) procedures (SAL)¹⁰

⁷ see in this sense, art.13 point 1 of GO no.2 / 2018

⁸ see in this sense, art.13 point 4 of Government Ordinance no.2 / 2018

⁹ see art.13 paragraph 3 of Government Ordinance no.2 / 2018

¹⁰ For more details see GO no.38 / 2015 on alternative dispute resolution between consumers and traders with subsequent amendments, and as appropriate the online dispute resolution platform under Regulation (EU)

- The intermediate travel agency has the obligation, at the request of the traveler, to ensure without undue delay, the contacting of the organizing travel agency both in the pre-contractual phase and in any phase of its execution.

Regarding the rights enjoyed by the traveler during the execution of the contract, he is entitled to "adequate assistance without undue delay" when in difficulty such as: consular assistance, medical assistance, providing information on local authorities, supporting the traveler in finding alternative travel services, etc.

However, the traveler may be required to pay a reasonable fee for any of the above categories of assistance if he or she has caused "the situation of difficulty intentionally or through his or her own negligence."¹¹

III. THE CONDITIONS FOR MODIFYING THE CLAUSES OF THE CONTRACT REGARDING THE PACKAGE OF TRAVEL SERVICES

The clauses of the contract regarding the travel services can be modified, according to the provisions of article 10 of GO no. 2/2018 when:

i) The traveler transfers the contract regarding the package of travel services to a person in compliance with the conditions stipulated in the contract after notifying the travel agency within a reasonable time, in the sense that the notification submitted on a durable medium and addressed to the economic operator, to be communicated at least seven days before the start of the package. The transferor and the person to whom the contract is transferred are jointly and severally liable for the payment of the balance, commissions and other additional costs generated by this transfer provided that they are reasonable and proven by the travel agency.

ii) If the contract explicitly provides for the possibility of changing the price, the traveler may request its reduction if there are changes generated by:

- a) the price of passenger transport results from the cost of fuels;
- b) the level of fees and commissions applicable to the services to which it refers contractually are established by third parties;
- c) the exchange rate.

For the same reasons mentioned above, the economic agent may request an increase of the contracted package price only if he has previously sent a notification justifying the increase decision based on a calculation, at least 20 days before the start of the package execution.

iii) If the travel agency, before starting the execution of the contract, cannot meet the special conditions required by the traveler, or proposes to increase the package price by more than 8% (increase generated by a) the price of passenger transport results from the cost of fuel ; b) the level of fees and commissions applicable to the services to which it refers contractually are established by third parties; c) the exchange rate), the traveler has the possibility either to accept the price increase or to terminate the contract without paying any penalty. When we remember these last situations, the traveler can accept another offer of the travel agency, of a quality at least equivalent to the initial one)¹².

no.524 / 2013 of the European Parliament and Decision of 21 May 2013 on the online settlement of consumer disputes and amending Regulation (EC) No.2006/2004

¹¹ see art.17 paragraph 2 of Government Ordinance no.2 / 2018

¹² see for more details art.11 paragraph 3 of GO no.2 / 2018

IV. CONSUMER PROTECTION - TRAVELER, IN CASE OF INSOLVENCY OF THE TRADER (TRAVEL AGENCY)

Article 18 of Government Ordinance no. 2/2018 stipulates that the organizing travel agencies established on the Romanian territory offer guarantees regarding the reimbursement of all expenses incurred by travelers or at the expense of travelers, as a result of the insolvency¹³ of the economic operator providing travel services.

The guarantees provided for in Article 18 (1) of GO no. 2/2018 are represented by:

- a) *Letters of bank guarantee*¹⁴. In an applied approach, within the meaning of the provisions of article 2321 of the Civil Code, the bank is the issuer of the letter of guarantee, the organizing travel agency is the author of the letter of guarantee and the Ministry of Tourism is the beneficiary of the letter of bank guarantee. The object of this instrument is the guarantee by the bank of the risk of non-payment by the organizing travel agency of the amounts paid by travelers, caused by the non-execution of all or part of the contracts regarding travel service packages, in case of insolvency of the organizing travel agency.
- b) *Insurance policies*¹⁵. According to Article 3 (5) of the "Guarantee Procedure of 15 January 2019", the insurance policy consists in guaranteeing by the insurance company the risk of non-payment by the travel agency of the amounts paid by passengers, caused by the non-execution in full or partial of the contracts for the sale of travel service packages, in case of insolvency of the organizing travel agency.... ”
- c) *travel package guarantee fund*¹⁶. The travel package guarantee fund represents the private guarantee scheme in the field of tourism, which aims to protect travelers who have purchased packages of travel services or travel services associated with the consequences of the insolvency of the organizing travel agency. The entity is organized as a Romanian joint stock company issuing registered shares, established based on the Companies Law no. 31/90¹⁷. The specificity of the guarantee fund consists in the fact that the shareholders (minimum 10, each holding at most 10% of the voting rights) are the travel agents or traders who facilitate an associated travel service or travel service providers.
- d) *Contract of trust*¹⁸. The trust contract as a guarantee instrument, implies the conclusion in authentic form of a contract between the organizing travel agency as a constituent and a trustee. The trust contract, as a guarantee instrument, has as

¹³ According to the provisions of art.5 paragraph 1 point 29 of Law no.85 / 2014 on insolvency prevention and insolvency procedures, with subsequent amendments and completions “insolvency is that state of the debtor's patrimony the payment of certain, liquid and due debts, as follows: a) the debtor's insolvency is presumed when, after 60 days from the due date, he has not paid his debt to the creditor; the presumption is relative; b) the insolvency is imminent when it is proved that the debtor will not be able to pay at maturity the due debts committed, with the funds available at the maturity date. See for more details and “Guarantee procedures from January 15, 2019” of the amounts paid by travelers in connection with travel service packages / associated travel services in case of insolvency of the organizing travel agency and traveler compensation procedures

¹⁴ The letter of bank guarantee represents the banking instrument by which the guaranteeing bank irrevocably undertakes to pay a certain amount of money to a beneficiary, in case the main debtor will not extinguish his own obligation.

¹⁵ The insurance policy represents the document / guarantee instrument (on electronic support or paper support) that proves the conclusion of an insurance contract and summarizes the clauses of the contract.

¹⁶ see in this sense art.2 point 7 of Government Ordinance no.2 / 2018

¹⁷ Companies law no. 31/90 republished with subsequent amendments and completions

¹⁸ According to art.773 of the updated civil code “trust is the legal operation by which one or more constituents transfer real rights, debt rights, guarantees or other patrimonial rights or a set of such rights, present or future, to one or more trustees

beneficiary the traveler, in the sense that if the latter has bought a package of travel services thus guaranteed, and is in the situation where the services paid as a result of upon entering the insolvency of the agency, the trustee will: a) return to the traveler the amount paid by him to the organizing agency, b) either pay the package instead of the agency for the traveler to continue to benefit from travel services, c) or pay the traveler's repatriation (transport and accommodation, if applicable)¹⁹.

e) other legally constituted guarantee instruments, etc.

Specifically, if the travel package was guaranteed by an insurance policy, in case of insolvency of the travel agency, according to article 3 of the "Guarantee Procedure", the insurance company undertakes that within a maximum of 12 hours upon receipt of the notification made by the traveler:

- to ensure to him, through an operator, his repatriation with the support of all the expenses incurred;
- to offer alternative services for the continuation of the package, such as changing the accommodation by offering in a unit equivalent to the initial one in the offer or of superior quality to the first one;
- if the traveler pays from his own funds the repatriation expenses, the insurance company has the obligation to reimburse their cost.

In conclusion, regardless of the type of guarantee, they cover:

- 1) *Refunds at the request of the traveler* (if the travel service was not performed by the travel agency);
- 2) *Similarly Travel services (holiday)*;
- 3) *Repatriation costs*²⁰ (if applicable, including the cost of accommodation before repatriation).

Regarding the need to protect the traveler, the normative act regulates the ways in which the funds and activities of tourism providers are supervised, as follows:

1. In order to obtain the tourism license, the agency has the obligation to prove the establishment of a guarantee instrument (guarantee fund)
2. The share capital of an economic operator organized as a limited liability company, holder of a tourism license for the organization activity, may not be less than 25,000 lei.²¹
3. The agencies have the obligation to periodically transmit to the Ministry of Tourism information regarding the activity carried out.
4. The current activity of a travel agency is subject to the supervision and control of the National Authority for Consumer Protection, the European Consumer Center in Romania²² or the alternative dispute resolution entities²³.

¹⁹ see for more details art.5 paragraph (2) of "Guarantee procedures from January 15, 2019"

²⁰ Represents "reasonable expenses incurred by the traveler or expenses incurred by the issuer of the guarantee instrument for returning to the place of departure or to the place agreed for delivery" see in this sense art.1 paragraph 1 point 2 of the "Guarantee procedures from 15 January 2019" of the amounts paid by travelers in connection with the packages of travel services / associated travel services in case of insolvency of the organizing travel agency and the procedures for compensating travelers

²¹ See in this sense art. 20 paragraph 2 of GO no. 2/2018 corroborated with art. 11 paragraph 1 of the Companies Law no. 31/1990 republished, with subsequent amendments and completions

²² When travel packages are purchased from organizing travel agencies established in another Member State of the European Union.

²³ According to the provisions of GO no. 38/2015 regarding the alternative settlement of disputes between consumers and traders with subsequent amendments

CONCLUSIONS

Although we are discussing the presence of EU legislation in the field of analysis, national transposing legislation, disparities between national rules are an element that discourages travelers from a particular EU Member State to purchase travel packages and associated travel services. from another Member State.

We believe that the Member States must make an additional combined effort so that travelers, consumers of tourist packages, benefit from the advantages of the internal market throughout the European Union.

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2. Law no. 85/2014 on insolvency prevention and insolvency procedures, with subsequent amendments and completions
3. Government Ordinance no. 38/2015 on the alternative settlement of disputes between consumers and traders with subsequent amendments, and as the case may be the online dispute resolution platform under Regulation (EU) no. 524/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2013 on the online settlement of consumer disputes and amendment of Regulation (EC) no. 2006/2004 Ordinance no. 2/2018 regarding the packages of travel services and associated travel services, as well as for the modification of some normative acts, published in the Official Gazette no. 728 of August 23, 2018
4. “Guarantee procedures from January 15, 2019” of the amounts paid by travelers in connection with the package of travel services / associated travel services in case of insolvency of the organizing travel agency and the procedures for compensating travelers, published in the Official Gazette no.76 from January 30, 2019

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THE EFFECT OF GEMS PROGRAM ON THE BASIC SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS AND ATTITUDES OF 6TH GRADE STUDENTS IN THE FORCE AND MOTION UNIT

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ABSTRACT:

THE AIM OF THIS STUDY IS TO INVESTIGATE THE EFFECT OF GEMS GREAT EXPLORATION IN MATH AND SCIENCE (GEMS) SCIENCE AND MATHEMATICS PROGRAM ON STUDENTS' BASIC SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS AND ATTITUDES IN THE 6TH GRADE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL "FORCE AND MOTION" UNIT THE EFFECTS OF THE PROGRAM AND TO GET THEIR OPINIONS. THE SAMPLE OF THE STUDY WAS A GROUP CONSISTING OF 80 6TH GRADE MIDDLE SCHOOL STUDENTS, ONE EXPERIMENTAL (N = 40) AND ONE CONTROL (N = 40) GROUP. IN ORDER TO DETERMINE THE LEVELS OF STUDENTS' BASIC SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS AND ATTITUDES, BASIC SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS SCALE FOR "FORCE AND MOTION" (BSPST) SCIENCE COURSE ATTITUDE SCALE (SCAS) WERE APPLIED TO BOTH GROUPS AS A PRE AND POST-TEST. WHEN THE BSPST POST-TEST SCORES OF THE EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP STUDENTS WERE COMPARED ACCORDING TO THE RESULTS OBTAINED FROM THE DATA COLLECTION TOOLS, IT WAS CLEAR THAT THE BASIC SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS LEVELS OF THE EXPERIMENTAL GROUP STUDENTS IMPROVED MORE. ACCORDING TO SCAS RESULTS; WHEN THE POST- TEST ATTITUDE SCORES OF THE EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUPS WERE EXAMINED AFTER THE APPLICATION, THE ATTITUDES OF THE EXPERIMENTAL GROUP STUDENTS TOWARDS THE ACTIVITIES DONE IN THE SCIENCE COURSE WERE MORE POSITIVE IN THE 1-MONTH PERIOD FROM THE PRE-TEST TO THE LAST TEST THANKS TO THE GEMS ACTIVITIES.,

KEY WORDS: GEMS, SCIENCE EDUCATION, BASIC SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS

INTRODUCTION

The rapid developments in our age have led to the increase of scientific knowledge exponentially, and upon this, the difficulties in accessing scientific information, explaining,

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and using it in daily life have come to the fore more. In some cases, traditional training methods are not sufficient to overcome these difficulties. In line with this need, innovative teaching approaches have emerged⁴. In recent years, a lot of research has been made to increase the content and efficiency of educational programs. In particular, studies on combining science and mathematics have accepted basic science processes as a common point and many projects have been developed in this direction. One of the important examples of these projects is Great Exploration in Math and Science (GEMS) Science and Mathematics Program⁵.

The GEMS combines science and mathematics to provide students with an interest in science and mathematics with fun activities, enabling students to gain all processes of science through effective learning and critical thinking, independent learning, they learned to draw conclusions, analysis and synthesis, developing skills such as questioning innovative activity, is a program⁶. The GEMS Program, which is implemented in many countries of the world, offers a wide spectrum from preschool to high school with its applications including contemporary learning approaches. As a starting point, the child should be encouraged to explore and understand the world as a scientist from birth and to apply learning methods by the principle of life long learning; it is a constantly evolving program with an international network of guidance books, seminars, and courses for educators and families⁷. GEMS was first created in 1984 by the LHS Law of Hall of Science (LHS) science center at the University of California⁸. It is used as a highly flexible enrichment program to deepen the learning of children and to support the use of children's learning. The number of qualifications included in the GEMS program can be processed in a long time and at different grade levels as the content increases. Nationwide's tested in thousands of class GEMS programs, teachers more guides and manuals also developed 70 for, students offer learning experience and a wide range of learning benefits until high school seniors from pre-school⁹. In addition to this, training courses, trainers, and seminars including educators and families are being revised continuously by an international communication network¹⁰.

The activities in the guidelines are flexible enough to address multiple grade levels according to the curriculum of the country or region that will use it. The guides provide teachers with detailed information on how to proceed, the materials, and methods to use. It also contributes to teachers by offering practical ways in classroom practices, suggestions for

⁴ Tekbiyık, A.. *Science Teachers' Expectations from Parents: To What Degree Do Parents Think They Satisfy Such Expectations?* Stanisław Juszcyk: 2013,202.

⁵ Sarıtaş, R. *Concept acquisition and the effectiveness of the GEMS (great exploration in math and science) science and mathematics program adapted to the ministry of education pre-school education program in preparing six-year-old kindergarten students for primary education.* (Published master's thesis). Gazi University, Ankara: 2013.

⁶ Barber, J., Bergman, L., Hosoume, K., Sneider, C. I., Stage, E., &Willard, C. *Great explorations in math and science: gems teacher's handbook.* Berkeley, CA: Lawrence Hall of Science, University of California:1988

⁷ Barrett, K., Blinderman, E., Boffen, B., Echols, J., House, P. A., Hosoume, K., &Kopp, J. *ScienceandMath ExplorationsforYoungChildren: A GEMS/PEACHES, HandbookforEarlyChildhoodEducators, childcare providers, and parents.* Great Explorations in MathandScience (GEMS), Lawrence Hall of Science University of California, Berkeley:1999.

⁸ Bergman, L. *Great Explorations in math and science.* Educational Effectiveness of GEMS:2012

⁹ Seaborg, T., G. *Leader'sHandbook.* The University Of Berkeley, LawrenceHall Of Science, California:1988.

¹⁰ Barrett, K., Blinderman, E., Boffen, B., Echols, J., House, P. A., Hosoume, K., &Kopp, J. *ScienceandMath ExplorationsforYoungChildren: A GEMS/PEACHES.* Handbook for Early Childhood Educators, childcare providers and parents. Great Explorations in MathandScience (GEMS), Lawrence Hall of Science University of California, Berkeley:1999.

material supply, and different perspectives. Teachers can use the ready-made GEMS units to adapt them to the students and develop their own GEMS designs ¹¹

GEMS is an approach that encourages students to work together and provide environments for finding solutions to mysterious activities ¹². Therefore, it has traces of multiple intelligences theory in terms of adopting both constructivist theory and interdisciplinary transitions ¹³. Also, activities in this approach; it has the flexibility to be tailored for students with different intelligence, abilities, knowledge levels, or learning styles. In the program, a process-based assessment is conducted and the products and scientific skills of children are evaluated throughout the process ^{14,15}. In the GEMS program, students evaluate the permanence of the information they have learned, where the assessment is not bound to a certain standard. The most important element here is that evaluation is a process evaluation and alternative measurement and evaluation tools are used ¹⁶. The most obvious feature of GEMS activities is that it incorporates guided discovery based on scientific inquiry. In the guided exploration approach, the active participation of students for effective learning is emphasized, where the aim is to make the students feel the basic science process skills directly ¹⁷

GEMS activities prepared in line with the constructivist approach are integrated into the National Education Program and the objective of the program is to transfer the basic skills in the courses such as basic science process skills, meta-cognitive skills, and mathematics and science to students through GEMS activities. Basic Science process skills that are effective in developing students' high-level skills are directly related to GEMS activities ¹⁸

"Basic skills that facilitate learning in Science, gain research paths and methods, enable students to be active, improve the sense of responsibility on their own learning and increase the permanence of learning are called science process skills" ¹⁹. According to the American Association of Advancing Science (A.A.A.S.), the basic science process skills are classification, measuring, making observations, using numbers, saving data, making

¹¹ Yalçın, F., & Terbiyik, A. *The effects of the project approach supported with gems based activities on children's conceptual development in early childhood education*. Turkish Studies International Periodical For The Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic: 2013, 8(9), 2375-2399

¹² Uyanik, O., & Kandır, A. *Adaptation of the Kaufman Survey of Early Academic and Language Skills to Turkish Children Aged 61 to 72 Months*. Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice: 2014 14(2), 682-692.

¹³ Sağlam, K. *Great Inventions of Science and Mathematics Program (GEMS: Great Explorations in Math and Science) efficiency analysis: A special case of primary school*. (Published master's thesis). Marmara University, İstanbul: 2012

¹⁴ Barber, J., Bergman, L., Hosoume, K., Sneider, C. I., Stage, E., & Willard, C. *Great explorations in math and science: gems teacher's handbook*. Berkeley, CA: Lawrence Hall of Science, University of California: 1988.

¹⁵ Barrett, K., Blinderman, E., Boffen, B., Echols, J., House, P. A., Hosoume, K., & Kopp, J. *Science and Math Explorations for Young Children: A GEMS/PEACHES*. Handbook for Early Childhood Educators, childcare providers, and parents. Great Explorations in Math and Science (GEMS), Lawrence Hall of Science, University of California, Berkeley: 1999

¹⁶ Barber, J. *Insights & Outcomes: Assessments for Great Explorations in math and science*. LHS GEMS. Great Explorations in math and science, University of California, Lawrence Hall of Science, Berkeley, CA 94720-5200.

¹⁷ Barrett, K., Blinderman, E., Boffen, B., Echols, J., House, P. A., Hosoume, K., & Kopp, J. *Science and Math Explorations for Young Children: A GEMS/PEACHES*. Handbook for Early Childhood Educators, childcare providers, and parents. Great Explorations in Math and Science (GEMS), Lawrence Hall of Science, University of California, Berkeley: 1999

¹⁸ Bergman, L. *Great Explorations in math and science. Educational Effectiveness of GEMS*. 2012.

¹⁹ Çepni, S., Ayas, A., Johnson, D., & Turgut, M. F. *Physics teaching*. Ankara: YÖK / World Bank National Education Development Project, Pre-Service Teacher Training. 1996.

predictions, and using space/time relationships^{20,21} When students begin to like mathematics and science they lay the first foundations of scientific thought through the fun activities of the GEMS Programme. While Science and nature studies in the GEMS Programme provide students facility of hands-on, observing, and exploring learning it also leads to gain basic science process skills. Students learn to research and observe themselves and discover knowledge through their own experience. GEMS subjects are prepared according to the usage of the basic science process skills of students²²

In the GEMS activities, students can^{23,24}

- observe with all senses and conclude according to observations.
- associate new situations and knowledge with old experiences.
- compare events and objects according to similarities and the differences in their qualitative and quantitative properties.
- organize, classify, and group objects and knowledge.
- be an active participant by touching, drawing, playing, questioning, communicating, sharing in the process.
- explore by playing games and experimenting.
- make intelligent predictions about the outcomes of events.
- gain basic science process skills such as applying new situations and drawing conclusions by interpreting information and methods.

GEMS activities provide students to use all basic science process skills to make their learning permanent, thus improving the quality and qualification of education as well as gaining students life long learning skills²⁵

This study aims to investigate the effect of the GEMS Program which prepared for 6th-grade force and motion unit on students' basic science process skills and attitudes towards scientific method and opinions about the GEMS Programme.

METHOD

In this study, the “Pre-Test-Post-Test Semi-Experimental Test with Control Group which is within the scope of experimental research design was used (Balçı, 2015). There is a control group created by a neutral assignment and an experimental group. Pre-test and post-test are applied to both groups. The pattern adopted in the study is presented in Table1.

²⁰ Esler, K. *Teaching Elementary Science*. Florida Technological University Publication. 1997

²¹ Padilla, M. J., Okey, J. R., & Garrard, K. *The effects of instruction on integrated science process skill achievement*. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*:1984, 21(3), 277-287.

²² Bergman, L. *Great Explorations in math and science*. Educational Effectiveness of GEMS. 2012.

²³ Barrett, K., Blinderman, E., Boffen, B., Echols, J., House, P. A., Hosoume, K., & Kopp, J. *Science and Math Explorations for Young Children: A GEMS/PEACHES*. Handbook for Early Childhood Educators, childcare providers, and parents. Great Explorations in Math and Science (GEMS), Lawrence Hall of Science, University of California, Berkeley:1999

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²⁵ Sağlam, K. *Great Inventions of Science and Mathematics Program (GEMS: Great Explorations in Math and Science) efficiency analysis: A special case of primary school*. (Published master's thesis). Marmara University, İstanbul:2012

Table 1. Experimental Design of the Study

Groups	Pre Test	Practice	Post Test
Experimental Group	BSPST, SCAS	SEC+ GEMS Teaching and	Supported BSPST, SCAS
Control Group	BSPST, SCAS	SEC	BSPST, SCAS

SEC: Science Education Curriculum; GEMS: Great Explorations in Mathematics and Science; BSPST: Basic Science Process Skills Test SCAS: Science Course Attitude Scale

The study groups of the research consisted of the 6th-grade students attending a secondary school located in the Altınordu district of Ordu province in the fall semester of the 2016-2017 academic year. Work with experimental groups to the secondary community and Grade 6 SEC MEB adapted GEMS Program administered 40 students, while the control group; 40 students do not apply the GEMS Program to the same secondary school. From to provide the internal validity group SEC teachers to be integrated to fit the prepared GEMS program to continue the control group MEB the meb learning teacher and allowed to do a different application. MEB 6 class SEC adapted GEMS was administered to one group.

Data Collection Tools

The research has a quasi-experimental nature. The research model, pre-test, and post-test were made with a quasi-experimental design with a control group. Basic Science Process Skills Test, Science Course Attitude Scale, were used as data collection tools.

A literature review was conducted for the development of "BSPST"^{26 27 28 29 30} scales. Later SEC Located 6th grade "Force and Motion" gap-filling considering the gains of the topic in the unit, multiple-choice, matching, right-wrong, and classic that trial substances consisting of questions were written. Item form for a trial form is in the software stage; 6th-grade science textbook and 6th-grade science workbook, leaf test, and question bank, science teaching teacher books³¹ were used. To ensure the content validity of the scale, a field educator and 3 experienced science teachers working in the MEB were consulted and evaluated in terms of scope and format. Within the framework of expert opinions, some questions were removed from the scale and some were corrected. Thus, a scale of 31 items consisting of 14 questions was created. For the pilot application of the experimental form, the students who have learned about force and motion were selected in the 6th grade science course. For this purpose, the pilot application of the 31-item trial form was applied to 6th

²⁶ Burns, J. C., Okey, J. R., & Wise, K. C. *Development of an integrated process skill test: TIPS II*. Journal of Research in Science Teaching:1985, 22(2), 169-177.

²⁷ Enger, S. K., & Yager, R. (Eds.) *The Iowa Assessment Handbook*. Iowa: University of Iowa:1988.

²⁸ Tatar, N. *The effect of inquiry-based learning approaches in the education of science in primary school on the science process skills, academic achievement, and attitude*. (Published doctoral dissertation). Gazi University, Ankara:2006

²⁹ Hazır, A. & Türkmen, L. *Scientific Process Skill Levels of Primary School 5th Grade Students*. Selçuk University Journal of Ahmet Keleşoğlu Education Faculty:2008 26,81-96.

³⁰ Aydoğdu, B., Tatar, N., Yıldız, E., & Buldur, S. *The science process skills scale development for elementary school students*. Journal of Theoretical Educational Science: 2012, 5(3), 292-311

³¹ Kesmez, A. *Force And Motion. Science Teaching Laboratory Applications-I*. Science and Technology, Erzurum:2010 193-220.

grade (n =200) students randomly selected in two secondary schools in the 2016-17 academic year. The first is 80 (n = 80) students in a secondary school in Fatsa, Ordu, and the second is 120 (n = 120) students in a secondary school in Durağan, Sinop. Pilot study data were analyzed with SPSS 22.00 program. The item difficulty and discriminative indices of each question obtained as a result of the analysis of the final version of the test were calculated and a 25-item scale consisting of 12 questions was formed. 25 items from BSPST we have KR-20 reliability coefficient of 0.8174 was found reliable. The average difficulty of the scale was determined as 0.38. It is seen that the items that make up the test are of medium difficulty³². As a result of the experts and the analysis, the validity and reliability of the scale were determined to be able to measure the gains in the “Force and Motion” unit. Reliability testing basic science process skills tested in the 2017-2018 academic year in the district in the 6th-grade level Altınordu front of the students was applied as pre-test and post test. Table 2 shows how the 12 questions in the Basic Science Process Skills Test for the Force and Motion Unit are represented according to the steps of the basic science process skills.

Table 2. Distribution of basic science process skills according to the test items.

Basic Science Process Skills	Question Numbers in “Basic Science Process Skills Test for Force and Motion Unit”
Observation	12
Classification	9
Measuring	4, 7, 8, 10
Data Interpretation	3, 5, 7, 8, 11, 12
Space / Time Relations	4, 7, 8, 10, 12

It is aimed to measure the attitudes of students towards science course and Nuhuğlu’s (2008) attitude towards Science and Technology course has been used. This scale is a 2-topic scale that measures the students 'attitudes towards science and Technology course and the students' interests and attitudes towards the activities included in this course. The scale is a 3-point Likert type and consists of 20 items in total. 6 for SCAS's studies on validity and reliability, 7th and 8th adapted from the classroom³³. In the results of the analysis, the reliability of KR-20 internal consistency multiple was calculated as 0.8739. As a result, it has been decided that the substances in the test used in the research will be used without any change. The scale was applied to students to be pre-test and final test.

Data Collection and Analysis

Statistical analysis of all the data obtained by the evaluation of the “Basic Science Process Skills Test” and “Attitude Scale” conducted before and after application to the groups was carried out with the help of the SPSS 22.00 package program. In the light of the data received from the BSPST, descriptive analysis was conducted for each level and group separately. Students' average scores for each SPS level were translated and interpreted as a percentage. Before statistical analysis, data distributions of BSPST and SCAS were examined and dependent and Independent t-test was applied according to the characteristics of the targets and groups to be measured.

³² Hasaıcebi, B., Terzi, Y., & Kuuk, Z. *Madde guluk indeksi ve madde ayırt edicilik indeksine dayalı elidirici analizi*. Gmşhane niversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstits Dergisi:2020 10(1), 224-240

³³ Nuhuėlu, H. *The Development of an Attitude Scale for Science and Technology Course*. Elementary Education Online:2008 7(3), 627-639.

FINDINGS

In this section, the data collection tools of the research are “BSPST” and “SCAS” of Middle School 6th students statistical analysis results of the data obtained from the applicatio. The statistical between the experimental group where GEMS-based courses were administered and the control group where program-based courses were administered was tested in terms of BSPST pre-test scores.

Table 3. Independent T-Test Results Comparing Pre-Test BSPST Scores of Test and Control Groups.

Groups	n	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Experimental Group	40	42.3250	10.74265	-.010	.992
Control group	40	42.3500	12.15614		

As shown in Table 3, there was no statistical difference between the preliminary test scores of the test and control groups This is an important finding for the research, showing that groups before implementation were equivalent groups in terms of pre-test scores. BSPST post-test points of experiment and control groups were analysed descriptively. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Independent t-Test Results Comparing The Post -Test BSPST Scores of Experimental And Control Groups.

Groups	n	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Experimental Group	40	70.7000	12.68595	6.177	.000
Control Group	40	53.9250	11.57891		

When Table 4 is examined, it is seen that the arithmetic mean of the experiment group is $\bar{X}=70.7000$ and the arithmetic mean of the control group is $\bar{X}=53.9250$. Between groups, a significant difference was found in favor of the experimental group ($p<0.05$, $p=.00$). The statistical connection among the pre-test and post-test BSPST point of the control group in which the Program-based courses were processed was tested.

Table 5. Control Group Pre Test and Post Test Results of Dependent t-Test Comparing BSPST Scores.

Control Group	n	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Pre Test	40	42.3500	12.15614	-18.068	.000
Post Test	40	53.9250	11.57891		

According to Table 5, the Pre-test arithmetic mean of the control group is $\bar{X}=42.3500$, post-test arithmetic mean is $\bar{X}= 53.9250$. A significant difference was found between the control group pre-test and final test scores ($p<0.05$, $p=.00$). The statistical connections among pre-test and post-test BSPST scores were tested in the experimental group where the SEC - based and GEMS-supported courses were applied.

Table 6. Experimental Group Pre Test And Post Test Results of Dependent t-Test Comparing BSPST Scores.

Experimental Group	n	\bar{x}	Ss	T	p
Pre Test	40	42.3250	10.74265	-8.418	.000
Post Test	40	70.7000	12.68595		

According to Table 6, there is a significant difference among the test group pre-test and final test scores. Therefore, the applications of GEMS carried out in the Experimental Group. Descriptive analyses of Sub dimensions of BSPST posttest basic science process skills is presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Experimental and Control Group BSPST Sub Dimensions Descriptive Analysis Results.

Basic Science Process Skills	Number of Question	Experimental Group			Control Group		
		\bar{X}	Ss	%	\bar{X}	Ss	%
Observation	2	8.250	3.889	82.5	4.875	4.661	48.75
Classification	1	4.050	1.810	81	2.179	2.269	44
Measuring	4	20.250	5.878	81	12.500	6.304	50
Data Interpretation	6	45.800	12.376	70.4	26.825	10.415	52.5
Space/Time Relations	5	23.1250	7.042	77	15.500	8.243	48.8

According to Table 7, the average score, standard deviation and true answer percentage of the control group on the basic science process skills scale Control group BSPST sub-dimensions as a result of descriptive analysis, “Data Interpretation” sub-dimension was found to be the most accurate answer

According to Table 7, the average score, standard deviation, and true answer percentage of the experimental group Students on the basic science process skills scale. The statistical between the experimental group where the GEMS-based courses were administered and the control group where the program-based courses were tested in terms of SCAS pre-test scores.

Table 8. All groups Pre-Test Results of Independent t-Test Comparing SCAS Scores.

Groups	n	\bar{X}	Ss	T	p
Control Group	40	42.2250	11.99463	-.426	.671
Experimental Group	40	41.2500	8.07576		

As stated in Table 8, there were no significant differences among all groups of pretest scores. This is an important finding and clearly shows that the attitudes of the groups related to the science course are similar to each other before implementation. The statistical relationship between the experimental group where the GEMS-based courses were administered and the control group where the program-based courses were processed was tested in terms of SCAS final-test scores.

Table 9. All groups Post-Test Results of Independent t-Test Comparing SCAS Scores.

Groups	n	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Control Group	40	43.2250	8.72805	1.381	.171
Experimental Group	40	45.5750	6.29158		

As indicated in Table 9, there was no significant difference among all groups for post-test attitude scores. Therefore, it was determined that both groups did not affect increasing the students' attitudes about the science course. The statistical connection among pre-test and final-test SCAS scores of the control group in which the Program-based courses are processed was tested.

Table 10. Dependent t-Test Results Where Control Group Pre-Post Test SCAS Point Are Compared. Pre-Post test comparison Related sample t test results in control group

Control Group	n	\bar{X}	Ss	T	p
Pretest	40	42	.2250	11.99463	-.611 .545
Posttest	40	43	.2250	8.77802	

For the SCAS pre-test, the arithmetic average of the control group is $\bar{X}=42.2250$, post-test arithmetic mean is $\bar{X}=43.2250$. There is no significant difference among the experimental and control groups as shown in Table 10 for the attitude scores of the final test ($p > 0.05$, $p=.545$). The statistical connection among pre-test and posttest SCAS scores was tested in the experimental group where GEMS-supported courses were administered subject to SEC.

Table 11. The Results of The Dependent t-Test in Which The Pre-Test And post-Test Scores of The Experimental Group Are Compared.

Experimental Group	n	\bar{X}	Ss	T	p
Pre Test	40	41.2250	45.5750	-4.343	.000
Post Test	40	45.5750	62.9158		

According to Table 11, the mean pre-test attitude point of the test group before the application is $\bar{X}=41.2500$ and the average of the final test attitude score after the application is $\bar{X}=62.9158$. Performed to determine statistical terms, the difference of the dependent t-test; at $p < 0.05$ level, since the experimental group pre-post test scores there is a significant difference between the attitude, Therefore, their attitudes about science in students of the experimental group conducted practices GEMS in a positive direction can be said to be effective. Content and descriptive analysis results were presented to reveal the opinions of the experimental group students on the GEMS curriculum.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to determine the effect of the GEMS program prepared according to the 6th grade "Force and Motion" unit on students' basic science process skills and attitudes towards the GEMS program. It's especially important to be gained basic science process skills which are the foundation of scientific literacy. In the research BSPST pre-test points of control and experiment group are examined. According to BSPST pre-test points there can't be found a significant difference between groups (see., Table 3). Not having a difference between the groups' pre-test points is a desirable situation. In the research, according to BSPST post-test points of the experiment and control groups, a significant difference is observed in favor of the experimental group in statistical size (see. Table 4). According to the post-test exam which evaluates basic science process skills in the "Force and Motion" unit,

students in the experimental group have been more successful than the students in the control group who took program-based courses. It has been observed a significant difference in students' observation, measuring, classification, number-space relationships and data interpretation skills in the post-tests. That shows the students in the experimental group have been had more increase in s basic science process skills which wanted to be measured. When the literature is examined, in the study conducted ³⁴ who was investigated the effect of a program designed with the activities according to the GEMS approach on the students' basic science process skills showed that a significant difference was observed on observation, modeling, determining variables, drawing conclusion and interpretation skills in post-tests. ³⁵ stated that the GEMS program will have a positive effect to gain basic science process skills in her study. Experiments in GEMS science activities give effective responses to students' feelings of wonder, increase the permanence of theoretical knowledge, and give a chance student to gain basic science process skills with hands on learning³⁶.

There can be seen the positive contribution of GEMS based activities on basic science process skills in the earlier studies^{37,38}

As seen in ^{39,40,41} studies, student-centered and active learning applications such as GEMS provide effective conclusions in developing basic science process skills, valuing the science, and gaining the awareness of these issues while leading the students to investigate and inquiry. In the research, a significant difference has been observed in favor of post-test points between BSPST pre and post-test points for students in the control group in statistical size. Students in the control group were applied activities included in the books approved by MEB and were conducted the experiments by the statements of the teacher. It was assumed that students in the control group have a lower level of success because of not fulfilling the basic elements of basic science process skills and not inquiring. When literature is examined similar result was assumed in ^{42,43,44} studies.

³⁴ Tekbıyık, A., Şeyihođlu, A., Sezen Vekli, G., & Birinci Konur, K. *Influence of a science camp based on active learning on students*. AcademicSocialScienceStudies (JASSS):2013, 6(1), 1383-1406.

³⁵ am, Ő. S. *GEMS Program-great exploration in math and science*. Journal of Research in Education and Teaching:2013 2(2), 148-154.

³⁶ epni, S. *Performansların deđerlendirilmesi*. E.Karip (Ed.), lme ve deđerlendirme iinde (s. 193-239). Ankara: Pegem A: 2007.

³⁷ SarıtaŐ, R. *Concept acquisition and the effectiveness of the GEMS (great exploration in math and science) science and mathematics program adapted to the ministry of education pre-school education program in preparing six-year-old kindergarten students for primary education*. (Published master's thesis). Gazi University, Ankara:2013

³⁸ Yalın, F., & Terbıyık, A. *The effects of the project approach supported with gems based activities on children's conceptual development in early childhood education*. TurkishStudies-International Periodical For The Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic: 2013, 8(9), 2375-2399

³⁹ Kula, Ő. G. *The effect of inquiry-based science learning on the student's science process skills, achievement, concept learning, and attitude*. (Published master's thesis). Marmara University, İstanbul: 2009

⁴⁰ Gnel, M., KabataŐ MemiŐ, E. & Bykkasap, E. *Effects of the Science Writing Heuristic Approach on Primary School Students' Science Achievement and Attitude toward Science Course*. Education and Science: 2010, 23,41-49.

⁴¹ Tekbıyık, A. *Science Teachers' Expectations from Parents: To What Degree Do Parents Think They Satisfy Such Expectations?* Stanisław Juszczyk: 2013,202.

⁴² Tatar, N. *The effect of inquiry-based learning approaches in the education of science in primary school on the science process skills, academic achievement, and attitude*. (Published doctoral dissertation). Gazi University, Ankara:2006.

⁴³ Duban, N. *Conducting science and technology courses through an inquiry-based learning approach in primary education: An action research*. (Published doctoral dissertation). Anadolu University, EskiŐehir: 2008.

In the research, a significant difference has been observed in favor of post-test points between BSPST pre and post-test points for students in the experiment group in statistical size. Since GEMS activities were effective in gaining basic elements of the basic science process skills to students it was observed that SPS levels of the students in the experimental group increased in a month period. But here the teacher who internalizing the processes very well, being equipped, applying the creative activities to students, guiding students and positive attitudes in lessons was effective to gain students SPS in the experimental group. When the literature is examined,⁴⁵ address the importance of the teacher in their studies as well.

When experiment and control groups' pre and post-test results evaluate it is observed a significant difference between the points of both experiment and control groups in statistical size. However, when we compare the groups since the increase in the average mean of the experimental group is better than the control group, it can be said the development of the basic science process skills of the students in the experiment group who took the courses GEMS supported is better than from the students in the control group who took the courses program based.

Experiment and control groups' post-tests sub-dimensions show that students in the experiment group have a better understanding of all sub-dimensions of the basic science process skills than the students in the control group and they answered more accurately the questions in the test. A significant difference was observed between the experiment and control groups' points according to t-test results which evaluates the sub-dimensions of the basic science process skills such as observation, classification, measuring, data prediction, time/ space relationships. Students' points in the experiment group who were conducted GEMS supported education is higher according to the test BSPST which measures the sub-dimensions of SPS. This result shows that students in the experiment group learn the sub-dimensions of basic science process skills such as observation, classification, measuring, data prediction, time/ space relationships better. When literature is examined, stated that alternative teaching methods or the programs that support the curriculum such as GEMS are effective to investigate students' basic science process skills.^{46,47,48}

According to the points of SCAS pre-test points of the students in the experiment and control groups who were involved in the research showed that the groups were equal to each other before the implementation (see., Table 8). It is observed that there is no significant difference between the points of SCAS post-test points of the students in the experiment and the control group (see., Table 9). As a result, it is not observed a significant difference between the attitudes towards science and technology between the experiment group which was conducted with SEC-based and GEMS supported courses, and the control group which was conducted with program-based courses. It is seen that there is no significant difference between the SCAS pre and post-test attitude points for the control group statistically. (see.,

⁴⁴ Yıldırım, M., & Altan, S. T. *Effect of inquiry-based learning approach on primary school pupils' science process skills*. Mustafa Kemal University Journal of Graduate School of Social Sciences:2017,14(38),71-89.

⁴⁵ Yıldırım, M., & Altan, S. T. *Effect of inquiry-based learning approach on primary school pupils' science process skills*. Mustafa Kemal University Journal of Graduate School of Social Sciences: 2017,14(38),71-89.

⁴⁶ Kula, Ş. G. *The effect of inquiry-based science learning on the student's science process skills, achievement, concept learning, and attitude*. (Published master's thesis). Marmara University, İstanbul:2009

⁴⁷ Günel, M., Kabataş Memiş, E. & Büyükkasap, E. *Effects of the Science Writing Heuristic Approach on Primary School Students' Science Achievement and Attitude toward Science Course*. Education and Science:2010,23,41-49.

⁴⁸ Tekbiyık, A. *Science Teachers' Expectations from Parents: To What Degree Do Parents Think They Satisfy Such Expectations?* Stanisław Juszczyk:2013, 202.

Table 10). The techniques or methods used in the implemented studies can negatively affect the students' attitudes in some situations. Studies that take place in a short period and the first encounter of the students with the new method can be shown as reasons among these situations⁴⁹

Statistically, there is a difference between the attitude points of SCAS pre and post-test points of the students in the experiment group (see., Table 11). A positive development was provided with the students' attitudes towards science and technology in the experiment group after implementation thanks to the GEMS activities adapted to SEC compared to before implementation. As a result, it can be stated that GEMS activities increase students' attitudes towards science courses and science activities in a positive way. The teachers who were involved in the study stated that GEMS has an affirmative effect on increasing the students' interests and attitudes to the science course, on to make students compatible with the classroom and also GEMS activities provide to develop a positive attitude towards science course⁵⁰. Put forward that GEMS activities affect students' interests and attitudes towards science courses, studying, and in-class behaviors in a positive way⁵¹.

GEMS approach that builds the foundation of mathematics and science integration besides developing a positive attitude towards lessons will be gained students' basic science process skills which help to solve faced problems and make sense of life⁵².

Investigate students' opinions about GEMS based activities, students stated that activities were enjoyable and interesting, did not force themselves, and were clear and understandable⁵³. Search the ideas and the opinions of candidates of teachers on applying GEMS activities in science education and candidate teachers stated that GEMS activities had positive effects on students and were enjoyable and make learning easy⁵⁴.

According to the research findings and the conclusions, it is seen that the level of basic science process skills of the students who learned the 6th grade "Force and Motion" unit with GEMS activities which adapted to SEC are higher than the level of basic science process skills of students who learned the same subject with Science curriculum based lesson. Students took an opportunity to act like a scientist and had a chance to use observation, measuring, classification, and data prediction in the implemented activities. Furthermore, the research was effected also on observation, measuring, classification, number-space relationships, and data prediction. Statistically, the reason for not having a significant difference in attitude can be attributed to short research time in this kind of researches⁵⁵. It was observed that students who were involved in the GEMS science and mathematics

⁴⁹ Altınışık, S. & Orhan, F. *The effects of the multimedia learning environment on the students' attitudes and achievement in social studies*. Hacettepe University Journal of Education Faculty:2002 23,41-49.

⁵⁰ Yıldırım, M., & Altan, S. T. *Effect of inquiry-based learning approach on primary school pupils' science process skills*. Mustafa Kemal University Journal of Graduate School of Social Sciences:2017, 14(38),71-89.

⁵¹ Sağlam, K. *Great Inventions of Science and Mathematics Program (GEMS: Great Explorations in Math and Science) efficiency analysis: A special case of primary school*. (Published master's thesis). Marmara University, İstanbul:2012

⁵² Çam, Ş. S. *GEMS Program-great exploration in math and science*. Journal of Research in Education and Teaching:2013 2(2), 148-154.

⁵³ Çelik, M., & Tekbiyik, A. *The influence of activities is based on GEMS with the theme of earth crust on the fourth-grade students' conceptual understanding and scientific process skills*. PegemJournal of Education and instruction:2016, 6(3), 303.

⁵⁴ Ceylan, E., & Bozkurt, O. *Effects of gems program on achievement, self efficacy, attitudes, and sciences reasoning capability of preservice science teachers*. Mustafa Kemal University Journal of Social Sciences Institute: 2017, 14(38), 45-70

⁵⁵ Nuhoglu, H. . *The Development of an Attitude Scale for Science and Technology Course*. Elementary Education Online:2008, 7(3), 627-639.

program were more interested in the course and feel enjoyable with the activities, at the end of the implementation an attitude scale applied to the experiment group showed that students had a positive increase on attitudes towards science course.

SUGGESTIONS

According to the results of the research, science and mathematics activities and activities in GEMS Science and mathematics program are more fun for students and make students want to learn more. For this reason, GEMS science and mathematics activities should be included in primary education Curriculums, or at least gems classes should be established at certain times in schools one day of the week and gems activities should be done. Based on GEMS Science and mathematics program, activities for different acquisition and units can be developed and the effectiveness of the activities developed can be examined. GEMS Science and mathematics program can be applied effectively with different disciplines other than science courses. Furthermore, the GEMS Science and mathematics program can be adapted to all levels of Education.

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BEST PRACTICES IN DEVELOPING AN ONLINE ASSESSMENT STRATEGY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Oana Alexandra ALEXA¹

ABSTRACT:

ASSESSMENT IS A CRUCIAL PART OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AND THE VAST MAJORITY OF COURSES RELY ON IT TO DETERMINE WHETHER THEY HAVE BEEN SUCCESSFUL. OVER THE 2020/2021 ACADEMIC YEAR, ALL TEACHING, LEARNING AND EVALUATION ACTIVITIES AT OUR UNIVERSITY WERE CONDUCTED ONLINE. WHILE THIS HAD ALSO BEEN THE CASE FOR THE MAJORITY OF THE SPRING SEMESTER OF THE PREVIOUS YEAR, THE SITUATION WAS ONLY SUPPOSED TO BE TEMPORARY AT THE TIME. THIS ARTICLE AIMS TO IDENTIFY AND PROVIDE PRACTICAL EXAMPLES OF BEST PRACTICES WHICH CAN BE EMPLOYED IN THE CLASSROOM IN ORDER TO DEVELOP A STRATEGY FOR ONLINE ASSESSMENT AS WE ENTER AN ERA OF WIDESPREAD DISTANCE LEARNING.

KEY WORDS: ONLINE ASSESSMENT, STRATEGY, HIGHER EDUCATION, BEST PRACTICES

INTRODUCTION

Up until recently, only a small part of the educational process (assessment included) in Romania had been conducted online, and it usually involved long-distance learners only. Employers would disregard candidates in possession of an online diploma or degree, their main argument being the perceived lower quality of the educational process. Consequently, online teaching, learning and assessment have always struggled for recognition, as direct teacher-student interaction and paper-based testing have been the gold standard for educational institutions worldwide. Even though online-based activities were slowly being adopted on a small scale, nothing could have prepared us for the dramatic shift brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. Basically, online learning and assessment have never been attempted on such a large scale and for such an extended period of time, which means that there is a great level of uncertainty and confusion, of trial and error and of unpredictable outcomes that remain to be dealt with in the future. Inevitably, this has led to a great number of challenges, first and foremost for teachers and educational institutions (due to the massive personal and financial investments necessary to make this new system work) but also for students, who have had to adapt to all this rather quickly. In terms of pedagogy, online

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assessment raises special concerns from both students and teachers. Developing assessment literacy is key for both categories, as is providing training for organising group meetings, remote communication via e-mail groups or apps and assessment through educational platforms.

As they look ahead, towards what will likely be another academic year of distance learning, teachers find themselves in need of a comprehensive online assessment strategy which will help them navigate what might be the most complicated issue in online education. While in the first few months of 2020 e-learning was only supposed to be a temporary solution to managing the pandemic, one and a half years later, teachers need this strategy in order to make online learning and assessment work in their classrooms. This article is based on the author's experience of teaching English at university level and aims to outline some key points to be considered before the start of the new academic year.

BEST PRACTICES IN DEVELOPING AN ONLINE ASSESSMENT STRATEGY

Traditionally, all the courses at our faculty would involve formative and summative face-to-face assessment, usually combining oral with written evaluation. With the sudden switch to distance learning (during the spring semester of the 2020/2021 academic year), the emergency solution was to transfer the same evaluation pattern online. However, we must keep in mind that simply transitioning an assessment program from pen to paper to CBT, while keeping all the regular procedures and costs the same, is extremely unrealistic because it can impact what, how, when and where we assess, as well as how and when we communicate the evaluation results.² In other words, while this may work temporarily, the most important point to consider when devising a strategy for online assessment is designing the course with this end in mind. It is essential for both the teacher and the students to know from the beginning how the evaluation process will be conducted, so that the conditions for reliability, validity and authenticity are met. If the entire course is conducted online, then it is easier for everyone involved to get acquainted with the technology used in the learning process ahead of the evaluation period, which will likely reduce testing anxiety. If, however, the course is held face-to-face, while assessment is done online, practice is necessary in order to familiarise students with the process beforehand.

The real problem appears when there is constant back-and-forth between offline and online instruction, based on the fluctuating epidemiological situation we have recently been dealing with. In our country, there are several thresholds based on the number of COVID-19 infections, which require education institutions to go from on-site to on-line learning and back again when the situation permits. Thus, there is no guarantee that assessment will take place one way or the other, which translates into the teacher's inability to plan accordingly.

What can be done is including both possible scenarios in devising our strategy through blended learning. Even if we go back to face-to-face activities, by including some online components into the course, the teacher is able to prepare students for different scenarios and make the transition to online assessment smoother. Distance learning should not be viewed as inferior and even the medium itself "is not the critical point; it is how the medium is utilized that matters."³

² Sandra Greenberg and Leon Smith, "Feasibility Studies on Transitioning Assessment Programs from Paper and Pencil to CBT Delivery" In *Online Assessment and Measurement. Case Studies from Higher Education, K-12 and Corporate*, edited by Scott L. Howell and Mary Hricko, Hershey, PA: Information Science Publishing, 2006, p. 247.

³ Evan Frenedo, *How to Teach Business English*, Harlow: Pearson Education Limited, 2012, p. 95.

There may be, of course, skills which are more difficult to teach and assess online, and in my particular case as a Business English teacher, one of them would be intercultural communication. However, as Sorina Chiper shows, Moodle™, Blackboard™ and Youtube™ are invaluable resources for trainers looking to create opportunities for their learners to discover other cultures, interact with foreigners and become a global citizen. In terms of ICT tools for evaluation, she points out that Mahara™ is very useful in evaluating intercultural competences, since it is an electronic portfolio system which allows users to upload files of their work and also develop their own profile. Moreover, this system allows for peer evaluation.⁴ When the pandemic hit, these tools, which had limited uses before, became indispensable. The key point is being able to identify, acquire and utilise the necessary resources to be able to implement these tools in such a way that is accessible and relevant to students' needs, while also making sure that assessment based on them is authentic.

As a prerequisite of adopting an online assessment strategy, we need to acknowledge that the “substantial resources in terms of time, energy, and money are needed to establish any form of online authentic assessment strategy. Additionally, efficient and reliable technical support, along with appropriate networking capabilities, are essential for all students and instructors.”⁵ While some evaluation tools are accessible free of charge, when it comes to large numbers of students and extended use, it is up to the educational institution to provide the financial, technical and human resources necessary in order for online learning and assessment to be implemented successfully. Based on an article from 2006, few universities (in the United States) had “written policies, guidelines or technical support for faculty members or students.”⁶ If that was the case back then, we can imagine that with the abrupt start of the pandemic, the situation has been even more problematic, especially in other parts of the world, where access to technology and the number of programs offering online education is even more limited. In the case of the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration in Iași, this translated into adapting the Moodle™ platform so it would enable students to take their multiple-choice tests online. In terms of lectures and seminars, videoconferencing through Microsoft Teams™ has been used for the past academic year, with a plan to continue using them moving forward, at least until the current situation improves.

One of the biggest issues with online assessment is cheating. This, of course, also happens in the case of traditional on-site exams, but taking a test from behind a computer screen brings a new set of challenges. Some solutions exist, from using software to verify IPs and video supervision to designing the test in such a way that there is little room for fraud. But the formerly mentioned software and equipment may not be available on a large scale, while the latter will still leave some room for cheating.

Thus, developing a strategy for online assessment not only requires planning ahead but also investing money and long-term effort, from the staff and learning institutions alike.

Investments are always more feasible when they are based on a well-executed plan. Obtaining positive results and a good return of investment take time, which is why

⁴ Sorina Chiper, “Teaching Intercultural Communication: ICT Resources and Best Practices.” *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 93 (2013), pp. 1643-1644.

⁵ Smita Mathur and Terry Murray, “Authentic Assessment Online: A Practical and Theoretical Challenge in Higher Education” In *Online Assessment, Measurement and Evaluation: Emerging Practices*, edited by David D. Williams, Scott L. Howell and Mary Hricko, Hershey, PA: Information Science Publishing, 2006, p. 249.

⁶ Mary K. Tallent-Runells et al. “Teaching Courses Online: An Overview of the Research” in *Review of Educational Research*, Vol. 76, No. 1 (Spring, 2006), p. 93.

consistency is key when it comes to implementing any given strategy. Even more so, online assessment requires everyone involved to acquire certain skills (from learning how to use technology, in general, and specific software, in particular) and going through an entire mindset shift. It took some time for everyone involved to process these changes, so it makes sense, from an investment viewpoint at least, to continue with the implementation of certain aspects of online education in the future, even after the pandemic is officially over. Being consistent with our evaluation process ensures that everyone involved knows what to expect, there are reliable systems in place and everything goes smoothly. Thus, making at least one component of the online assessment process permanent would benefit students from an accessibility viewpoint and would pave the way for more online activities in the future.

At this point, there is still plenty to be learnt and improved when it comes to online assessment at our faculty and, to this end, feedback from everyone involved is extremely valuable. The 2020/2021 academic year was an experimental one, but for the most part distance learning worked, so now it is time for educators to incorporate that feedback in the strategy for this year, which will most likely roughly follow the same pattern as the previous one in terms of online instruction.

What we have learnt so far is that, provided with the necessary infrastructure and tools, both teachers and students are able to adapt to change fairly quickly. At the same time, online education requires considerably more effort, especially from a communication viewpoint, since it is now mediated through ICT. As a result, developing a quality assurance process based on the feedback we collect from all the involved parties, as part of the strategy for designing online courses and assessment, is paramount.⁷ This will ensure that their effort will not have been in vain and that we can use the past year as a solid base for the future integration of online assessment into the course description at our university.

CONCLUSION

As Fernando Rubio concludes his article on assessing oral proficiency in online language courses, “treating assessment in online courses the same way we regard it in F2F teaching would be trying to fit a square peg into a round hole. Although the proficiency expectations should be the same regardless of the delivery format, how we achieve them and the way we measure them in each context do not necessarily need to be the same.”⁸ When devising a strategy for online assessment, as shown, teachers need to consider how the medium affects the process in the long run and be consistent with their choices, while also making sure that everyone has access to reliable infrastructure for equal opportunities. Implementing an online assessment strategy should be done with the support of the educational institution, as it impacts the activity at all levels and requires significant investment.

What would be advisable is to use this period as an opportunity to gather information about what works and what doesn’t in terms of online education in general and of online assessment, in particular, so that we can come out of the pandemic with a clear idea of how to move forward. Perhaps it will take some time to devise and implement a well-rounded

⁷ David Dayton and Mary McShane Vaughn discuss the importance of utilising QA checklists in their article titled “Developing a Quality Assurance Process to Guide the Design and Assessment of Online Courses” in *Technical Communication*, Vol. 54, No. 4 (November 2007).

⁸ Fernando Rubio, “Assessment of Oral Proficiency in Online Language Courses: Beyond Reinventing the Wheel” in *The Modern Language Journal* Vol. 99, No. 2 (Summer 2015), p. 407.

strategy and it may prove to be less reliable than others, but the door to extensive use of technology in the educational field has been flung open and there is little chance of it being completely closed again. Consequently, even if at institutional level things are not yet clear in terms of making some of these changes permanent, teachers need to be aware of the fact that they are often the ones who can set the tone in this sense.

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BOOK REVIEW: Handbook of Positive Youth Development: Advancing Research, Policy, and Practice in Global Contexts

Radosveta Dimitrova and Nora Wiium (Eds)
Cham, Switzerland, Springer, 2021, 754 pages

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The *Handbook of Positive Youth Development: Advancing the Next Generation of Research, Policy and Practice in Global Contexts* (2021), edited by Radosveta Dimitrova and Nora Wiium, encompasses a unique collection of theoretical and empirical studies on positive youth development (PYD) across wide range of contexts and countries from Africa, Asia, Australia, Europe, Latin America, Middle East, New Zealand to North America. Multiple research methods, practical applications, policy interventions on PYD mechanisms in specific environments are presented in this newly released collective contribution, designed to scientifically advance the study of young people and emerging adults' positive development.

The present volume advances our understanding on the entire ecology of development in national, regional and international settings, significantly enhancing the existing PYD trajectories, research tools and interventions methods, through a transformative undertaking, focusing on youth potentiality and the importance of an appropriate developmental context in adolescence and emerging adulthood (individual, peer, familial, societal). This *Handbook* finds its origins in *Positive Youth Development across Cultures Project*³ initiated by Nora Wiium, from University of Bergen, and constantly developed within a rich research network in over 40 countries, across large and even hard to access samples (N = 22,083).

The 37 chapters of the book are organized along two sections. The first one, entitled *Positive Youth Development in Global Context*, focuses on putting forth empirical evidence from often neglected samples from Asia (India, Indonesia, Pakistan, Malaysia), Africa (Ghana), Latin America, and Eastern Europe, as well as Southern and Northern Europe, Australia, New Zealand, and two additional chapters on multi-country comparisons (Wiium and Kozina, 2021; Dimitrova et al, 2021a) This geographic representation is in line with the book's ethos of advancing PYD beyond its WEIRD-centric bias.

From a theoretical standpoint, the section provides an introduction to the principal models employed in PYD research: the developmental assets model (Scales, Roehlkepartain, and Shramko, 2017), the 5Cs (Confidence, Competence, Character, Caring and Connection) and 6Cs models of PYD (Competence, Confidence, Character, Caring, Connection, and Contribution) (Burkhard et al., 2019; Geldhof et al., 2015) and the newly developed 7Cs

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³ More details about The Positive Youth Development cross-national project are available at <https://www.uib.no/en/rg/sipa/pydcrossnational>

model of PYD among young people in a variety of cultural contexts (Dimitrova et al., 2021a). In line with the academic tradition of building upon the “Cs model”, the volume goes beyond the 5Cs and 6Cs through the addition of Creativity as a new indicator. This new theoretic model is outlined by the leading editor and collaborators in the first chapter of Part I and further tested not only in this chapter, but in others from the section as well. For example, Chapter 3 highlights how the model including Creativity can be used to explain reduced risk behaviour in youth from Colombia and Peru (Manrique-Millones et al., 2021), while Chapter 4 provides additional validation of the 7Cs model by relating it to mindfulness (Abdul Kadir, Mohd, and Dimitrova, 2021).

The chapters in part one use quantitative and qualitative methods alike to investigate how PYD models apply to adolescents and emerging adults in a variety of global contexts, challenging the balance of universality and relativity. Methodologically, it advances scholarship on PYD by tackling cultural adaptation and measurement invariance issues (Dimitrova et al., 2021a; Dimitrova et al., 2021b). The large and diverse samples collected provide an excellent occasion for developing psychometrically strong and cross-culturally applicable measures of PYD.

The second section, entitled *PYD Applications and Interventions*, provides practical insights and policy implications from diverse contexts in China, Colombia, Italy, Jordan, Kenya, the Philippines, Sweden, Thailand, Jamaica, South Africa, Slovenia, Lithuania, Finland, Norway, Canada and the United States. Special attention is given to the large-sized networking in the field of international PYD research with examples of outstanding projects (Lansford et al., 2021). Methodological issues and innovative perspectives in studying latent growth models (Hull et al., 2021), leadership across cultures (Bremner and Schwartz 2021), Social Emotional Learning (Kozina 2021), community intervention (Kaniušonytė and Truskauskaitė-Kunevičienė 2021), Student Engagement and well-being (Upadyaya and Salmela-Aro 2021), the role of Classroom Climate in PYD, (Ginner Hau, Ferrer-Wreder, and Allodi Westling 2021), applications of the logic model of PYD to the school programs (Bogsnes Larsen and Holsen 2021), along with The Planned Intervention Adaptation (PIA) protocol adaptation (Ferrer-Wreder et al., 2021) and parenting knowledge with implications for Positive Youth Development (PYD) are being debated. The Romanian PYD context is assessed in two chapters, one approaching inter-generational transmission of vocational competence within family in national context (Negru Subtirica and Badescu 2021) and the other examining the 5Cs model of PYD through factorial structure and measurement invariance, within a cross-cultural analysis (Radosveta et al., 2021b)

A special focus is given in the *Handbook* to empowering new a generation of PYD scholarship in less represented countries, to establishing reliable measurements in assessing PYD cross-culturally, and to enforcing the PYD field with pertinent research, policy, and practice, worldwide. The book sets itself apart as pioneering in PYD research, nowadays, as acknowledged by Daniel Shek, one of the leading scholars in PYD research and intervention especially in Asia, who sets the tone for the contributions in this volume. Besides summarizing a number of unique features and relevant conceptual and methodological contributions of the book at hand, the foreword written by Shek stands itself as a testament to the book’s ethos of increasing visibility of non-WEIRD PYD research and scholars. The *Handbook* is a tremendous ambitious collective product that raises the voice and advances the research in PYD in both WEIRD and non-WEIRD societies.

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DEDIFFERENTIATED ENDOMETRIAL CARCINOMA ASSOCIATED WITH ENDOMETRIAL POLYPS WITH STROMAL ATYPIA – A CASE REPORT AND REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT:

DEDIFFERENTIATED ENDOMETRIAL CARCINOMA IS A RARE OCCURRENCE IN UTERINE MALIGNANCIES. THIS HISTOPATHOLOGICAL SUBTYPE IS RELATIVELY NEW IN TUMOUR CLASSIFICATIONS AND MOLECULAR ALTERATIONS ARE IN CONTINUOUS DEVELOPMENT. WE DESCRIBE A 61-YEAR-OLD WOMAN WITH THIS DIAGNOSIS ASSOCIATING TWO ENDOMETRIAL POLYPS WITH STROMAL ATYPIA. THIS TYPE OF ASSOCIATION HAS NOT BEEN PREVIOUSLY REPORTED AND DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS IS OF THE UTMOST IMPORTANCE. WE EXCLUDED OTHER POTENTIAL DIAGNOSES SUCH AS MIXED CARCINOMA OR CARCINOSARCOMA. OUR AIM WAS TO BRING RECOGNITION TO THIS RELATIVELY NEW LESION AND REVIEW THE LITERATURE.

KEY WORDS: DEDIFFERENTIATED, ENDOMETRIAL, CARCINOMA.

INTRODUCTION

Dedifferentiated endometrial carcinoma is a relatively rare entity defined by the association of an undifferentiated component with a low-grade endometrioid component (FIGO grade 1 or 2)⁶. It accounts for approximately 9% of endometrial carcinomas⁷ and is

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⁶ WHO classification of tumours editorial board, *Female Genital Tumours*.

⁷ Vroobel and Attygalle, "Sarcomatous Transformation in Undifferentiated/Dedifferentiated Endometrial Carcinoma."

usually associated with poor prognosis. Considering that new molecular subgroups have been proposed by the TCGA and WHO ⁸ for endometrial carcinomas, this rare entity has also been investigated. Reported cases have shown a heterogenous display of molecular alterations with different percentages in all four subgroups ⁹.

Endometrial polyps with stromal atypia are considered rare occurrences in postmenopausal women in which the atypical stroma is thought to be a degenerative or reactive process ¹⁰. Studies are limited regarding this lesion, but its importance lies in the differential diagnosis. Malignancies must be excluded in this situation: carcinosarcoma or adenosarcoma.

MAIN TEXT

A 61-year-old female patient was referred to our clinic for surgical consult and treatment after accusing multiple abundant metrorrhagias and receiving a diagnosis of endometrioid endometrial carcinoma on a curettage in another institution. Patient history revealed heart failure NYHA II, paroxysmal atrial fibrillation under treatment, liver steatosis, a left renal cyst and gallbladder lithiasis. Clinical examination showed morbid obesity, with no other visible changes. A cardiology consult was performed and subsequent medication was established. CT examination revealed an enlarged uterus with the highest diameter of 20 mm with no secondary involvement of lymph nodes, lung, liver or bone. Total hysterectomy with bilateral adnexectomy with radical lymph node removal was performed.

Gross examination revealed an 8/6/6 cm endometrial tumour that occupied more than a half of the myometrium. Additionally, we found two endometrial polyps, closely connected to the endometrial tumour, measuring 5/3/2 cm and 3,5/4/1 cm respectively (Figure 1.). Histopathological examination revealed that the endometrial tumour consisted of two malignant populations: a low-grade (FIGO grade 2) endometrioid component (70%) and an undifferentiated component (30%) (Figure 2.A). Our findings were similar to other case reports, except for the presence of the two polyps ¹¹.

Figure 1.

⁸ Hoang et al., “Interobserver Agreement in Endometrial Carcinoma Histotype Diagnosis Varies Depending on The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA)-Based Molecular Subgroup.”

⁹ Busca et al., “Undifferentiated Endometrial Carcinoma Arising in the Background of High-grade Endometrial Carcinoma – Expanding the Definition of Dedifferentiated Endometrial Carcinoma.”

¹⁰ Tai and Tavassoli, “Endometrial Polyps With Atypical (Bizarre) Stromal Cells.”

¹¹ Han et al., “Dedifferentiated Endometrioid Carcinoma of the Uterus.”

According to standardized pathological protocol, we reported several histopathologic parameters as follows: lympho-vascular invasion – present; uterine serosa involvement – absent; cervical stroma involvement – absent; lower uterine segment involvement – present.

Pattern of tumour invasion was reported as `adenomyosis involvement` (Figure 2.D). All resection margins and all lymph nodes were negative. Preliminary histopathological diagnosis was dedifferentiated endometrial carcinoma with TNM staging: pT1b pN0 LV1 R0, FIGO IB. On microscopic examination, the two endometrial polyps revealed tumour invasion and, in addition, their stroma showed pleomorphic, multinucleated stromal cells, warranting a differential diagnosis with a potential sarcomatous component (Figure 2.B, 2.C).

Figure 2.

An immunohistochemical panel was selected in order to evaluate all prognostic parameters and to exclude other differential diagnoses such as mixed endometrial carcinoma or carcinosarcoma. Genetic testing for POLE mutation was not available for this case. We performed ER (Figure 3.F) and PR (Figure 3.D) that were positive in 95% of tumour nuclei in the endometrioid component and negative in the undifferentiated component. Hormone receptor negativity in the undifferentiated component is a relatively constant finding, further confirming the diagnosis ¹².

MLH1 (Figure 3.C), MSH2, PMS2 and MSH6 were positive in both components (MSS molecular subgroup – microsatellite stability). Surprisingly, most dedifferentiated

¹² Yigit et al., “Dedifferentiated Endometrioid Adenocarcinoma; Clinicopathologic and Immunohistochemical Features of Five Cases.”

endometrial carcinomas show microsatellite instability – MSI or are connected to the Lynch syndrome. Therefore, these subtypes are good candidates for immunotherapy and frequently express the immunohistochemical marker PD-L1¹³.

Figure 3.

P53 was overexpressed in both components (Figure 3.A, 3E), in more than 90% of tumour nuclei (p53abn molecular subgroup). WHO states that dedifferentiated endometrial carcinomas usually belong to the copy-number low subgroup, followed less frequently by the POLE-mutated subgroup and the TP53-mutated subgroup (p53abn). One recent study classified undifferentiated and dedifferentiated endometrial carcinoma according to the four TCGA molecular subgroups, showing that the p53abn molecular subgroup was identified in 18.6% of cases¹⁴. EMA (Figure 3.B) and CK8/18 (Figure 3.H) were positive in the endometrioid component, and only focally positive in the undifferentiated component. HER2 was negative in both components. Ki67 was positive in 90% (Figure 3.G) of tumour nuclei in both components.

In addition, we performed immunohistochemical testing in the endometrial polyps with atypical stroma. SMA (Figure 4.D.) and Vimentin (Figure 4.B.) were positive in the atypical stromal cells. CD10 was focally positive in the stromal cells (Figure 4.A). AE1-AE3 (Figure

¹³ Ono et al., “Dedifferentiated Endometrial Carcinoma Could Be A Target for Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors (Anti PD-1/PD-L1 Antibodies).”

¹⁴ Travaglino et al., “TCGA Molecular Subgroups in Endometrial Undifferentiated/Dedifferentiated Carcinoma.”

4.E) was negative in the atypical stromal cells. Ki67 (Figure 4.C.) was positive in 4% of nuclei in the atypical stromal cells. Consequently, we excluded other sarcomatous components. Stromal atypia in endometrial polyps is rare and usually identified in patients that followed tamoxifen treatment¹⁵. Since this is not the case with our patient, we concluded that the atypical stromal cells should be interpreted as degenerative in a post menopause patient.

Figure 4.

Final histopathological and immunohistochemical diagnosis was dedifferentiated endometrial carcinoma, MSS, p53abn, associated with endometrial polyps with stromal atypia.

CONCLUSION

The rarity of our case is represented by various factors: the histopathological subtype, the microsatellite stability, belonging to the p53abn molecular subgroup and the association with two endometrial polyps with stromal atypia.

Dedifferentiated endometrial carcinomas are rare histopathological subtypes and have a very poor prognosis. One should always have in mind the differential diagnoses for the undifferentiated component such as high-grade (FIGO3) endometrioid carcinoma, which has a very different clinical behaviour. To our knowledge, this is one of a few case reports of

¹⁵ Öztürk et al., “Case Report of Atypical Endometrial Stromal Cells in an Endometrial Polyp and Osteoclastic like Giant Cells in Leiomyoma in the Same Patient.”

dedifferentiated endometrial carcinoma associated with endometrial polyps with stromal atypia in our country.

I undersign, certificate that I have the written consent of the identifiable person or his/her legal guardian in order to present the cases in this scientific paper. All authors equally contributed to this research. All authors report no potential conflict of interest.

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HYPERTRIGLYCERIDAEMIC PANCREATITIS AND DIABETIC KETOACIDOSIS

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ABSTRACT:

ACUTE PANCREATITIS IS AN INFLAMMATORY CONDITION OF THE PANCREAS WITH MULTIPLE ETIOLOGIES. HYPERTRIGLYCERIDAEMIC PANCREATITIS (HTG-AP) IS NOT A COMMON CAUSE OF AP BUT IS ASSOCIATED WITH A INCREASED RATE OF COMPLICATIONS. PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS ARE AT INCREASED RISK OF AP. THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN HYPERTRIGLYCERIDAEMIA, KETOACIDOSIS AND AP IS RARE. THE TREATMENT OF THIS TYPE OF PANCREATITIS IS NOT WELL ESTABLISHED IN CURRENT GUIDELINES, SPECIFIC THERAPEUTIC MEASUREMENTS INCLUDE HEPARIN, INSULIN TREATMENT, PLASMAPHERESIS, COMBINED BLOOD PURIFICATION THERAPY, HIGH-VOLUME HEMOFILTRATION AND HEMOPERFUSION. WE REPORTED TWO CASES OF HYPERTRIGLYCERIDAEMIA (HTG) INDUCED AP, IN PATIENTS WITH UNCONTROLLED TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS AND KETOACIDOSIS ONE TREATED WITH INSULIN INFUSION AND ANOTHER TREATED WITH INSULIN INFUSION AND PLASMAPHERESIS. BOTH CASES WERE SUCCESSFULLY MANAGED WITH SPECIFIC MEASURES AND SUPPORTIVE CARE.

KEYWORDS: ACUTE PANCREATITIS, HYPERTRIGLYCERIDAEMIA, DIABETIC KETOACIDOSIS, PLASMAPHERESIS.

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INTRODUCTION

Acute pancreatitis, diabetes mellitus and hypertriglyceridaemia are diseases with increased incidence in our modern world. Diabetes mellitus is a common metabolic disorder with 102% increasing incidence between 1990 and 2017⁸ and the life-threatening complication, diabetic ketoacidosis, had a reported incidence of 0,48/1000 in a Japanese study⁹ with increased incidence reported in several studies^{10,11}. Regarding AP the continuous increase in the incidence among both men and women in the last 31 years was reported in a Danish study¹².

HTG-AP is the third cause of AP following alcohol and biliary etiology with a reported incidence between 4% and 9%^{13,14}. In National Cholesterol Education Program ATP III, triglyceride (TGs) level is normal (<150), borderline high (150-199), high (200-499), and very high (>500 mg/dL)¹⁵. Hypertriglyceridemia can be primary (inherited) and secondary (acquired). The conditions associated with HTG include *obesity, metabolic syndrome, diabetes, alcohol, renal disease, pregnancy, medications, immunological disorders*¹⁶. *TG cut off value associated with AP is 1000 mg/dl*¹⁷. The diagnosis of HTG AP is made by the presence of two of three criteria: upper abdominal pain, increase of pancreatic enzymes over three times the upper limit of normal and characteristic radiological finding. The optimal management of HTG-AP is not well established but it is desirable to decrease the TG level quickly¹⁸.

⁸ Liu J, Ren ZH, Qiang H, Wu J, Shen M, Zhang L, Lyu J. Trends in the incidence of diabetes mellitus: results from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017 and implications for diabetes mellitus prevention. *BMC Public Health*. 2020 Sep 17;20(1):1415. doi: 10.1186/s12889-020-09502-x. PMID: 32943028; PMCID: PMC7500018

⁹ Takeuchi M, Kawamura T, Sato I, Kawakami K. Population-based incidence of diabetic ketoacidosis in type 2 diabetes: medical claims data analysis in Japan. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf*. 2018 Jan;27(1):123-126. doi: 10.1002/pds.4271. Epub 2017 Jul 28. PMID: 28752620

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¹¹ Javor KA, Kotsanos JG, McDonald RC, Baron AD, Kesterson JG, Tierney WM. Diabetic ketoacidosis charges relative to medical charges of adult patients with type I diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 1997;20:349-54. 10.2337/diacare.20.3.349 pmid:9051386.

¹² Knudsen JS, Heide-Jørgensen U, Mortensen FV, Sørensen HT, Ehrenstein V. Acute pancreatitis: 31-Year trends in incidence and mortality - A Danish population-based cohort study. *Pancreatology*. 2020 Oct;20(7):1332-1339. doi: 10.1016/j.pan.2020.09.011. Epub 2020 Sep 14. PMID: 32958367..

¹³ Tsuang W, Navaneethan U, Ruiz L, Palascak JB, Gelrud A. Hypertriglyceridemic pancreatitis: presentation and management. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2009 Apr;104(4):984-91. doi: 10.1038/ajg.2009.27. Epub 2009 Mar 17. PMID: 19293788

¹⁴ Rosalie A. Carr, Benjamin J. Rejowski, Gregory A. Cote, Henry A. Pitt, Nicholas J. Zyromski, Systematic review of hypertriglyceridemia-induced acute pancreatitis: A more virulent etiology?, *Pancreatology*, Volume 16, Issue 4, 2016, Pages 469-476, ISSN390 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pan.2016.02.011>.

¹⁵ Expert Panel on Detection Evaluation and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults. Executive summary of the third report of the National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) expert panel on detection, evaluation, and treatment of high blood cholesterol in adults (adult treatment panel III) *Journal of the American Medical Association*. 2001;285(19):2486-2497. doi: 10.1001/jama.285.19.2486.

¹⁶ Autoimmune severe hypertriglyceridemia induced by anti-apolipoprotein C-II antibody. Yamamoto H, Tanaka M, Yoshiga S, Funahashi T, Shimomura I, Kihara SJ *Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2014 May; 99(5):1525-30

¹⁷ Yadav D, Pitchumoni CS. Issues in hyperlipidemic pancreatitis. *J Clin Gastroenterol*. 2003 Jan;36(1):54-62. doi: 10.1097/00004836-200301000-00016. PMID: 12488710

¹⁸ Valdivielso P, Ramírez-Bueno A, Ewald N. Current knowledge of hypertriglyceridemic pancreatitis. *Eur J Intern Med*. 2014;25:689-694.

CASE 1

We report the case of a 47 year old caucasian male who presented to the emergency room for abdominal pain, nausea and vomiting started in the last 48 hours. He had a medical history of type 2 diabetes mellitus therapeutically neglected, former smoker, without history of illicit drug use or alcohol abuse. The clinical examination revealed a restless and anxious patient, with cold, sweaty skin, Kussmaul breathing, tachycardia (heart rate was 124 beats/min), mean arterial pressure 65 mmHg, distended abdomen and epigastric tenderness.

Laboratory parameters showed severe metabolic acidosis with high anion gap, pH 7.07, bicarbonate 8 mmol/l (normal range 22-28 mmol/l), anion gap 20 mmol/l (normal range 4-12 mmol/l), BE -22 mmol/l hyperglycemia, glucose blood level 727 mg/dl (normal range 70-106 mg/dl), lipase 6157 U/l (normal range 73-393 U/l), amylase 822 U/l (normal range 15-115 U/l), severe HTG, TG 4491 mg/dl (normal range 30-150 mg/dl), hypocalcemia 6.1 mg/dl (normal range 8.2-10.7 mg/dl), Na 116 mmol/l (normal range 135-150 mmol/l), K 5.2 mmol/l (normal range 3.5-5.2 mmol/l), LDH 902 U/l (normal range 84-227 U/l), creatinine 1.59 (normal range 0.5-1.5 mg/dl), AST 117 (normal range 2-40 U/l), ALT 88 U/l, creatinine 1.59 mg/dl. Glycated hemoglobin was 11,8 mg/dl (normal range 4.3-6 %). The white blood cell count, hemoglobin and hematocrit values were normal and a high CRP level (>30 mg/l) was found. The serum was lactescent. Urine analysis revealed a urine glucose of 500mg/dL and ketonuria (80mg/dL). The computed tomography (CT) scan showed an oedematous pancreas surrounded by peri-pancreatic, prerenal space and lateroconal fascia fluid collections, a fatty liver, normal gall bladder and bile ducts (Balthazar CT severity index 4).

These data led to the diagnosis of HTG-AP and diabetic ketoacidosis. The treatment was started immediately with insulin bolus 0,1 U/kg followed by insulin 0.1 U/kg/h infusion and volemic resuscitation, in 4 l of normal saline in 24 hours.

After the first 24 hours, the evolution was complicated by the occurrence of hypoxemic respiratory failure and the patient was transferred to intensive care unit (ICU) conscious but very agitated (Richmond Agitation Sedation scale +3), with severe dyspnea, respiratory rate 36/min, mean arterial pressure 70 mmHg. The arterial blood gases (ABG) on ICU admission was suggestive for hypoxemia and metabolic acidosis (pH 7.15, CO₂ 28 mmHg, O₂ 65mmHg, bicarbonate 8.5 mmol/l, anion gap 18 mmol/l). Glucose blood level was 282 mg/dl, Na 128 mmol/l, K 4.2 mmol/l, ALT 128 U/l, AST 81 U/l, TG level 1250 mg/ml, cholesterol 408 mg/dl, normal values of creatinine and levels. In these conditions we decided on intubation and mechanical ventilation using protective lung strategies. At the ICU admission the APACHE II score was 18 and the SOFA score 4. In the ICU it was continued the fluid resuscitation and insulin infusion. Given the high level of TG and the development of respiratory failure and SIRS (Systemic inflammatory response syndrome) in a patient with HTG-AP we performed a plasmapheresis session using human albumin 5% and heparin anticoagulation. The TG level after plasmapheresis was 345 mg/dl. Blood glucose values were controlled but the patient's condition did not improve, requiring sedation and further mechanical ventilation. The enteral feeding, statine and fibrates therapy were started on the second day of ICU stay via nasogastric tube feeding. On the third day of ICU stay the patient presented fever (39° C) and leukocytosis (WBC 15600/ μL). A CT scan was performed showing bilateral pleural effusion (maximum 3 centimeters), bilateral basal pulmonary infiltrates and slight increase in size of peripancreatic, prerenal and lateroconal fascia fluid. A bacteriological screening was performed and broad spectrum antibiotic was administered (meropenem). Tracheal aspirate culture was positive for *Acinetobacter* spp. carbapenem-resistant, colistin-susceptible and the antibiotherapy was escalated with colistin. During his

ICU stay the patient was hemodynamically stable. After 13 days the patient was extubated and then transferred to a regular medicine floor. The CT exam performed five weeks later showed the resolution of the pleural effusions and the presence of multiple peripancreatic collections with a tendency to encapsulation and the patient was discharged with statine, fibrates therapy and insulin therapy.

CASE 2

A 45 year old woman with history of autoimmune thyroiditis without home treatment, no alcohol consumption came to the emergency department for severe upper abdominal pain, nausea and vomiting started 4 days earlier when she performed a glucose strip test at home and found a high glucose blood level (345 mg/dl) but she did not go to the hospital.

Clinical examination showed an alert patient, with decreased skin turgor, respiratory frequency 22/ min, TA 89/45 mmHg, heart rate 120 beats/min. Laboratory exam pH 7.2, bicarbonate 7.2 mmol/l, BE -20 mmol/l, anion gap 23 mmol/l, hyperglycemia (508 mg/dl), TG 1379 mg/dl, cholesterol 411 mg/dl, creatinine 1,63 mg/dl, urea 29 mg/dl K 5.78 mmol/l, Na 123 mmol/l, total calcium 7 mg/dl, ALT 59 U/l, AST 49 U/l, total bilirubin 0,4 mg/dl, lipase 2329 U/l, amylase 1529 U/l, white blood cell 14400/ μ L. Urine analysis revealed a urine glucose of 500mg/dL and ketonuria (30mg/dL), density 1030. The procalcitonin level was > 10 ng/ml and TSH, free T3 and free T4 were in normal range. Glycated hemoglobin was 11,2 mg/dl.

The CT showed pancreatic oedema and peripancreatic, perirenal fluid with a Balthazar CT severity index 4, a fatty liver, no gallstone and normal bile ducts.

The patient was admitted to ICU with an APACHE score 7 and the treatment was started immediately with volemic resuscitation and insulin 0.1U/kg bolus followed by continuous infusion with a rate of 0.1 U/h progressively decreased with the decrease in blood glucose. The patient received prophylactic antibiotic treatment, analgesia with Fentanyl. Forty-eight hours after admission, the TG level reached 432 mg/dl. Enteral feeding, statine and fibrate therapy were started on the third day. The patient's evolution was complicated by the occurrence of renal dysfunction framed as AKI stage 2 (AKIN classification/staging system of acute kidney injury) remitted in about 96 hours. The patient's health state improved and five days later she was transferred from the ICU to a diabetes and metabolism clinic.

DISCUSSION

Diabetic ketoacidosis is due to absolute or relative deficiency of insulin that leads to leads to the formation of ketone bodies and the appearance of hyperglycemia, ketoacidosis and ketonuria. Episodes of ketoacidosis are accompanied by hypertriglyceridemia and an increase in the amount of free fatty acids that cause pancreatic injury¹⁹ but acute pancreatitis can lead to diabetic ketoacidosis.

The association between HTG-AP, diabetic ketoacidosis and hyperglycemia is rarely described in the literature and affects both children and adults. This triad is associated with a higher rate of local and systemic complications and higher mortality.²⁰

¹⁹ Yang F, Wang Y, Sternfeld L, et al. The role of free fatty acids, pancreatic lipase and Ca⁺ signalling in injury of isolated acinar cells and pancreatitis model in lipoprotein lipase-deficient mice. *Acta Physiologica (Oxford, England)*. 2009 Jan;195(1):13-28. DOI: 10.1111/j.1748-1716.2008.01933.x. PMID: 18983441.

²⁰ Simons-Linares CR, Jang S, Sanaka M, Bhatt A, Lopez R, Vargo J, Stevens T, Chahal P. The triad of diabetes ketoacidosis, hypertriglyceridemia and acute pancreatitis. How does it affect mortality and morbidity?: A 10-year analysis of the National Inpatient Sample. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2019 Feb;98(7):e14378. doi: 10.1097/MD.00000000000014378. PMID: 30762737; PMCID: PMC6408121.

The diagnosis of HTG-AP in patients with diabetic ketoacidosis is difficult due to the fact that ketoacidosis is accompanied by abdominal pain and increased level of amylases and lipases even in the absence of pancreatitis²¹, while the amylase level can be normal in patients with HTG-AP²².

The cases presented above occurred in patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus. The first one evolved as severe acute pancreatitis and the second as moderately severe acute pancreatitis. In the first case, the severity was given by the occurrence of respiratory failure despite insulin therapy and in this context a plasmapheresis session was performed with the decrease of the TG level. The respiratory failure was later maintained by the appearance of ventilator associated pneumonia with multi drug resistant germs. The second case was complicated by AKI stage 2. The two cases had different levels of TG but had the same Balthazar CT severity index and their evolution correlated with triglyceride levels rather than CT score.

The initial treatment in both cases was based on fluid resuscitation and insulin administration. The role of plasmapheresis in the treatment of HTG-AP remains to be established in further studies.

CONCLUSION

The early diagnosis and treatment of HTG-AP associated with ketoacidosis are essential given the lethal potential. They represent a real challenge for clinicians. The control of risk factors is crucial because it leads to a decrease in the incidence of this pathology.

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All authors report no potential conflict of interest.

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²² Warshaw AL, Bellini CA, Lesser PB. Inhibition of serum and urine amylase activity in pancreatitis with hyperlipemia. *Annals of Surgery.* 1975 Jul;182(1):72-75. DOI: 10.1097/0000658-197507000-00014. PMID: 1147712.

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THE PERI-APPENDICEAL RED PATCH: A TRADEMARK SKIP LESION IN ULCERATIVE COLITIS

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ABSTRACT:

CONVENTIONALLY, UC IS RECOGNIZED AS A DISEASE WITH CONTINUOUS MUCOSAL INFLAMMATION THAT EXTENDS FROM THE RECTUM TO THE PROXIMAL PART OF THE COLON, BUT DURING THE LAST DECADE, A PARTICULAR PATTERN OF COLITIS THAT INVOLVES THE DISTAL COLON WITH A NORMAL APPEARANCE MUCOSA INTERPOSED AND A WELL DEFINED AREA OF INFLAMMATION AROUND THE APPENDIX HAS BEEN HIGHLIGHTED. WE USED A TERTIARY CARE CENTER EVIDENCES TO ANALYZE THE CHARACTERISTICS OF UC PATIENTS WITH PARP. WE EVALUATED 76 PATIENTS WHO WENT TO OUR CLINIC FOR INVESTIGATING CHRONIC DIARRHEA SYNDROME BETWEEN JANUARY 2018-DECEMBER 2020 AND FOR WHOM A DIAGNOSIS OF ULCERATIVE COLITIS WAS ESTABLISHED. ONLY 7 PATIENTS HAD ENDOSCOPICALLY ASPECT OF PARP (THIS HAPPENED DURING FOLLOW-UP ENDOSCOPY), ASPECT SUPPORTED ALSO BY THE HISTOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION (NANCY INDEX SCORE). DURING FOLLOW-UP, MOST PATIENTS WITH PARP KEPT THE SAME EXTENT OF LESIONS.

CONCLUSIONS: WE CONFIRM THE PRESENCE OF PARP AS A "SKIP LESION" IN DISTAL UC, DIAGNOSTIC SUPPORTED ALSO BY THE HISTOPATHOLOGIST, AND EVEN THOUGH WE ARE CONFIDENT IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF ULCERATIVE COLITIS, ONE PATIENT HAD A CROHN'S DISEASE PHENOTYPE SWITCH DURING THE EVOLUTION. NONETHELESS, WE CANNOT CONCLUDE THAT PARP HAS A ROLE IN THE EXTENSION OF LESIONS, REMISSION OR RELAPSE OF DISEASE, GIVEN THE FACT THAT WE DO NOT HAVE A SUFFICIENT GROUP OF ELIGIBLE PATIENTS, FOR WHICH REASON DETAILED STUDIES ARE NEEDED.

KEYWORDS: CECAL PATCH; PERI-APPENDICEAL RED PATCH (PARP); APPENDICEAL ORIFICE INFLAMMATION (AOI); ULCERATIVE COLITIS (UC).

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last few years, the display of inflammation near the appendix in patients presenting with proctitis/ left-sided ulcerative colitis (UC) has been underlined. Anyway, the practical importance of appendiceal orifice inflammation (AOI)/ peri-appendiceal red patch (PARP)/ cecal patch as a skip lesion in UC is not very clearly established.

UC is one of the two subtypes of inflammatory bowel diseases, most often affecting young adults, with an increasing incidence and prevalence in developed countries. The current manifesto of UC pathogenesis basically implies a constellation of genetic, environment and microbiota modifications, along with an altered response and a damage of the epithelial barrier.

Differentiation between UC, Crohn's disease and other pathologies (such as infectious colitis, ischemic or radiation colitis, segmental colitis associated with diverticulosis) is of critical importance for a tailored management, because each pathology demands particular therapeutic approach and it has a distinct prognosis.

UC produces lesions that spread in a continuous manner, starting from the rectum to the proximal parts of the colon, the ileum being rarely affected (except for "backwash ileitis", when the ileal mucosa is exposed to cecal bacteria). The typical lesions detected, differ on the severity of the disease, and accepted and validated endoscopic scores are helpful. Therefore, depending on the disease activity, the following lesions can be described as follows: erythema, erosions, blurring of the normal vascular pattern, oedema, friability of the mucosa or the presence of pseudopolyps/mucopurulent exudates. There are a few exceptions from the already known rule and this is when the rectum is of normal macroscopic appearance, as in: pediatric population, fulminant colitis, the use of topical 5-aminosalicylate (5-ASA) or in association with sclerosing cholangitis⁴. This topic is receiving emerging attention, giving the fact that in recent years studies that demonstrated the existence of UC with an atypical distribution of inflammatory lesions were published⁵.

This particular lesion (AOI/PARP) was first described in 1958 by Lumb and Protheroe, which reported eight cases of UC with an island of inflammation of the cecum mucosa, opposite to the ileocecal valve⁶.

Regarding Crohn's disease, the major endoscopic findings that are suggestive for this diagnosis are: aphthous ulcers, cobblestoning and discontinuous lesions. Basically, a normal appearance rectum directs the diagnosis to Crohn's disease⁷.

⁴ Faubion WA, Jr., Loftus EV, Sandborn WJ, Freese DK, Perrault J. Pediatric "PSC-IBD": A descriptive report of associated inflammatory bowel disease among pediatric patients with psc. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr* 2001;33:296-300; Odze R, Antonioli D, Peppercorn M, et al. Effect of topical 5-aminosalicylic acid (5-ASA) therapy on rectal mucosal biopsy morphology in chronic ulcerative colitis. *Am J Surg Pathol*. 1993;17: 869–875; Jorgensen KK, Grzyb K, Lundin KE, et al. Inflammatory bowel disease in patients with primary sclerosing cholangitis: Clinical characterization in liver transplanted and nontransplanted patients. *Inflamm Bowel Dis* 2012;18:536-45

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⁶ Pera A, Bellando P, Caldera D, Ponti V, Astegiano M, Barletti C, David E, Arrigoni A, Rocca G, Verme G . Colonoscopy in inflammatory bowel disease. Diagnostic accuracy and proposal of an endoscopic score. *Gastroenterology*. 1987;92(1):181

⁷ Dignass A, Lindsay JO, Sturm A, Windsor A, Colombel JF, Allez M, D'Haens G, D'Hoore A, Mantzaris G, Novacek G, et al. Second European evidence-based consensus on the diagnosis and management of ulcerative colitis part 2: current management. *J Crohns Colitis*. 2012;6:991–1030

The size of the problem, when we refer to establishing a clear diagnosis, is big because medical treatment and type of surgery is very relevant, in particular when proctocolectomy may be needed.

Studies from the literature show that the clinical evolution of patients with atypical distribution may be slightly different (in a positive way) from that of patients with classical distribution, regarding remission, relapse or the need for colectomy or hospitalization.

It is well known the fact that the cecal inflammation may be part of the normal mucosal state of health, because the cecum consists of a high number of eosinophils, Paneth cells and cellularity in lamina propria (lymphocytes and plasma cells). In a study published in 2007 in American Journal of Gastroenterology, regarding “the importance of recognizing increased cecal inflammation in health and avoiding the misdiagnosis of nonspecific colitis” which involved taking biopsies from the cecum and rectum in 85 people without any digestive symptoms, they found out that there is an increased microscopic inflammation of the cecum in healthy persons and every pathologist and clinician must be aware of these modifications⁸.

Some studies published over the years have shown conflicting results between the role of appendectomy and the progression rate of ulcerative colitis: a cohort study from Denmark and Sweden which included 709353 patients with a familial predisposition to inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), appendicitis or mesenteric lymphadenitis during childhood or adolescence had a low risk to develop UC in adulthood⁹. On the other hand, the results published from a study from British which included 3829 patients who suffered an appendectomy and were compared with the same number of controls, did not find a relationship between these two pathologies¹⁰.

Fig.1 Chronic active inflammation, erosive, non-granulomatous, located peri-appendicular.

⁸ Paski, S. C., Wightman, R., Robert, M.E., & Bernstein, C.N. The importance of recognizing increased cecal inflammation in health and avoiding the misdiagnosis of nonspecific colitis. *The American Journal of Gastroenterology*. 2007. 102(10), 2294-299

⁹ Morten Frisch, Bo V Pedersen, Rolland E Andersson. Appendicitis, mesenteric lymphadenitis, and subsequent risk of ulcerative colitis: cohort studies in Sweden and Denmark. *BMJ*. 2009; 338: b716

¹⁰ Carla Felice, Alessandro Armuzzi. Therapeutic Role of Appendectomy in Ulcerative Colitis: A Tangible Perspective? *Journal of Crohn's and Colitis*, Volume 13, Issue 2, February 2019, Pages 142–143

Fig. 2 showing the aspect of AOI

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The aim of this study is to explore the clinical characteristics and course, principally focused on distal extension of UC and AOI.

We searched our hospital database for the files of all patients who presented in our clinic between January 2018- December 2020 for symptoms associated to chronic diarrhea and carried a diagnostic of ulcerative colitis (either new diagnostic or follow up colonoscopy), and the disease activity was mild to moderate. We excluded those patients with indeterminate colitis, incomplete colonoscopy (the impossibility to explore correctly the cecum), or who had lesions proximal the splenic flexure. All the endoscopies were performed by well trained doctors from the same medical clinic.

The endoscopic report had to mention the cecal patch (and the degree of AOI was noted endoscopically as follows: 1- oedema, 2- moderate inflammation, 3- marked inflammation), appendiceal orifice inflammation or peri-appendiceal red patch, in the presence of proctitis or left-sided colitis to meet the eligibility criteria.

Baseline informations regarding demographic datas, family history of IBD, clinical disease activity, extent of the disease, the treatment used during the evolution, the number of colonoscopies performed, the progression of lesions, the necessity of surgery, as well as the histopathologist report were evaluated. Histological inflammation was scored by a pathologist with experience in UC, using Nancy score. The diagnostic of UC was made corroborating clinical symptoms, colonoscopy and histopathological specific features congruent with the disease.

Due to the fact that we had a small group of patients, basic statistics were calculated.

RESULTS

Were identified 98 patients who performed colonoscopy in our medical institution, of which 22 had pancolitis, so they were excluded from our study. Demographic data showed that 31 patients (40.00%) were females and 45 (60.00%) were males, most of them living in urban area (72.00%), and 36 of them (48.00%) were ex-smokers. Only one male patient (1.3%) with UC had a family history of IBD and this patient also met endoscopic criteria to be included in the AOI group. The treatment initiated for all the patients, from the beginning, in order to maintain the remission, included 5 aminosalicylic acid and most of them received

oral preparations and enemas. For 21 (28.00%) patients it was decided that the activity of disease was moderate and corticosteroid therapy was initiated, and some (16 patients) had multiple courses of corticosteroids, during the follow-up period. Of this 21 patients, 3 had also endoscopic (and histologic) diagnostic of AOI. Due to the severity of disease, 21.33% (16) got azathioprine and 11 patients (14.67%) needed anti-TNF therapy during follow-up period; none of them has lost the response for this treatment.

At the first presentation in the clinic, we appreciated that 1 patient (1.33%) had only rectal involvement, 25 (31.97%) had procto-sigmoiditis and 50 (66.67%) had lesions that extend till the splenic flexure, but none was diagnosed with PARP from the first beginning.

In regard to extraintestinal manifestations, 67 patients (87.67%) had none, but 3 of them had ankylosing spondylitis, 1 had hemolytic anemia, 3 had dermatologic disease (vitiligo and eritema nodosum) and 2 had hepatobiliary disease (primary sclerosing cholangitis and gallstones).

The surgeries performed for other pathologies are as follows: renal pathology (urolithiasis) -7 patients, cardiac pathology (coronary artery bypass graft surgery)-1 patient, neurosurgical pathology-1 patient and proctological impairment (anal fissure and hemorrhoids)-2 patients.

The report from the endoscopist showed typical features of UC at the index colonoscopy, with erythema, friability, ulcerations and granularity, without a specific aspect of PARP, but in evolution, this appearance was described in 7 patients, and the degree of macroscopic inflammation was at least moderate.

7 of the 76 eligible patients had PARP reported endoscopically, during their follow-up visits. Of this 7 patients, most of them (5) were non- smoking males, lived in the urban area and there weren't any important distinctions between those with or without PARP, in terms of age or progression of disease, but one woman had a restorative proctocolectomy with ileal pouch-anal anastomosis, because she failed medical therapy and the pathology specimen was used to endorse the already known diagnostic.

The endoscopy performed at the time of PARP diagnosis showed that all 7 patients had continuous lesions till the splenic flexure, meaning that for this group of patients, the lesions remained constant as extension.

There were 191 colonoscopies performed for all patients that had macroscopic and documented histological display of UC and 24 of it were performed for the 7 patient with PARP during the 3 year follow-up (median number of 3 colonoscopies, with a range of 2- 6). Biopsies from the cecum were taken every time a macroscopic appearance of AOI was suggested and out histopathologist noted the presence of basal plasmocitosis, chronic inflammatory infiltrate, the presence of neutrophils in lamina propria or in the epithelium and as well as the presence of erosions or ulcerations, calculating Nancy index in order to assess the histological disease activity. This histological activity resembled the activity shown in distal disease. All 7 patients with PARP obtain a grade 4 of the Nancy score, which is the analogous to severely active disease.

None of these patients had an escalation of treatment, after they were diagnosed with PARP lesions. It is important to mention that one person was found to have Crohn's disease during the natural process, distinguished by the the appearance of complex perianal fistulas. The diagnostic was then supported by histopatology and radiologic findings.

CONCLUSION

Endoscopic and histopathologic classification of inflammatory bowel disease is of critical importance in order to establish a clear diagnostic and implement the correct

medication. Although this specific entity is neglected by endoscopists and not all of them report it, the cecal patch is a signature lesion in ulcerative colitis, about which all those involved in the treatment of such disease should be aware, not to be confused with Crohn's disease. Nonetheless, a "cecal patch" of confined periappendiceal inflammation, probably due to normal immune cell density is a autograph skip lesion, contravening the well-known idea of continuous damage of the colonic mucosa. In our group of patients, the presence of PARP was not significantly correlated with an increased risk of proximal disease extension, so further studies are needed, with a larger group of patients to determine if there is a disparate prognosis in terms of disease severity, extension of the lesions or progress to colorectal cancer. To conclude, these patients should be prudently followed-up with complete colonoscopy and even though our colleagues described this entity, the idea that it was not missed on other occasions cannot be ruled out with certainty.

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ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY: PRESENT AND FUTURE NARRATIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT:

ACUTE RENAL INJURY (AKI) IS A CLINICAL SYNDROME THAT HAS MULTIPLE ETIOLOGIES AND IS CHARACTERIZED BY A DECREASE IN KIDNEY FUNCTION. AKI IS A FAIRLY COMMON DIAGNOSIS IN HOSPITALIZED PATIENTS, WITH AN INCREASING INCIDENCE IN RECENT DECADES, BEING ASSOCIATED WITH LOW OUTCOMES AND HIGH HOSPITALIZATION COSTS. GIVEN THE STEADY PROGRESS OF THE LAST DECADE IN THIS REVIEW, WE BRIEFLY DISCUSS THE EVOLUTION OVER TIME OF THE AKI DEFINITION, CLASSIFICATION, NEW METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.

KEYWORDS: ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY, BIOMARKERS, PENTOXIFILINE, NEPHROTOXICS, SARS COV-2.

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INTRODUCTION

Acute kidney failure is the clinical syndrome with multiple etiology and variable severity that is defined by a rapid reduction in glomerular filtration rate (eGFR)¹⁴, (rapid decrease in hours or in weeks), phenomenon leading to nitrogen retention, which can affect free kidneys or those with coexisting chronic kidney disease (CKD)¹⁵.

Many patients have a mixed etiology in which the presence of ischemia, sepsis and nephrotoxicity often co-exist and complicate treatment and early diagnosis. However, this syndrome is quite common among patients without comorbidities and is essential that doctors, especially those without specialization in kidney disease¹⁶, make an early diagnosis¹⁷.

The incidence of AKI has increased in recent decades, as the recognition of the diagnosis is increased, another reason is the increase in life expectancy, the presence of comorbidities such as CKD, and prolonged exposure to nephrotoxics. Although there has been a global decline in global mortality in recent years, it is well recognized that mortality increases with more severe AKI and can reach up to 60% in those with severe conditions¹⁸.

In recently published meta-analyzes, the incidence of AKI in hospital patients using the definition of KDIGO was approximately 22.3% in North America, 31.0% in South America, Australia, and approximately 16.9% in New Zealand 19,3% and 25.2% in Europe. Incidence rate increases globally over 10 years¹⁹.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was conducted in accordance with published guidelines for systematic review, analysis, and reporting of meta-analyses of observational studies.

DIAGNOSIS AND NEW BIOMARKERS FOR AKI

The definition of AKI has undergone significant changes in recent years²⁰, because it does not adequately define the complexity of the phenomena that occur in a kidney impairment, and has been replaced in the literature with Acute Kidney Injury (AKI). This term, more correctly, includes all changes that occur when there is a kidney injury²¹, because

¹⁴ J. Gameiro, F. J. Agapito, S. Jorge and J. Lopes, "Acute Kidney Injury Definition and Diagnosis: A Narrative Review," *J Clin Med.*, vol. 7, no. 10, p. 307, 2018; A. Covic, M. Apetrii, Ş. Ardeleanu and et al, "Nefrologie," in *Principii teoretice și practice*, Iași, Demiurg, 2011, p. 531.

¹⁵ A. Covic, M. Apetrii, Ş. Ardeleanu and et al, "Nefrologie," in *Principii teoretice și practice*, Iași, Demiurg, 2011, p. 531.

¹⁶ R. Wiersema, S. Jukarainen, R. Eck and et al, "Different applications of the KDIGO criteria for AKI lead to different incidences in critically ill patients: a post hoc analysis from the prospective observational SICS-II study," *Crit Care*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 164, 2020.

¹⁷ Z. Li, L. Cai, X. Liang, Z. Du, Y. Chen, S. An, N. Tan, L. Xu, R. Li, L. Li and W. Shi, "Identification and predicting short-term prognosis of early cardiorenal syndrome type 1: KDIGO is superior to RIFLE or AKIN," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 9, no. 12, p. e114369, 2014.

¹⁸ J. Gameiro, J. Fonseca, F. Marques and J. Lopes, "Management of Acute Kidney Injury Following Major Abdominal Surgery: A Contemporary Review," *J Clin Med*, vol. 9, no. 8, p. 2679, 2020.

¹⁹ S. Goldstein, B. Jaber, S. Faubel and L. Chawla, "Acute Kidney Injury Advisory Group of American Society of Nephrology. AKI transition of care: a potential opportunity to detect and prevent CKD," *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol.*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 476-83, 2013.

²⁰ S. L. Makris K, "Acute Kidney Injury: Definition, Pathophysiology and Clinical Phenotypes," *Clin Biochem Rev*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 85-98, 2016.

²¹ A. Covic, M. Apetrii, Ş. Ardeleanu and et al, "Nefrologie," in *Principii teoretice și practice*, Iași, Demiurg, 2011, p. 531.

the earliest and most standardized diagnosis of AKI is important for epidemiological, scientific and clinical purposes²².

In 2004, at the initiative of the ADQI group (Acute Dialysis Quality Improvement Initiative) proposed an AKI classification system ("Risk, injury, failure, loss, end stage kidney disease" -RIFLE)²³. RIFLE criteria are commonly based on: acute changes in serum creatinine and the presence of oligo-anuria²⁴, which have been slightly updated in a new AKIN (Acute Kidney Injury Network) classification to increase the sensitivity of the diagnosis²⁵. The definition of KDIGO (Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes) is based²⁶ on three diagnostic criteria: increased serum creatinine, oligo-anuria, initiation of renal function replacement therapy²⁷.

The AKIN classification emerged from the joint work of nephrologists and intensive care physicians to make the AKI criteria more sensitive and reliable compared to the RIFLE criteria. These definitions did not show a better prognostic acuity in terms of mortality, although it allowed the identification of a larger number of patients with AKI²⁸. KDIGO group instead has implemented changes in AKI staging, this new classification has been important for medical practice, especially in terms of time, KDIGO covering both AKIN and RIFLE criteria, taking into account creatinine changes in serum within 48 hours or a decrease in eRFG within 7 days. Furthermore, patients under 18 years of age with eRFG < 35 mL/min and patients with serum creatinine > 4.0 mg/dL were added in AKIN stage 3²⁹.

²² W. Huber, J. Schneider, T. Lahmer and et al, "Validation of RIFLE, AKIN, and a modified AKIN definition ("backward classification") of acute kidney injury in a general ICU: Analysis of a 1-year period," *Medicine (Baltimore)*, vol. 97, no. 38, p. e12465, 2018.

²³ C. Ronco, J. Kellum, R. Bellomo and R. Mehta, "Acute Dialysis Quality Initiative (ADQI)," *Contrib Nephrol.*, vol. 182, pp. 1-4, 2013.

²⁴ A. Libório, K. Branco and C. Torres de Melo Bezerra, "Acute kidney injury in neonates: from urine output to new biomarkers," *Biomed Res Int.*, vol. 2014:601568., 2014.

²⁵ J. Lopes and S. Jorge, "The RIFLE and AKIN classifications for acute kidney injury: a critical and comprehensive review," *Clin Kidney J.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 8-14, 2013; R. Chu, C. Li, S. Wang, W. Zou, G. Liu and L. Yang, "Assessment of KDIGO definitions in patients with histopathologic evidence of acute renal disease," *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol.*, vol. 9, no. 7, pp. 1175-1182, 2014.

²⁶ J. Jonny, M. Hasyim, V. Angelia and et al. , "Incidence of acute kidney injury and use of renal replacement therapy in intensive care unit patients in Indonesia," *BMC Nephrol*, vol. 21, no. 191, 2020.

²⁷ R. Wiersema, S. Jukarainem, R. Eck and et al, "Different applications of the KDIGO criteria for AKI lead to different incidences in critically ill patients: a post hoc analysis from the prospective observational SICS-II study," *Crit Care*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 164, 2020.

²⁸ J. Lopes and S. Jorge, "The RIFLE and AKIN classifications for acute kidney injury: a critical and comprehensive review," *Clinical Kinney Journal*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 8-14, 2013.

²⁹ T. Levi, S. de Souza, J. de Magalhães, M. de Carvalho, A. Cunha, J. Dantas, M. Cruz, Y. Guimarães, M. Cruz, Y. Guimarães and C. Cruz, "Comparison of the RIFLE, AKIN and KDIGO criteria to predict mortality in critically ill patients," *Rev Bras Ter Intensiva.*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 290-296, 2013.

Table 1 Classifications for AKI: RIFLE, AKIN and KDIGO (adapted from Shin SR et al.)³⁰.

Criterion (name for RIFLE)	RIFLE	KDIGO	AKIN	The value of diuresis
Stage 1 (Risk)	≥1,5 the baseline creatinine or ↓ eRFG > 25%	≥ 0,3mg/dl increase in creatinine or ↑ ≥ 1,5 times baseline creatinine	≥ 0,3mg/dl increase in creatinine in 48h or ↑ ≥ 1,5 – 1,9 times baseline creatinine within 7 days	< 0,5 ml/kg/h in > 6 hours
Stage 2 (Injury)	≥ 2,2 baseline creatinine or ↓ eRFG > 50%	≥ 2 x baseline creatinine	2,0-2,9 times baseline within 7 days	< 0,5 ml/kg/h within 12 hours
Stage 3 (End stage)	≥ 3 x baseline creatinine or creatinine ≥ 4 mg/dl or ↓ eRFG ≥ 75%	≥ 3 x baseline creatinine	≥3 times baseline within 7 days or increase to ≥ 4 mg/dl with an acute increase of initiation of dialysis	< 0,3 ml/kg/h in 24 hours or anuria for > 12hours
Loss of kidney function	Complete loss of kidney function for > 4 weeks	-	-	-
Kidney disease in the end stage	Complete loss of kidney function > 3 months	-	-	-

The use of non-invasive biomarkers in the diagnosis and management of various pathologies is increasingly reported in the literature, also, their use is particularly important for certain age groups³¹.

Serum creatinine is an imperfect biological marker of eGFR that does not allow the identification of mild forms of AKI or CKD in the early stages, thus does not allow the differentiation of prerenal AKI from intrinsic AKI (acute tubular necrosis (ATN), acute glomerulonephritis) or in lupus nephropathy where intrinsic AKI is present but serum creatinine may be normal or elevated³².

The increase in serum creatinine above the upper limit occurs at a reduction of more than 50% eGFR, and therefore it is necessary to calculate eGFR, by creatinine clearance. The

³⁰ S. Shin, W. Kim, D. Kim, I. Shin and J. Sohn, "Prediction and Prevention of Acute Kidney Injury after Cardiac Surgery," *Biomed Res. Int.*, vol. 2016, 2016.

³¹ R. Ali, F. Al-Obaidi and H. Arif, "The Role of Urinary N-acetyl Beta-D-glucosaminidase in Children with Urological Problems," *Oman Med J*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 285-288, 2014.

³² R. Musa, L. Brent and A. Qurie, "Lupus Nephritis," *StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL)*, 2021.

value of serum creatinine also varies depending on age, sex, muscle mass of the patient and eGFR (creatinine excretion)³³.

Currently, eGFR is the standard marker for AKI or CKD. However, eGFR is almost never measured directly in the clinical setting, and surrogate markers of renal function are frequently used. The current eGFR equations (MDRD Study, Cockcroft-Gault and CKD-EPI) cannot be used when the creatinine concentration is not at steady state, as is the case with those who develop AKI because the patient may become oligo-anuric where it should be considered. that eGFR is <10 ml/min³⁴.

eGFR values are associated with age, sex and body surface area and normal values are between 120 and 130 mL/min at 1.73 m² in young men and women, respectively (eGFR decreases with age)³⁵, or co-occurring disease states (heart disease, diabetes, sepsis, etc.)³⁶.

Recently, the new biomarkers identified for AKI are either low molecular weight proteins that are present in the systemic circulation. They are glomerular filtered (ie markers of glomerular function), either inflammatory mediators released by renal cells or infiltrating inflammatory cells (ie markers of the degree of damage and indicators of the location of the lesion). Small proteins could be enzymes that are released by tubular cells in the urine after tubular cell damage (ie markers of tubular damage)³⁷.

Modern genomics and proteomics techniques have identified several renal biological markers, such as: cystatin C, kidney injury molecule-1, N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase (NAG), α 1/ β 2-microglobulin neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin, interleukin-18, liver-type fatty acid-binding protein, γ -glutamyl transpeptidase, pi-glutathione S-transferase (pi-GST), retinol binding protein (RBP), etc³⁸.

The urinary NAG index value is expressed as the ratio of NAG to urinary creatinine, as this relationship shows less variability than urinary enzyme excretion as a function of volume or time³⁹, which has the ability to change its values early compared to other markers traditionally used (urea, creatinine)⁴⁰.

Another study demonstrates the variation of the urinary NAG index before the increase in serum urea and serum creatinine⁴¹.

Among patients, the evaluation of urinary NAG activity is used to monitor the nephrotoxic effects of aminoglycosides, heavy metals or to diagnose diabetic nephropathy.

³³ E. Mota and et al, "Compendiu de Nefrologie," in *Compendiu de Nefrologie*, Craiova, Editura Medicală Universitară, 2010, p. 55.

³⁴ K. M. Peter, K. H. Raymond and D. L. Kathleen, "Management of Acute Kidney Injury: Core Curriculum 2018," *American Journal Kidney Diseases*, vol. 72, no. 1, pp. 136-148, 2018.

³⁵ S. Lopez-Giacoman and M. Madero, "Biomarkers in chronic kidney disease, from kidney function to kidney damage," *World J Nephrol*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 57-73, 2015.

³⁶ V. Vaidya, M. Ferguson and J. Bonventre, "Biomarkers of acute kidney injury," *Annu Rev Pharmacol Toxicol.*, vol. 48, pp. 463-493, 2008;48:463-493.

³⁷ M. Ostermann, B. Philips and L. Forni, "Clinical review: Biomarkers of acute kidney injury: where are we now?," *Crit Care*, vol. 16, no. 5, p. 233, 2012.

³⁸ S. Firu, C. Streba, D. Firu, D. Tache and I. Rogoveanu, "Neutrophil Gelatinase Associated Lipocalin (NGAL) - a biomarker of renal dysfunction in patients with liver cirrhosis: Do we have enough proof?," *J Med Life.*, vol. 8, pp. 15-20, 2015.

³⁹ R. Ali, F. Al-Obaidi and H. Arif, "The Role of Urinary N-acetyl Beta-D-glucosaminidase in Children with Urological Problems," *Oman Med J*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 285-288, 2014.

⁴⁰ W. Han, S. Waikar, A. Johnson, R. Betensky, C. Dent, P. Devarajan and J. Bonventre, "Urinary biomarkers in the early diagnosis of acute kidney injury," *Kidney Int*, vol. 73, no. 7, pp. 863-869, 2008.

⁴¹ R. Sato, S. Soeta, M. Miyazaki, B. Syuto, J. Sato, Y. Miyake, J. Yasuda, K. Okada and Y. Naito, "Clinical availability of urinary N-acetyl-beta-D-glucosaminidase index in dogs with urinary diseases," *J Vet Med Sci*, vol. 64, no. 4, pp. 361-5, 2002.

Elevated values of urinary NAG have been found in patients with nephrotic syndrome or in patients with kidney malformations⁴². Although it may be a good biomarker for AKI, false positive values have been reported in patients with diabetes, rheumatoid arthritis or hyperthyroidism⁴³.

Serum cystatin C (Cys C) has emerged as a possible alternative to creatinine, but its accuracy may be adversely affected by thyroid dysfunction or systemic inflammatory syndrome. Cys C concentration increases in serum earlier in AKI than serum creatinine, therefore Cys C is often considered a "better creatinine"⁴⁴.

New biomarkers can complete the measurement of creatinine clearance or most likely improve the accuracy of AKI diagnosis when used in combination. However, new biomarkers need to demonstrate their clinical applicability, accuracy and cost-effectiveness before implementation in clinical practice⁴⁵. Another reason for new biomarkers applicability in clinical practice is that they have not yet been evaluated with sufficient data in very specific populations for example (infants and the elderly)⁴⁶.

CLASIFICACION AND PHISIOPATHOLOGY AKI

An essential function of the kidneys is the excretion and filtration of nitrogen toxins from the body. To achieve this, the kidneys usually receive a quarter of the cardiac output, and when AKI occurs there is a rapid decrease in eGFR which leads to significant nitrogen retention⁴⁷. From a pathophysiological point of view, AKI can be grouped into three broad categories from an etiological point of view⁴⁸.

Prerenal AKI causes:

AKI etiology of prerenal cause includes: hypovolemia (hemorrhage, vomiting, excessive sweating, diarrhea, low fluid intake, burns, kidney loss, congestive heart failure), drug-induced vasodilation, autonomic neuropathy, anaphylactic shock, or renal vasoconstriction, decreased cardiac output. The latter can be caused by a heart attack, pulmonary hypertension and excessive peripheral vasodilation associated with sepsis. Usually, a rapid volume recovery therapy will improve renal function, so maintaining an eGFR within normal limits largely depends on optimal renal infusion⁴⁹.

⁴² S. Kovarikova, "Urinary biomarkers of renal function in dogs: a review," *Veterinari Medicina*, vol. 60, no. 11, p. 589–602, 2015.

⁴³ F. Lombardia, A. Muryan, R. Canzonieri and H. Trimarchi, "Biomarkers in acute kidney injury: Evidence or paradigm?," *Nefrologia*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 333-464, 2016.

⁴⁴ B. Griffin, K. Gist and S. Faubel, "Current Status of Novel Biomarkers for the Diagnosis of Acute Kidney Injury: A Historical Perspective," *J Intensive Care Med.*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 415-424, 2020.

⁴⁵ M. Schmid, D. Dalela, R. Tahbaz, J. Langetepe, M. Randazzo, R. Dahlem, M. Fisch, Q. Trinh and F. Chun, "Novel biomarkers of acute kidney injury: Evaluation and evidence in urologic surgery," *World J Nephrol.*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 160-168, 2015.

⁴⁶ S. Pozzoli, M. Simonini and P. Manunta, "Predicting acute kidney injury: current status and future challenges," *J Nephrol.*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 209-223, 2018.

⁴⁷ H. Manzoor and H. Bhatt, "Prerenal Kidney Failure," *In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL), 2020.*

⁴⁸ S. Bindroo, B. Quintanilla Rodriguez and H. Challa, "Renal Failure," *StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL), 2021.*

⁴⁹ A. M. S. T. Basile DP, "Pathophysiology of acute kidney injury," *Compr Physiol*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 1303-1353, 2012.

Intrinsic AKI causes

AKI is results from damage to the renal tubules, vascular structures, glomerulus interstitial, or from obstruction of the renal tubules. intrinsic causes are 10% -50% of all cases of AKI⁵⁰. Ischemic ATN and prerenal nitrogen retention have the same pathophysiological spectrum, so any precipitating factor leading to prerenal nitrogen retention can produce ischemic ATN and may have the same etiology the prerenal causes previously mentioned⁵¹.

Drug-induced intrinsic AKI

Drugs exert therapeutic effects as well as side effects by interacting with certain molecules. These molecular targets are often receptors or enzymes, which propagate a signal from the drug through the effector pathways that ultimately determine the effects of the drug on an organ or the function of the whole body. Drug side effects are additional side effects, usually undesirable, which may occur through the same mechanism of action as the therapeutic effect or through a mechanism distinct from it⁵².

The presence of certain pharmaceutical agents can produce ATN leading to damage to the cells of the proximal tubes by the formation of free radicals, alteration of mitochondrial cells and damage to transport systems. The main nephrotoxic substances that are frequently associated with ATN⁵³ are most commonly caused by antibiotics, contrast agents, cocaine, cisplatin and antiretroviral agents (adefovir, cidofovir, tenofovir, foscarnet)⁵⁴, organic solvents, bacterial toxins, administration of intravenous immunoglobulins, natural poisons (mushroom poisoning, snake venom) and synthetics, pigments, myoglobin, crystalloids (uric acid, oxalates, calcium deposited at the tubular level), methemoglobin or tumor necrosis products⁵⁵.

Medications are the most common cause of acute interstitial nephropathy (AIN) in all age groups. Non-steroidal antibiotics and anti-inflammatory drugs are commonly associated with AINs, rifampicin, allopurinol and acyclovir are other drugs that can cause AINs. In theory, any drug can precipitate AINs, and the list of contraventional drugs has grown over time⁵⁶.

Crystal nephropathy is caused by antivirals (acyclovir), and antibiotics (such as ampicillin)⁵⁷. Chemotherapy used in leukemia can also induce tumor lysis syndrome, a condition characterized by the release of uric acid from dead blood cells and the monosodium urate crystal that precipitates in tubular lumen⁵⁸.

⁵⁰ B. McDaniel and M. Bentley, "The role of medications and their management in acute kidney injury," *Integr Pharm Res Pract.*, vol. 4, pp. 21-29, 2015.

⁵¹ M. Hanif, A. Bali and K. Ramphul, "Acute Renal Tubular Necrosis," *StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL)*, 2020.

⁵² S. Berger and R. Iyengar, "Role of systems pharmacology in understanding drug adverse events," *Wiley Interdiscip Rev Syst Biol Med*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 129-135, 2011.

⁵³ A. Covic, M. Apetrii, Ș. Ardeleanu and et al, "Nefrologie," in *Principii teoretice și practice în nefrologie*, Iași, Demiurg, 2011, p. 536.

⁵⁴ B. McDaniel and M. Bentley, "The role of medications and their management in acute kidney injury," *Integr Pharm Res Pract.*, vol. 4, pp. 21-29, 2015.

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⁵⁶ R. Naik and P. Annamaraju, "Interstitial Nephritis," In: *StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL)*, 2021.

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⁵⁸ S. R. Mulay, C. Shi, X. Ma and H. Anders, "Novel Insights into Crystal-Induced Kidney Injury," *Kidney Dis*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 49-57, 2018.

Table 2 Examples of nephrotoxic drugs (adapted from Janak Patel⁵⁹).

Drug	Class	Affected Aria
Acetaminophen	Analgesic	ATN,
Acetazolamide	Carbonic anhydrase inhibitor	Acidosis TP
Allopurinol	Hypouricemic	AIN
Furosemide	Diuretic loop	AIN
Rifampicin	Antibiotic	AIN
Tacrolimus	Immunosuppressive	ATN
Tetracycline	Antibiotic	ATN
VAN	Antibiotic	AIN

SARS COV-2 ASSOCIATED AKI

Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is an infection that causes coronavirus disease 2019⁶⁰, this disease affects people around the world, with an increased mortality rate between 0, 9% and 7.2%, depending on demographic data, implementation of preventive measures, testing strategies and availability of health care resources⁶¹.

The most common and important clinical manifestations of COVID-19 are febrile conditions (98%), dry cough (76%), fatigue and myalgia (18% each), with the presence of leukopenia (25%) and lymphopenia (63%). Symptoms of upper respiratory tract infection with productive cough and rhinorrhea are uncommon in adults, but more common in adolescents and children. The clinical course of SARS-CoV-2 infection is unpredictable and shows great variability, ranging from asymptomatic infection to multi-organ systemic failure or death (16% -20% being classified as severe or critical)⁶².

In addition, the mortality rate is high when the patient has associated pathologies, such as lung or kidney pathologies. A close association between AKI and coronavirus infection has been reported in SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV epidemics. Data from the literature reported that AKI developed in approximately 5% to 15% of cases and the mortality rate was high (70% to 90%) in MERS-CoV and SARS infections⁶³.

AKI during COVID-19 infection is due to different triggers. Such as: ATN, renal hypoperfusion, irregular inflammatory response, microcirculatory dysfunction, cytokine storm syndrome present in sepsis, direct viral damage and metabolic changes. The presence of angiotensin 2 conversion enzyme receptors in renal tissues could also facilitate viral invasion, resulting in direct damage⁶⁴.

Histopathological examinations in COVID-19 infected patients with AKI are limited, but the available evidence suggests that there are many causes of AKI in COVID-19. A study of 26 patients with COVID-19 and AKI showed acute tubular lesions and the presence of

⁵⁹ J. Patel and A. Sapra, "Nephrotoxic Medications," *StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL)*, 2020.

⁶⁰ A. Ahmed, C. Ebad, S. Stoneman, M. Satti and P. Conlon, "Kidney injury in COVID-19," *World J Nephrol*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 18-32, 2020; N. Saraladevi, Y. Chih-Wei, H. Shang-Jyh, L. Bi-Cheng, C. Jiang-Hua and J. Vivekanand, "The Novel Coronavirus 2019 epidemic and kidneys," *Kidney International*, vol. 97, no. 5, pp. 824-828, 2020.

⁶¹ A. Ahmed, C. Ebad, S. Stoneman, M. Satti and P. Conlon, "Kidney injury in COVID-19," *World J Nephrol*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 18-32, 2020.

⁶² N. Saraladevi, Y. Chih-Wei, H. Shang-Jyh, L. Bi-Cheng, C. Jiang-Hua and J. Vivekanand, "The Novel Coronavirus 2019 epidemic and kidneys," *Kidney International*, vol. 97, no. 5, pp. 824-828, 2020.

⁶³ F. Fabrizi, C. Alfieri, R. Cerutti, G. Lunghi and P. Messa, "COVID-19 and Acute Kidney Injury: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis," *Pathogens*, vol. 9, no. 12, p. 1052, 2020.

⁶⁴ T. Mallhi, Y. Khan and A. Adnan, "Stratification of Acute Kidney Injury in COVID-19," *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, vol. 103, no. 6, pp. 2164-2167, 2020.

viral particles in both the tubular epithelium and the podocyte at microscopic examination on histopathological examination, which demonstrates a direct kidney infection⁶⁵.

Figure 1: AKI pathophysiology in Covid-19 Adapted from Batlle D. et al.⁶⁶

CONTRAST SUBSTANCES-INDUCED AKI

Contrast substances-induced AKI formerly known as contrast-induced nephropathy is a syndrome in which acute kidney dysfunction is diagnosed after intravascular administration of contrast agents. Contrasting agents are widely used for therapeutic and diagnostic purposes. Their nephrotoxicity was first reported 50 years ago and today is one of the most common causes of AKI in hospitalized patients. The pathophysiology is not very well defined. Animal models of AKI suggest several potential mechanisms of nephrotoxicity, including renal ischemia, vasoconstriction, reactive oxygen species formation, and direct tubular toxicity, leading to decreased renal perfusion⁶⁷.

Postrenal cause AKI

The most common causes of postrenal AKI are obstruction created by kidney stones, ureteral stones, tumors and thrombi, from those the most encountered etiology of post-renal AKI is obstruction of the ureter. Another noteworthy fact is that a unilateral obstruction of the ureter cannot always produce AKI, the other kidney can compensate for the malfunction of the contralateral kidney and also because the obstruction is gradually formed (as in the case of the tumors)⁶⁸.

⁶⁵ M. Nadim, L. Forni, R. Mehta and e. al., "COVID-19-associated acute kidney injury: consensus report of the 25th Acute Disease Quality Initiative (ADQI) Workgroup," *Nat Rev Nephrol*, vol. 16, p. 747–764, 2020.

⁶⁶ D. Batlle, M. Soler, M. Sparks, S. Hiremath, A. South, P. Welling and S. Swaminathan, "Acute Kidney Injury in COVID-19: Emerging Evidence of a Distinct Pathophysiology," *JASN*, vol. 31, no. 7, pp. 1380-1383, 2020.

⁶⁷ S. L. Makris K, "Acute Kidney Injury: Definition, Pathophysiology and Clinical Phenotypes," *Clin Biochem Rev*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 85-98, 2016.

⁶⁸ A. Goyal, P. Daneshpajouhnejad, M. Hashmi and e. al., "Acute Kidney Injury (Acute Renal Failure)," *StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL)*, 2020.

Figure 2: Classification physiopathology for AKI (Adapted from Makris K and colab⁶⁹).

TREATMENT AND NEPHROPROTECTION IN AKI

Treatment goals in patients with AKI include: optimization or preservation of renal function done through hydro-electrolytic and acid-base balancing. Also, mineral deficiency compensation is necessary in order to minimize the damage to secondary organs from AKI and good management of the effects of decreased renal function⁷⁰.

THERAPY WITH FLUIDS

The main indication for fluid administration in AKI is to optimize intravascular circulating volume, increase cardiac output and increase infusion with the main purpose of improving renal blood flow and glomerular function. Although hypotension is a strong risk factor for AKI, preserving blood pressure alone is not enough to ensure adequate renal perfusion⁷¹.

Hypovolemia can precipitate drug-induced AKI, however, current evidence supporting preventive hydration is merely observational studies, with no consensus on the timing, type of solution used saj volulum required. Extension of prophylactic volume has been shown to prevent damage caused by antivirals, amphotericin B foscarnet, adefovir or

⁶⁹ S. L. Makris K, "Acute Kidney Injury: Definition, Pathophysiology and Clinical Phenotypes," *Clin Biochem Rev*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 85-98, 2016.

⁷⁰ V. Kher, N. Srisawat, E. Noiri and e. al., "Prevention and Therapy of Acute Kidney Injury in the Developing World," *Kidney Int Rep.*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 544-558, 2017.

⁷¹ M. Ostermann, K. Liu and K. Kashani, "Fluid Management in Acute Kidney Injury," *Contemporary Reviews In Critical Care Medicine*, vol. 3, pp. 594-603, 2019.

cidofovir, as well as drugs that cause crystalline nephropathy, such as acyclovir, indinavir and sulfadiazine⁷².

Crystalloids are fluids used for the treatment of AKI, which contain ionic solutions, which are able to circulate through the semipermeable membranes. Crystalloids are the most commonly used in-hospital fluids worldwide and are financially less expensive than colloids. Crystalloids contain NaCl and other anions that cause increased extracellular fluid tonicity, with the exception of glucose. These physicochemical properties are important factors that determine the effectiveness of the crystalloids for the expansion of vascular volume⁷³. In the same time, those physicochemical properties rise the potential of crystalloids for renal toxicity.

Hydration can also have adverse effects especially in patients with reduced cardiac and renal function. It creates an increased risk of pulmonary edema, the main recommendation being to reduce the volume of hydration to prevent fluid overload (which may increase the risk of suboptimal renal treatment)⁷⁴.

The SAFE study compares the effect of saline administration on albumin on mortality in a heterogeneous population of UTI patients. In principle, the study did not indicate statistically significant differences in the risk of death among patients receiving saline compared with those receiving albumin⁷⁵.

VASSOPRESOR DRUGS

Vasoactive drugs produce systemic vasoconstriction, thus increasing renal infusion⁷⁶ vasopressin is one of the drugs that is gaining popularity in the treatment of refractory shock of norepinephrine. Noradrenaline improves diuresis compared to vasopressin, but it has not yet been shown to increase survival or reduce the need for dialysis. It has not yet been established exactly which vasopressor agent is most effective in preventing or treating patients with AKI septic shock. Most studies have focused on dopamine, norepinephrine or vasopressin⁷⁷.

THERPAY WITH DIURETICS

Patients with AKI may develop fluid retention and oligo-anuria, which are associated with additional complications, such as respiratory failure or anasarca. In many studies, oliguric AKI has been associated with poorer results than non-oliguric AKI and the use of diuretics in oliguric AKI is common⁷⁸.

Furosemide is a loop diuretic that is intensively used in emergency medicine and intensive care because it provides the opportunity to eliminate large amounts of water and

⁷² M. Joannidis, W. Druml, L. Forni and et al, "Prevention of acute kidney injury and protection of renal function in the intensive care unit: update 2017," *Intensive Care Med*, vol. 43, p. 730–749, 2017.

⁷³ S. Finfer, J. Myburgh and R. Bellomo, "Intravenous fluid therapy in critically ill adults," *Nat Rev Nephrol*, vol. 14, p. 541–557, 2018.

⁷⁴ W. Vandenberghe and E. Hoste, "Contrast-associated acute kidney injury: does it really exist, and if so, what to do about it?," *F1000 Research*, vol. 8, no. F1000, p. 753, 2019.

⁷⁵ J. Myburgh, D. Cooper, S. Finfer, R. Bellomo, R. Norton, N. Bishop, L. S. Kai and V. Shirley, "Saline or albumin for fluid resuscitation in patients with traumatic brain injury," *N Engl J Med*, vol. 357, no. 9, pp. 874–84, 2007.

⁷⁶ D. Hertzberg, L. Rydén, J. Pickering, U. Sartipy and M. Holzmann, "Acute kidney injury-an overview of diagnostic methods and clinical management," *Clin Kidney J*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 323–331, 2017.

⁷⁷ "Section 3: Prevention and Treatment of AKI," *Kidney Int Suppl (2011)*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 37–68, 2012.

⁷⁸ N.-F. Annie-Claire and J. Bouchard, "Fluid Management and Use of Diuretics in Acute Kidney Injury," *Advances in Chronic Kidney disease*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 45–55, 2013.

electrolytes, as long as the kidneys are functional, so hyperhydration can be controlled. However, only low renal function cannot indicate the etiology of AKI. Although loop diuretics are commonly used if fluid retention results from impaired renal function, it is still debatable whether the renal prognosis itself can be improved⁷⁹.

Furosemide reduces oxygen consumption in the thick portions of the ascending branch of the Henle loop by interfering with its function and thus will protect it from ischemia. Another benefit is the inhibition of prostaglandin dehydrogenase production, as a result of which decomposes prostaglandin E which is a renal vasodilator. This decomposition of prostaglandin E is also maintaining urinary flow and could prevent renal obstruction⁸⁰.

DIALYSIS AND AKI

AKI has a high frequency in the UTI, being one of the most serious complications of patients with comorbidities in the UTI. Approximately 4% of patients in the UTI with AKI require dialysis, because specific drug therapy is not effective in patients with AKI⁸¹.

Common indications for dialysis can be 'renal' or 'non-renal', usually for the acute management of life-threatening AKI complications, such as severe uremia, oligo-anuria, severe hyperkalemia, pulmonary edema, hemorrhagic diathesis, pericarditis, uremic or uremic encephalopathy⁸². Another indication of dialysis is metabolic acidosis refractory to treatment, because the kidneys lose their excretory function, thus developing the progression of acidosis⁸³. In the meta-analysis performed by Lin WT suggested that dialysis initiated in early stages does not improve survival compared to dialysis initiated late⁸⁴.

Figure 3. Kidney function replacement device in operation

⁷⁹ D. Patschan, S. Patschan, I. Buschmann and O. Ritter, "Loop Diuretics in Acute Kidney Injury Prevention, Therapy, and Risk Stratification," *Kidney Blood Press Res*, vol. 44, pp. 457-464, 2019.

⁸⁰ A. Hegde, "Diuretics in Acute Kidney Injury." *Indian journal of critical care medicine : peer-reviewed, Indian Society of Critical Care Medicine*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. S98-S99, 2020.

⁸¹ S. Negi, D. Koreeda, S. Kobayashi and e. al, "Renal replacement therapy for acute kidney injury," *Ren Replace Ther* 2, vol. 31, 2016.

⁸² C. Nickson, "Renal replacement therapy Indications," 2020.

⁸³ M. Diaconu, R. Popa, L. Stanescu, N. Guta, C. Georgescu and M. Tancu, "Pharmacological and interdisciplinary therapeutic approach of a patient with cardiac disease, sepsis and chronic kidney disease," *Research & Science Today*, vol. 2, no. 20, pp. 205-212, 2020.

⁸⁴ W. Lin, C. Lai, . S. Chang and et al, "Effects of early dialysis on the outcomes of critically ill patients with acute kidney injury: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials," *Sci Rep*, vol. 9, p. 18283, 2019.

OTHERS THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES

Glucosteroids are drugs widely used in acute or chronic inflammatory pathology⁸⁵, and their efficacy in the treatment of drug-induced AIN has not yet been evaluated by prospective, controlled studies. Glucosteroids are frequently used in the treatment of drug-induced NSAIDs and studies have shown a good recovery of renal function⁸⁶. A multicenter, placebo-controlled, randomized, double-blind study by Laviolle B et al. indicated that low-dose hydrocortisone appears to improve renal function⁸⁷.

Pentoxifylline (PTX) administered in AKI for 14 days reduced the values of nitrogen retention and the continuation of treatment for another 14 days after stopping the administration of nephrotoxic, reduced the values of renal function within normal limits⁸⁸.

Another experimental study demonstrated the usefulness of PTX have been shown that this drug has improved microcirculation, reduced blood viscosity⁸⁹, exerts hemorrhoidal effects, erythrocyte stiffness and platelet aggregation. Its potential to reduce intraglomerular pressure has led to various studies in which PTX has been used as a nephroprotective agent. In fact, data from clinical trials and animal models support the use of PTX as an antiproteinuric agent, this property having a strong anti-inflammatory effect⁹⁰.

Figure 4.: Actions zone at kidney for different therapeutical drogs in AKI

⁸⁵ R. Popa, L. Lautaru, R. Lucretiu, D. Ruiu, D. Caragea, M. Olteanu, A. Mihailovici, C. Ene, V. Padureanu, R. Padureanu and V. Cirlig, "Therapy Side Effects in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus," *Current health sciences journal*, vol. 44, no. 3, p. 31, 2018.

⁸⁶ G. Fernandez-Juarez, J. Perez, F. Caravaca-Fontán, L. Quintana, A. Shabaka, E. Rodriguez, L. Gadola, A. de Lorenzo, M. Cobo, A. Oliet, M. Sierrax and C. Cobelo, "Duration of Treatment with Corticosteroids and Recovery of Kidney Function in Acute Interstitial Nephritis." *Clinical journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, *CJASN*, vol. 13(12), no. doi:10.2215/CJN.013901, pp. 1851-1858, 2018.

⁸⁷ B. Laviolle, D. Annane, C. Fougrou and E. Bellissant, "Gluco- and mineralocorticoid biological effects of a 7-day treatment with low doses of hydrocortisone and fludrocortisone in septic shock," *Intensive Care Medicine*, vol. 38, no. 8, pp. 1306-1314, 2012.

⁸⁸ M. Mohammad Waheed El-Anwar, M. Said Abdelmonem, M. Ebtessam Nada, M. Dalia Galhoom and M. Ahmed A. Abdelsameea, "Protective effect of pentoxifylline on amikacin-induced ototoxicity," *ENT-Ear, Nose & Throat Journal*, 2018.

⁸⁹ N.-T. Zahra, D.-K. Simin, K. Hossein and L.-P. Mahboob, "A review of the potential protective effects of pentoxifylline against drug-induced nephrotoxicity," *European journal of clinical pharmacology*, vol. 69, 2012.

⁹⁰ D.-C. Javier, G. T. Víctor, F. Carla, M.-N. Ernesto, H.-C. Carolina, U.-T. Pablo, R.-O. Marta and O. Alberto, "Pentoxifylline for Renal Protection in Diabetic Kidney Disease. A Model of Old Drugs for New Horizons," *J. Clin. Med*, vol. 8, no. 3, p. 287, 2019.

CONCLUSION

AKI is an increased complexity syndrome with a significant impact on patient outcomes; thus, prevention, early detection and prompt treatment are important to minimize mortality and morbidity. Research in the field of nephrology, especially experimental studies, has led to an improvement in the understanding of the pathophysiology of AKI, an increase in awareness of the incidence and prognostic impact. The perfect biomarker for AKI is still under study and in the future, we need to focus on early diagnostic measures, predictors and new therapeutic protocols.

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CLINICAL AND HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CORRELATIONS IN BOWEN'S DISEASE

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ABSTRACT:

BOWEN'S DISEASE (BD) IS AN IN SITU, PREINVASIVE CANCER WITH POTENTIAL FOR PROGRESSION IN SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA (SCC), BEING CLINICALLY CONSIDERED A PRECANCER WITH A HIGH POTENTIAL FOR MALIGNANCY.

THE AIMS OF THE STUDY WERE TO ASSESS THE CLINICAL, HISTOLOGICAL, AND EVOLUTIONARY ASPECTS OF THE BOWEN'S DISEASE AND INVASIVE BOWEN DISEASE.

THE STUDIED GROUP COMPRISES 50 PATIENTS DIAGNOSED WITH BOWEN DISEASE OR INVASIVE BD, HOSPITALIZED IN THE DERMATOLOGY CLINIC OF EMERGENCY COUNTY HOSPITAL OF CRAIOVA, BETWEEN 2010 AND MARCH 2021. THERE WERE 18 MALES AND 32 FEMALES, AGED 30 TO 85 YEARS, 66% OF THE PATIENTS BEING FROM THE URBAN ENVIRONMENT. THE MOST FREQUENT LOCALIZATION OF BD WAS AT THE LEVEL OF THE LIMBS (52%), ON PHOTOEXPOSED AREAS. IN 92% OF CASES, WE NOTICED CLINICAL ASPECT OF BD WITH SINGLE LESIONS AND THE TYPICAL FORM WAS PREDOMINANCE (80%).

THE PATHOLOGY DIAGNOSED 41 BD AND 9 INVASIVE BD (SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA). PRESUMPTIVE CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS IN 31 CASES (57.40%), WAS CONFIRMED BY HISTOPATHOLOGICAL EXAMINATION.

THE CORRELATION OF CLINICAL, HISTOPATHOLOGICAL DATA LEAD TO AN ACCURATE DIAGNOSIS OF BD. BOWEN'S DISEASE, ALONG WITH OTHER KERATINOCYTIC PRECANCERS, BEING A STRONG PREDICTOR OF THE RISK OF DEVELOPING SKIN CARCINOMAS AND MELANOMA, REQUIRING A PROMPT THERAPEUTIC ATTITUDE AND CAREFUL MONITORING.

KEYWORDS: BOWEN DISEASE, SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA, EPIDEMIOLOGY, HISTOPATHOLOGY.

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INTRODUCTION

Bowen's disease is a rare condition, described by Bowen in 1912 as "atypical cancerous epithelial proliferation." Subsequently, the clinical and nosologically framework of the disease extends, including erythroplasia Queyrat, which is distinguished from Bowen's disease by its localization on the mucous membranes^{8 9}.

Bowen's disease can occur at any age and gender, rarely, cases have been described at the age of under 30 years. Patients are usually affected in the 6-8 decade of life^{1,2,3}.

The lesions are localized and on areas not exposed to the sun, but there is a predilection for sun exposed areas. The lesions are usually unique, but in 10-20% of patients they are multiple. In men, the lesions are localized especially on the alopecia scalp, anterior ears and thorax and in women on the cheeks and lower limbs.

In immunocompromised patients, BB occurs at younger ages, the lesions are larger, and the trunk, limbs and neck are particularly affected, and they have more frequent relapsing forms compared to immunocompetent people.

In the appearance of the lesion are involved many favorable factors that act synergistically in the development of the tumor in context of an immunosuppression or a genetic predisposition^{1,2}.

Many factors are involved in the development and tumor progression: chronic arsenic exposure (rarely encountered), in which the lesions are multiple; exposure to insecticides; chronic exposure to the sun, explaining the localizations in 2/3 of the cases on the discovered parts; ionizing radiation; infection with HPV, HHV8 (in the lesions of patients with organ transplantation); immunosuppression; traumatic injuries^{1,2,10}.

The diagnosis is suggested by the presence of localized ano-genital plaques or glabra areas, a few centimeters in size, well delimited and squamous with moderate erythema, in usually elderly patients; frequently, lesions occur on areas chronically exposed to the sun, women being more frequently affected. Dermoscopy is useful both in the diagnosis of Bowen's disease and in the posttherapeutic monitoring, the existence of dermatoscopic vascular structures after the treatment being associated with the residual disease¹¹. In the pigmented version, the presence of diffuse, irregular pigmentation or irregularly distributed points and globules can be observed¹².

Positive diagnosis of the lesion is based on clinical suspicion, then confirmed by histopathological exam.

AIM

This study objectives were to evaluate epidemiological, clinical evolutive, and histopathological features of BD and invasive BD hospitalized in Dermatology Department of Craiova.

⁸ Dimitrescu A., Trifu P., Precancerale și cancerile cutanate, Ed. Medicală, București, 1992, 10-74.

⁹ Markus V. Hept, Gabriel Schlager, Carola Berking. Epithelial Precancerous Lesions In: Kang S., Amagai M, Bruckner A, Enk A, Margolis D, McMichael A, Orringer J (eds), Fitzpatrick's Dermatology in General Medicine, Ninth Edition, Mc Graw Hill Medical Companies, Inc., 2019, 1867-1871.

¹⁰ Boyd A. Tumors of the epidermis, In: Barnhill R.(Ed), Dermatology, third edition, Mc. Graw Hill Medical, Inc. 2010; 556-614.

¹¹ Mun J.-H., Kim S.-H., Jung D.-S., Ko H.-C., Kwon K.-S., Kim M.-B.. Dermoscopic features of Bowen's disease in Asians. JEADV 2010; 24(7): 805-810.

¹² Zalaudek I., Di Stefani A., Argenziano G. The specific dermatoscopic criteria of Bowen's disease. J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol 2006; 20(3): 361-362.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A clinical and histological retrospective study was performed on a lot of 50 patients diagnosed with BD, hospitalized in Dermato-venerology Clinic of Craiova Romania, between 2010 and March 2021. Surgical excision and histopathologic exam were performed for all patients.

All patients have given their consent for surgery and subsequent pathologic exams.

The study material was represented by biopsy or excised lesions, collected under local anesthesia. The biopsy or resealed specimens were examined fresh, subsequently fixed and sent to the Department of Pathology of the County Emergency Clinical Hospital in Craiova, in order to be processed histologically. The biopsy specimens were processed using hematoxylin-eosin stain.

For the purpose of the study, the data obtained prospectively from the patients and recorded in the observation sheets were correlated with the histological diagnostic registers from the Pathological Anatomy laboratory, being subsequently selected from the histotheque of the respective unit.

The recording of data related to the evaluated parameters was done in the database tables of the Microsoft Excel module, component of the Microsoft Office 2007 Professional program package.

The images, representing the main clinical aspects, were taken with the help of a Nikon 10 Mpixeli digital camera; the processing of the images was carried out with the help of AdobePhotoshop, ver. CS3.

The histopathological examination was performed in all cases, performing multiple histological sections, in order to form an image of the tumor in its entirety. The serial sections have a special importance for the discovery of malignant transformation, as well as for the study of peritumor structures, allowing obtaining a diagnosis as accurate as possible.

The morphological study included a usual histopathological study, the resection pieces (excisional biopsy or tumor biopsy fragment) being evaluated from the microscopic point of view, the following objectives being targeted: assessment of the degree of cellular differentiation; assessment of the degree of invasion of neighboring structures; response or reaction of host tissues to the presence of the tumor.

For the microscopic analysis of these parameters, we used Nikon eclipse microscope 55i, Nikon's Image-ProPLUS program, examining fine sections (4 microns), colored by the usual method with Hematoxylin-Eosin.

RESULTS

Clinical and morphological data

There were 18 males (36%) and 32 females (64%), while 33 (66%) patients were from the urban environment; urban women are more commonly affected (22 cases) compared to men (11 cases). We also have noticed that in the group with malignant transformation of BD there is an almost equal distribution by genders (5 women and 4 men), 3 women and 3 men were from rural areas.

The mean age of the group with BD was 68.95 years, the age of the patients varying from 30 to 85 years, while for the group with malignancy was 73.82 years, with limits between 65 and 83 years. The mean age in women was 69.31 years, and in men 70.44 years.

BD was more frequently diagnosed in the 8th decade of life, with an increase in the number of cases since the 6th decade.

We observe the same tendency of increasing the number of malignant transformed cases with aging, so that 55.55% of malignant cases belong to the 6th decade of life (figure1).

(figure1) Distribution of patients with Bowen's disease by age group

Following the distribution by age, gender and environment, we noticed that regardless of age and gender BD is more frequently diagnosed in urban areas. In the 6th, 7th and 8th decade of life, women are more frequently affected, so that in the 9th decade of life both sexes are affected, regardless of the environment of origin.

The history of the lesions was between 1 month and 30 years, the size of the lesions being between 0.5 and 7 cm.

The tumors' topography, both for BD and invasive BD is presented in the table 1.

Topography of lesions by gender and the environment of origin

Localization	Cephalic extremity				Upper limbs				Lower limbs				Thorax				Genital region			
	U		R		U		R		U		R		U		R		U		R	
Environment	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B
Gender	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B	F	B
BD*	6	1	-	-	3	2	2	3	6	1	4	1	3	4	1	1	1	-	1	1
IBD**	1	1	1	1	-	2	1	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
No. of cases	7	2	1	1	3	4	3	3	7	1	4	1	4	4	1	1	1	-	1	1
%	14	4	2	2	6	8	6	6	14	2	8	2	8	8	2	2	2		2	2

(table 1)

*- Bowen disease, **- invasive Bowen disease

In the studied group we encountered in 47 cases the form of BD with single lesions. The appearance of a round-oval, yellowish-brown or pink plaque, with dimensions between 2 and 7 cm, discoid, slightly protruding with clearly delimited edges, covered by scales or crusts, sometimes hyperkeratosis, located on the trunk and limbs, on the photoexposed or traumatized areas was observed in 40 cases; the hyperkeratotic aspect was observed in 6 cases, clinically the lesion suggesting an actinic keratosis, angiokeratoma, seborrheic keratosis, vulgar wart; in one case the presence of ulceration was observed, announcing a possible malignancy. Among the particular clinical forms of BD, the following were observed: BD with multiple lesions – 3 cases (figure 2); 1 case of BD with periungual localization and 2 cases of pigmented BD with genital localization and on the thigh.

(figure 2) Clinical aspects in Bowen disease.

We noticed in the studied group the predominance of Bowen's disease with single lesions (92%), located more frequently on the limbs, on areas with chronic sun exposure.

Presumptive clinical diagnosis in 31 cases (57.40%), was confirmed by histopathological examination. In 19 cases the diagnosis of Bowen's disease was established on the basis of histopathological examination, there being no clinical suspicion of Bowen's disease (basal cell carcinoma in 9 cases, squamous carcinoma in 1 case, actinic keratosis in 3 cases, psoriasis in 1 case, seborrheic keratosis, melanocytic nevi, angiokeratoma and vulgar wart in 4 cases, genital leukoplakia 1 case).

The cutaneous manifestations of photo-aging, occurring as a result of chronic sun exposure, we have identified in most patients.

The risk factors involved in the occurrence of Bowen's disease in the studied group were: old age (the mean age in women was 69,31 years, and in men 70,44 years), chronic exposure to the sun (82% of lesions occur on photoexposed areas; 90% of patients recognize repeated and prolonged exposure to the sun), skin phototype (70% of cases belong to phototypes II and III), smoking (30% of the patients being smokers), chemical carcinogens (20%), chronic traumas to the skin (54,54%).

The evolution of the BD lesions was slow, of apparent stagnation, for long periods of time the changes being barely noticeable. Out of the 9 malignant cases in 5 cases, the transformation into invasive squamous carcinoma was clinically suspected, in one case the diagnosis was of basal cell carcinoma, and in 3 cases the clinical diagnosis was of actinic or seborrheic keratosis.

Regarding the association with other carcinomas and cutaneous precancers, 35 patients had a history or had concomitantly: one case SCC; basal cell carcinoma - 5 cases; multiple actinic keratoses located on the face and on the back of the hands in 25 cases, actinic cheilitis in 10 cases, cutaneous horn in 3 cases.

The histopathological study allowed the classification of these tumors in various histological subtypes depending on the growth pattern of the tumors and the assessment

in malignant cases of the degree of malignancy depending on the degree of differentiation of the cells.

For an accurate diagnosis, the pathologist must have at his disposal the entire tumor or a deep biopsy fragment, comprising a part of the tumor and the healthy perilesional skin.

In 41 cases (82%), histopathological examination establishes the diagnosis of BB without invasion. Histological features depend on the evolutionary stage of the tumor; all the tumors studied had the histopathological aspect of carcinoma in situ (figure 3).

(figure 3) **A.** Bowen's disease: acanthotic epidermis with hyperkeratosis, with large areas of parakeratosis, dyskeratosis, marked nuclear atypia and the presence of atypical mitosis, underlying chronic lymphoplasmacytic inflammatory infiltrate; HE stain x40 **B.** Bowen's disease (detail): marked nuclear atypia and the presence of atypical mitosis; HE stain x400

They have been identified as particular histopathological types of BD: acantholytic type (1 case), hyperkeratotic type (3 cases), pigmented type (2 cases), pagetoid type (3 cases).

In 9 cases (18%) the transformation into squamous carcinoma was diagnosed. In 6 cases we observed the invasion of the dermis, which initially occurs in a limited area, highlighting the area of carcinoma in situ and microcarcinoma, and in 3 cases it was observed moderately invasively differentiated invasive SCC in the hypodermis.

In order to detect the invasion, serial sections were made through the entire block; inflammatory infiltrate becomes abundant (figure 4).

Cases with malignant transformation occur in 5 women in the 7th and 9th decade of life, representing 15.62% of women and 10% of the total cases of Bowen's disease and in 4 men in the 7th, 8th and 9th decade of life, representing 22.22% of men and 8% of the total studied group.

DISCUSSIONS

Squamous cell carcinoma is an important public health problem, with an increasing annual incidence between 3-8% in all regions of the world and its efficient management consisting primarily in the detection and treatment of precursor precancerous lesions.

Bowen's disease is an *in situ*, preinvasive cancers with potential for progression in SCC, being clinically considered a precancer with high potential for malignancy. The exact incidence of Bowen's disease is not known¹.

In an epidemiological, clinical and evolutionary study, regarding the incidence of cutaneous carcinomas, carried out in our geographical area, the authors report the occurrence of CS in 46,24% of cases on precancerous lesions: actinic cheilitis, actinic keratoses, keratoacanthomas, cutaneous horn, Bowen's disease, erythroplasia of Queyrat, lichen sclerosis, chronic scars¹³.

The studied group includes 50 cases of Bowen's disease, diagnosed histopathologically over a period of 10 years. The gender ratio is 1:1.77 in favor of women, results consistent with a number of published studies, while others show an equal distribution by sex, or the predominance of men^{1,2,14}. Women seem to be more frequently affected than men, in the studied group they represent 64% of cases, and the lesions predominate on the lower extremities, on the sun exposed areas.

Cases with malignant transformation occur in 15.62% of women, accounting for 10% of all cases of Bowen's disease.

Bowen's disease was more frequently diagnosed in the 8th decade of life, with an increase in cases since the 6th decade, the age of the patients being between 30 and 85 years. We observe the occurrence of cases of malignant Bowen disease, equally, in the 7th, 8th and 9th decade of life, they represent 18% of the studied group.

Regarding the environment of origin, we noticed the more frequent affectation of patients from urban areas (66%), women being more frequently affected.

¹³ Pătrașcu V., Tănase L.E. Aspecte epidemiologice, histopatologice și clinic-evolutive ale carcinoamelor cutanate în județul Dolj-studiu pe 356 de cazuri. *DermatoVenerol.* (Buc), 2009; 54:13-20.

¹⁴ Hara H., Honda A., Suzuki H., Matsukura T. Detection of human papillomavirus type 34 in Bowen's disease on the pubic area. *JEADV*, 2006; 20: 206-208.

Of the 41 cases diagnosed with Bowen's disease, 65.85% came from urban areas, observing the same predominance of women in urban areas (70.37%), men having an almost equal distribution.

Age is an important predisposing factor, in the studied group it is noticed that the prevalence of Bowen's disease increases with age, with values ranging from 10% in the age group 51-60 years, to 30% in people aged 61-70 years and 54% in people aged 71-85 years, most cases being noticed in the 7th and 8th decade of life (72%).

In the occurrence of Bowen's disease are involved many factors, which act synergistically in the development of the tumor, in context of an immunosuppression or a genetic predisposition^{1,2,15,16}.

The role of chronic exposure to ultraviolet radiation in the etiology of Bowen's disease is very important and is documented by the frequent occurrence of Bowen's disease on the areas chronically exposed to the sun, in the studied group 82% of the lesions appearing on photoexposed areas. Although the majority of patients come from urban areas, 90% of patients recognize repeated and prolonged exposure to the sun.

There were also other arguments regarding the involvement of ultraviolet radiations: the rare occurrence in patients with intensely hyperpigmented skin and the appearance of BB after PUVA-therapy¹⁶.

Photocarcinogenesis is possible after repeated and prolonged exposures to the sun, several hours a day (professional and geographical factor), to which is added the racial phenotypic factor (Caucasians) and skin phototype⁷.

In precancerous lesions and in the skin chronically irradiated with UV, there have been found mutation of the p53 gene, data that can be regarded as an alarm signal for an already dangerous solar capital^{2,17}.

The repeated irradiation of the skin by ionizing radiation finds its morphological expression in chronic radiodermatitis, with important malignancy potential, on this lesion can appear keratoses, keratoacanthomas, SCC^{1,2}.

The risk of developing skin cancers increases if, along with irradiation, the patient will be exposed to ultraviolet, chemical carcinogens or oncogene viruses^{1,2,3}.

The relationship between chemical carcinogens and the occurrence of Bowen's disease has been documented, these factors acting alone or potentiated by UV^{2,17}. Insecticides could be involved in the etiopathogenesis of the disease in 10 patients, and smokers accounted for 30% of cases. Exposure to mineral trivalent arsenic (carcinogenic) is associated with the development of actinic keratoses, Bowen's disease, SCC, BCC, internal malignancies; the latency period is 25-30 years. The neoplastic process is whipped by the intervention and other risk factors (UV, HPV)^{2,18}.

Smoking has been associated with mutations in the p53 gene, which reveals another way of involving smoking in the process of carcinogenesis².

¹⁵ .Moldoveanu E., Popescu L.M., Apoptoza – mecanisme moleculare, Ediția a II-a, Ed. Universitară "Carol Davila", București, 1999, 21-60.

¹⁶ Pulitzer MP, Beer TW, Cerio R, Kao GF, Murphy GF, Nagore E, Scolyer RA. Squamous cell carcinoma in situ (Bowen disease). In: Elder D., Massi D, Scolyer R, Willemze R (IARC Group). WHO Classification of skin tumours, 4th Edition. Lyon, 2018, 46-47. ISBN-13: 978-9283224402.

¹⁷ .Pătrașcu V., Boli dermatologice și infecții sexual-transmisibile. Ediția a III-a, Ed. Sitech Craiova, 2014, 430-435, 449-464.

¹⁸ Dlugosz A., Yuspa S., Carcinogenesis Chemical. In: Wolff K, Goldsmith L., Katz S, Gilchrest B, Paller A, Leffell D (ed), Fitzpatrick's Dermatology in General Medicine, Seventh Edition, Mc Graw Hill Medical Companies, Inc., 2008, 986-994.

Passive smoking also increases the risk of cancer because smoke contains carcinogenic substances. Drug use associated with smoking and alcohol increases the risk of cancer².

Repeated local trauma is involved in the production of Bowen's disease, in our study 54.54% of patients with injuries on the hand, report multiple traumas in history.

Mechanical traumas have a role, appreciated differently by various authors, in the production or aggravation of a cancer or precancer; certain proinflammatory cytokines can inhibit the p53 gene, which explains the relationship between chronic inflammation and the development of tumors. They can be unique and brutal, bleeding or of weak intensity, but repeated. This factor is also involved in SCC but also in melanoma^{1,2}.

In the field of skin cancers, the group of those with mixed pathogenesis, genetic and environmental, is the majority.

In this context, correlations have been noted between the incidence of keratinocyte precancers and carcinomas and the cutaneous phototype, giving a special importance to the individual sensitivity to solar radiations².

Epidemiological studies have revealed significant differences in morbidity through cutaneous carcinomas depending on skin pigmentation. The risk of developing cutaneous carcinomas is maximum for phototype I and minimum for phototype VI. In the U.S.A, it has been estimated that whites have a 7 to 8-fold higher frequency of skin cancers compared to blacks (phototype VI)^{1,2}.

Regarding epithelial precancers, it has been observed that they occur more frequently in people with phototypes I and II.

Immunocompromised patients develop more frequently relapsing forms compared to immunocompetent people. In our study there was only one case with BB with multiple relapsing lesions.

The incidence of cancers in those with significant immune deficiency is 10,000 times higher than in immunocompetents of the same age, and in those with transplants 35 times higher than in the rest of the population^{1,19}. Cases with Lewandowski-Lutz verruciform epidermodysplasia or xeroderma pigmentosum in the studied group have not been identified; phototypes I and II, to which chronic exposure to the sun and outdoor occupations are associated, represent 70% of cases.

The presence of Bowen's disease in the studied group makes all patients to be considered susceptible to UV immunosuppression, knowing that the solar spectrum can diminish the immune function of the skin and thus lead to the formation of skin cancer.

To the UV-induced cutaneous immunosuppression is added prolonged immunosuppression related to the presence of systemic diseases, in the studied group a single case of Bowen's disease with multiple lesions having a history of ganglionar tuberculosis and phototype II, 1 case had a history of operated pulmonary neoplasm and phototype II and 1 case had an associated genodermatosis, these factors contributing to the development and evolution of the disease.

Regarding the role of viruses in carcinogenesis, it has been experimentally demonstrated that a chronic antigenic stimulation with herpesviruses (especially cytomegalovirus) in immunodepressed patients, such as those with organ transplantation or AIDS, induces the appearance of lymphomas and skin cancers^{1,2}.

¹⁹ Dlugosz A., Yuspa S., Carcinogenesis Chemical. In: Wolff K, Goldsmith L., Katz S, Gilchrest B, Paller A, Leffell D (ed), Fitzpatrick's Dermatology in General Medicine, Seventh Edition, Mc Graw Hill Medical Companies, Inc., 2008, 986-994.

The role of HPV in skin cancer remains controversial, but there are evidence of the role of the virus by promoting cancer, through mutagenic effects induced by ultraviolet B radiation, malignant conversion being potentiated by the action of some cocarcinogens (ultraviolet radiation, smoking, ionizing radiation, chemicals, immunodepression)^{1,2,12,20}.

The role HPV and HHV8 in the production of BD lesions is demonstrated in the localizations at the extremities and respectively in the lesions of the patients with organ transplantation. The association with HPV in extragenital lesions is more common in the black race, the acral localizations, the young age and the hyperkeratotic or verrucous appearance. PCR techniques allow the identification of cutaneous and mucous types of HPV, in some cases of extragenital BD there is a link with high-risk mucous HPV types^{21, 22,23,24}.

Subtypes 16, 18, 31, 34, 35, 54, 58, 61, 62, and 73 of HPV were detected in lesions of BD². Infection with high-risk subtypes of HPV (HPV 16) may be responsible for BD with localization in the hands or fingers through anal-digital contamination, in patients who also have simultaneous or genital lesions. The prevalence of HPV association of BD lesions is higher on areas of the skin not exposed to the sun compared to lesions on the photo exposed areas².

Although the occurrence of BD after burns was cited, in the studied group we did not notice this situation.

Cancers developed on a burn scar, have a latency duration of about 35 years (7 to 62 years), although cases have been described in the child. SCC predominates, but basal cell carcinoma, melanoma can also develop. About 2% of post-burn scars degenerate^{2,3,11}.

Regarding the topography of the lesions, regardless of gender and the presence or not of the malignant transformation, in the studied group, the most frequent localization of BB was at the level of the limbs (52%), on photo exposed areas, followed by the cephalic extremity (22%), thorax (20%) and genital (6%), suggesting the importance of chronic exposure to the sun in the etiopathogenesis of the disease. Men develop lesions on the upper limb more frequently, and women on the lower limbs, the results being consistent with those in the literature².

Bowen's disease with single lesions we noticed in 92% of cases, in 80% of cases the appearance is of round-oval plaque, covered with scales or crusts on the photo exposed or traumatized areas. Intense keratotic appearance we observed in 6 cases, clinically the lesion suggesting an actinic keratosis, angiokeratoma, seborrheic keratosis, vulgar wart.

²⁰ Zavos G., Karidis N., Tsurouflis G., Bokus J., Diles K., Sotirchos G., Theodoropoulou E., Kostakis A. Nonmelanoma skin cancer after renal transplantation: a single-center experience in 1736 transplantations. *International Journal of Dermatology* 2011; 50: 1496-1500.

²¹ Basset-Seguir N., Lebbe C., Proby C., Storey A., Oncogenes, Tumor Suppressor Genes and Viral Carcinogenesis, In: Wolff K, Goldsmith L., Katz S, Gilchrist B, Paller A, Leffell D (ed), *Fitzpatrick's Dermatology in General Medicine*, Seventh Edition, Mc Graw Hill Medical Companies, Inc., 2008, 995-998.

²² Mitsuishi T., Kawashima M., Matsukura T., Sata T. Human papillomavirus type 58 in Bowen's disease of the elbow. *Br J Dermatol.* 2001; 144:384-386.

²³ Zheng S., Adachi A., Shimizu M., Shibata S-I., Yasue S., Sakakibara A., Sugiura M., Nagasaka T., Tomita Y. Human papillomaviruses of the mucosal type are present in some cases of extragenital Bowen's disease. *Br J Dermatol.* 2005; 152:1243-1247.

²⁴ Ekeowa-Anderson A.L., Harwood C.A., Perrett C.M. Vulval intraepithelial neoplasia and periungual Bowen's disease concordant for mucosal (HPV-34) and epidermodysplasia verruciformis (HPV-21) human papillomavirus types. *Clin Exp Dermatol.* 2007; 32:304-307.

In 2% of the cases, we noticed the appearance of a prominent plaque with the presence of ulceration announcing a possible malignancy.

Among the particular clinical forms, we have encountered 3 cases of Bowen's disease with multiple lesions, localized on the calves, arm and thorax, or thigh and thorax. Clinical forms with multiple lesions are described in localizations on the trunk, especially the abdomen. This clinical form occurs in 40% of patients, the lesions can appear gradually, over several years²⁵. Nishimura Y reports a particular case of Bowen's disease with multiple interdigital, symmetrical lesions in a patient with chronic lymphocytic leukemia²⁶.

The disease remains for a long time stationary, with slow evolution, of apparent stagnation, long periods of time, of 10-15 years; ulceration and infiltration may be signs of malignant transformation. In the studied group, Bowen's disease evolved in 70% of the cases for 1-2 years, and in 28% of the cases between 4 and 5 years, a single case had an evolution of 30 years. Malignancy is noticed after a shorter latency period than that described in the literature (10-15 years). Also, the risk of progression into invasive carcinoma of 3-5% for Bowen's disease on the skin, described in the literature, is much lower than in the studied group^{2,11}. Patients with multiple lesions are more exposed to develop SCC, but in the 3 cases with multiple lesions, the malignant transformation was not revealed.

Most carcinomas, especially SCC, arise by the transition from dysplasia to carcinoma in situ and then to invasive carcinoma²⁷.

The existence of dysplasia facilitates the development of carcinoma in situ, dysplasia having a regressive or progressive spontaneous evolution. In contrast, there is no reliable evidence that a carcinoma in situ, once developed, can regress spontaneously.

The malignant transformation is suggested by the sudden development of the lesion, not so much in the surface but in height, the lesion becoming more prominent, with the more papillomatous surface and with the infiltration of the base, finally ulcerating, in the studied group two cases presenting these clinical characteristics.

The diagnosis of BD was correctly suspected clinically in 31 cases (57,40%), in the rest of the cases being diagnosed as basal cell carcinoma (9 cases), squamous cell carcinoma (1 case), actinic keratosis (3 cases), psoriasis (1 case), seborrheic keratosis, nevocellular nevus, angiokeratoma and vulgar wart in 4 cases, genital leukoplakia (1 case). For malignant cases only in 55.55% of cases, malignancy was suspected.

Most studies suggest a 3-5% risk of progression into invasive carcinoma for Bowen's disease on the skin and 10% for Queyrat erythroplasia^{1,11}. Patients with multiple lesions are more exposed to develop SCC. Of the cases in which the transformation into invasive carcinoma occurred, 13% will metastasize, and of these, 10% will die through systemic dissemination.

Studies show that 30-50% of patients with Bowen's disease have developed or will develop cutaneous carcinomas². Regarding the association with cutaneous carcinomas and actinic keratosis, 14% of the cases and, respectively, 76% of the cases, had associated

²⁵ Avram M.E., Costache I., Georgescu S.R., Benea V., Rusu A. Boală Bowen cutanată cu leziuni multiple. *DermatoVenerol.* 2007; 52: 157-159

²⁶ Nishimura Y., Kishigawa T., Tanaka T. Bilateral Bowen's disease. *British Journal of Dermatology* 2004; 151: 227-228.

²⁷ Duțu R., *Diagnosticul morfologic al Carcinoamelor*, Ed. Medicală, București, 1985, 37- 88.

cutaneous carcinomas (CBC – 10%, CSC – 4%) and multiple actinic keratosis.

We did not find in the studied group the association with pagetoid epitheliomas and associations with bowenoid papulosis, or internal neoplasia (although classically it was considered that Bowen's disease is a marker for internal malignancies and skin cancers, recent data seem to refute this theory)^{2,28}. Other authors report that in the next 5-10 years the diagnosis of Bowen's disease below 10% (less often 25-50%) of patients will get an internal cancer, malignant lymphoma, or skin cancer^{29,30,31}.

Histopathological examination is the golden standard in the diagnosis of skin cancers, the accuracy of diagnosis increasing when the initial histological results are reassessed by a dermatohistopathologist.

One of the factors that influence the exact estimation of the incidence and prevalence of skin precancers is the lack of histopathological examination in most studies^{2,32,33}.

Thus, the histological study of the skin precancerous lesions acquires a special importance, all the more so because in our geographical area many of these lesions are not addressed to the histopathologist, and the accuracy of the clinical diagnosis is quite low.

Since the clinical aspect has nothing characteristic, in the studied group the clinical diagnosis was correct in 57,40% of cases.

By comparing the histopathological diagnosis with the clinical one in the studied group, the accuracy of 57,40% for the clinical diagnosis and of only 55,55% in identifying malignancy, emphasizes the need for histological examination in these lesions.

Histopathological point of view Bowen's disease is an in situ squamous cell carcinoma, in which neoplastic cells originally appeared multicenterly, in small but expansive areas, and proliferate for a variable period of time only intraepidermal^{1,2}.

The histopathological aspects observed in Bowen's disease are similar, regardless of the sex of the patients, the environment of origin, the location of the lesions, the clinical form. Lesions located on areas chronically exposed to the sun are accompanied by actinic degeneration of collagen fibers. In 82% of the cases the histological picture reveals typical epidermal changes, consisting of hyperacantosis with Malpighian cells of different sizes, cramped, set disorderly, with voluminous atypical nuclei (Bowen cells), with early individual keratinization (cells with mantle, round bodies). The basal membrane is intact, as in all carcinomas in situ.

Damage to the appendages, especially the pilosebaceous complex, may be present, but it has not been encountered in the studied group. Hyperpigmentation along the basal layer and proliferation of dermal melanophages is accentuated in the pigmented version, also found in 2 cases in the studied group. Pagetoid and clear-cell variants have been reported³. The

²⁸ Iosif S., Tatu A., Costache M. Boala Bowen cutanată și pigmentară pe abdomenul inferior. Dermatovenerologie. 1998; 43: 119-121.

²⁹ Reyman F., Ravnborg L., Schou G. Bowen's disease and internal malignant diseases. A study of 581 patients. Arch Dermatol. 1988; 124:677-679.

³⁰ Arbesman H., Ransohoff D.F. Is Bowen's disease a predictor for the development of internal malignancy? A methodological critique of the literature. JAMA. 1987; 257:516-518.

³¹ Jaeger A.B., Gramkow A., Hjalgrim H. Bowen disease and risk of subsequent malignant neoplasms. Arch Dermatol. 1999; 135:790-793.

³² Schwartz RA. Premalignant keratinocytic neoplasms. J Am Acad Dermatol, 1996; 35: 223-242.

³³ Diepgen T.L., Mahler V. The epidemiology of skin cancer. Br J Dermatol 2002; 146 (suppl.61): 1-6.

invasion of the dermis occurs in 3-5% of cases, especially in the lesions of the head and neck, of the elderly or middle-aged people, and occurs initially in a limited area, and for its detection it is sometimes necessary to make serial sections through the entire block^{2,3}. In the studied group we observed the dermal invasion in 18% of the cases, the lesions being located on the back of the hand, forearm, face, calf and thorax, in both sexes in the 6th, 7th and 8th decade of life.

Both in cases with single lesions and in the clinical form with multiple lesions, the histopathological aspect is identical, suggestive of the diagnosis of carcinoma in situ. The invasion of the dermis initially occurs in a limited area, highlighting in 6 cases the area of carcinoma in situ and microcarcinoma, and in 3 cases it was observed the moderately differentiated SCC invasive in the hypodermis. In order to detect the invasion, serial sections were made through the entire block. Inflammatory infiltrate becomes abundant in cases with the invasion of the dermis. Some authors have described the phenomenon of fibrosis regression and scarring of the papillary dermis³⁴. Amyloid deposits are described in the injured and perilesional tegument, being the result of the degradation of cytokeratins from the dyskeratotic keratinocytes²⁶.

The appearance of the invasive process is announced by the accentuation of pseudoepitheliomatous hyperplasia, the presence of squamous cells with atypical mitosis, hyperchromatic nuclei, their number increasing with the number of undifferentiated cells, the appearance of discontinuities of the basal membrane, the accentuation of the reactional inflammatory infiltrate. The histopathological differential diagnosis was made mainly with bowenoid actinic keratoses, bowenoid papulosis, pagetoid in situ melanoma, actinic keratosis. Bowenoid actinic keratosis and bowenoid papulosis are histopathologically identical to Bowen's disease; however, these tumors are small and are usually completely excised by biopsy, for differentiation being useful immunohistochemical staining.

CONCLUSIONS

Although Bowen's disease is still considered by some clinicians a cutaneous precancer, histopathologically it is a potentially invasive in situ carcinoma. Age over 60 years, chronic exposure to the sun, chronic trauma and immunodepression are factors that intervene in the occurrence of the disease in the studied group. Age-related immunodepression and ultraviolet exposure are factors that intervene in the malignancy process. The positive diagnosis of the lesion is based on the clinical suspicion confirmed by the histopathological examination, which is mandatory for a diagnosis of certainty and to exclude invasive SCC.

The polymorphic clinical aspect explains that the diagnosis of BD was correctly suspected clinically in 57.40% of cases, and malignancy of lesions was clinically suspected only in 55.55% of cases.

BD tends to persistence and evolution towards an invasive squamous carcinoma, observing the malignant transformation of BD in 18% of cases, in both sexes in the 6th, 7th and 8th decade of life, the lesions being located on the photodamaged skin.

Early diagnosis of BD, correct treatment and careful monitoring of patients carry out prophylaxis of squamous carcinoma, a tumor with the potential for lymphatic or blood metastasis.

³⁴ Murata Y., Kumano K., Sashikata T. Partial spontaneous regression of Bowen's disease. Arch Dermatol. 1996; 132:429-432.

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PITYRIASIS RUBRA PILARIS TYPE I ASSOCIATED WITH CIRRHOSIS OF THE LIVER

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ABSTRACT:

PITYRIASIS RUBRA PILARIS (PRP) IS AN INFLAMMATORY SKIN DISEASE WITH POLYMORPHIC CLINICAL FEATURES, CONSISTING OF KERATOSIC FOLLICULAR PAPULES, YELLOW-ORANGE PALMOPLANTAR KERATODERMA ASSOCIATED WITH ERYTHEMATOUS OR ERYTHEMATOUS-SQUAMOUS PLAQUES, WHICH INTERSPERSED WITH AREAS OF HEALTHY SKIN. WE PRESENT THE CASE OF A 72-YEAR-OLD MAN IN WHICH THE DIAGNOSIS OF PRP REQUIRED ADDITIONAL EXPLORATIONS, FOR EXCLUDING NEOPLASIA OR OTHER INFLAMMATORY DISEASE. FINDING CONCOMITANT LIVER DISEASE REQUIRED A REASSESSMENT OF THERAPY.

KEYWORDS: A PITYRIASIS RUBRA PILARIS, ASSOCIATED CONDITIONS, TREATMENT.

INTRODUCTION

Pityriasis rubra pilaris is a rare condition, characterized by the appearance of follicular hiperkeratotic papules, associated with erythematous or erythematous-squamous plaques, which intersperse with areas of healthy tissue and yellow-orange palmoplantar keratoderma⁶. There are variations in the incidence depending on the race, in the UK there are 1 case

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reported for 5000 inhabitants and in India 1 case for 50,000 inhabitants. Both sexes are equally affected regardless of age, and family spread is only sporadic (up to 6.5%). Type I PRP although it responds well to retinoids treatment may have a reserved prognosis due to associated comorbidities⁷.

CASE REPORT

A 72-year-old patient, from rural environment, non-smoking, is admitted in the Dermatology Clinic for a rash consisting of follicular hiperkeratotic papules and erythematous plaques covered by white scales, with psoriasiform aspect, some coalescent in placards with imprecisely delimited margins, located on the trunk and limbs, lesions that appeared two months ago (figure 1, 2, 3).

(figure 1) Isolated follicular hyperkeratotic papules which in evolution forming psoriasiform erythematous plaques in classic adult type I pityriasis rubra pilaris. **A**, clinical aspect at admission. **B**, aspect 2 months after initiation of treatment with retinoids.

(figure 2) Follicular hyperkeratotic papules on the down half of the body. **A**, clinical aspect at admission. **B**, aspect 2 months after initiation of treatment with retinoids.

⁷ Virendra N Sehgal, Govind Srivastava, Sunil Dogra. Adult onset pityriasis rubra pilaris. IJDVL, 2008, Volume 74 (4): 311-321

(figure 3) Erythematous macules, psoriasiform plaques, follicular hyperkeratotic papules isolated and grouped. **A**, clinical aspect at admission. **B**, aspect 2 months after initiation of treatment with retinoids.

Bilateral palmar and plantar had a diffuse hyperkeratosis with painful fissures on the surface, occurring two weeks before the lesions on the trunk and limbs. The fingernails of the hands and feet were thickened, there were no injuries to the mucous. (figure 4)

(figure 4) Waxy, diffuse, yellowish palmar and plantar keratoderma with deep fissures in PRP type 1. **A**, clinical aspect at admission. **B**, aspect 1 month after initiation of treatment with retinoids. **C**, aspect 2 months after treatment.

From medical history we noticed: hypertension, atrial fibrillation, dyslipidemia.

Background medication: Indapamide LPH 1.5mg, p.o., b.i.d., Trimetazidine LPH 35mg p.o., b.i.d., Monopril 10mg p.o., b.i.d., Spironolactone 25mg p.o., q.d., Carvedilol 6.25mg p.o., b.i.d., Atorvastatin 20mg p.o., q.d.

Clinical examination: patient with good general condition, with obesity grade I (BMI = 32.74), pain in the lumbar spine, abdomen enlarged by volume through adipose tissue.

Laboratory explorations: Mild thrombocytopenia (136000/ μ l), blood count, GOT, GPT, glycemia, cholesterol, triglycerides, urea, creatinine, within normal limits, anti-HCV antibodies and negative HBs antigen. Urinalysis revealed: increased number of leukocytes, erythrocytes present, relatively frequent flat epithelium.

Abdomino and pelvic Ultrasound: Liver with anteroposterior diameter of left lobe 8.5cm, anteroposterior diameter of right lobe 18 cm, slightly increased consistency without localized processes. Gallbladder with thickened walls with sludge in the infundibular area, without calculi, portal vein with normal diameter, right kidney normal, homogeneous spleen. Left kidney with cyst at the level of the lower cortical pole with 3.2 cm diameter. Intensely hyperechogenic norm-sized pancreas. No fluid in the peritoneal cavity.

Pulmonary X-ray: Nothing active pleuro-pulmonary. Cord with increased transverse diameter.

Otorhinolaryngology exam: Left ear plug. Right otomycosis. Perforation of the right eardrum. It is practiced local toilet. Spraying with iodized boric acid is practiced.

During the hospitalization were performed two skin biopsies: from the level of the right calf – the posterior region and from the dorsal face of the right forearm.

The histopathological examination reveals: Epidermis with focal acanthosis, orthokeratosis that alternating horizontal and vertical with parakeratosis, hipergranulosis, thickening of the rete ridges, follicular hyperkeratosis, dilation of the infundibule of the hair follicle, discrete spongiosis. Underlying chronic perivascular inflammatory infiltrate, collagen degeneration.

Based on the anamnesis, clinical features, laboratory and histopathological examinations, we have established the diagnosis of classical type I PRP.

Treatment with acitretin at a dose of 50 mg/day was initiated for 3 weeks, with the dose lowered to 30 mg/day for 3 weeks and then 20 mg/day for 2 weeks. (figure 5)

(figure 5) Erythematous slightly scaling eruption with a tendency to erythroderma. **A**, clinical aspect at admission. **B**, aspect 1 month after initiation of treatment with retinoids. **C**, aspect 2 months after treatment.

The evolution was favorable, with the remission of palmoplantar hyperkeratosis, persisting a desquamative erythema on the dorsal face of the hands and a desquamative cheilitis, for which he is undergoing emollient treatment. For pecuniary reasons the patient discontinued therapy with acitretin.

2 months after discontinuation of acitretin therapy, the patient was hospitalized for recurrence of lesions.

Laboratory exams have revealed the persistence of thrombocytopenia (121700/ μ l), increased GOT (53U/L), slightly elevated triglycerides (152 mg/dl) and increased tumor markers AFP (8.60 IU/mL) and CA 19-9 (65.20 IU/mL).

Abdominal and pelvic ultrasound reveals an enlarged liver of volume with left lobe of 8.3 cm, right lobe 16 cm, inhomogeneous, pseudo-nodular structure, with hyperechogenic nodules up to 6 mm on a possible cirrhotic liver, a relaxed gallbladder without calculi, CBP 5 mm, VP 10 mm, intense hyperechogenic pancreas, anteroposterior diameter in the body 27 mm, normal kidneys size, without calculi, without dilations, normal vascularization, spleen 10.5 cm, urinary bladder normal.

The Internal Medicine consult recommends the extension of investigations: upper endoscopy, abdominal CT scan, colonoscopy and reassessment with the results obtained.

Upon discharge the patient there was recommended systemic treatment with acitretin at a dose of 30 mg/day for two months and hepatoprotective medication. For palmoplantar region we prescribed an ointment with salicylic acid 5% and urea 10%. Also, there were indicated a hypolipemic hygienic-dietary regimen, prohibition of alcohol consumption, regular control of lipid profile and transaminases and conducting investigations in the gastroenterology clinic.

After 2 months, at the admission to the Gastroenterology Clinic, the patient diagnosed with: alcoholic cirrhosis of the liver, chronic liver failure, esophageal varices with bleeding, high blood pressure, congestive heart failure, atrioventricular block grade 1.

DISCUSSIONS

The etiology and pathogenesis of PRP remain still poorly understood. There is considered that exist a dysfunction in the metabolism of vitamin A, but the role of its deficiency remaining uncertain because the attempts to produce lesions by the lack of vitamin A were not conclusive. Acute upper respiratory tract infections are implicated as triggers for juvenile forms of PRP. Autosomal dominant genetic factors play an important role in PRP induction⁸.

According to Griffiths, PRP is classified according to the clinical features and evolution as follows:

Type I (adult, classic) – is the most common form. It affects the sexes equally, having peak incidence between 40 and 60 years. The rash at onset consists of erythematous macules, slightly squamous at the level of the head, neck, or upper trunk, followed by the appearance of new macules over the course in a few weeks. Then arise many erythematous perifollicular papules with central hyperkeratotic plug, initially isolated, which then will merge together. Interfollicular erythema occurs, and follicular lesions combine into erythematous plaques with a slight orange tinge that generalize. The face becomes evenly erythematous and can be observed the occurrence an ectropion. Erythroderma usually develops within 2-3 months. In

⁸ Schäkel Knut. Pityriasis Rubra Pilaris In: Kang S., Amagai M, Bruckner A, Enk A, Margolis D, McMichael A, Orringer J (eds), Fitzpatrick's Dermatology in General Medicine, Ninth Edition, Mc Graw Hill Medical Companies, Inc., 2019, 498-503.

most cases, well-demarcated islands of healthy tissue about 1 cm in size remain a useful diagnostic sign. The nails are thickened and discolored distally, with longitudinal hemorrhagic striae; and compared to psoriasis, there is no dystrophy of the nail bed and pitting is minimal. Spontaneous resolution occurs in 60-80% of patients in 1-3 years, but the disease can persist indefinitely. The rash resembles seborrheic dermatitis as it resolves. Recurrences are rare³.

Type II (adult, atypical) - Affects 5% of patients and presents as a prominent follicular hyperkeratosis in certain areas with lamellar scales in other locations, especially in the lower limbs. Often there are areas with changes of eczematous type³.

Type III (juvenile, classic) - The onset is from 5 to 18 years. It resembles type I but can quickly develop an acute infection and spontaneous resolution is usually between 1-2 years. The evolution from type III to type IV and vice versa may occur.

Type IV (juvenile, circumscribed) - Onset by the age of 12 years. Patients have well-defined hyperkeratosis plaques with erythema of varying intensity located in the knees and elbows and several squamous erythematous macules sprinkled on the trunk or scalp, with certain cases also showing marked keratoderma of the palms and soles. The prognosis remains unclear but certain cases heal at the end of adolescence³.

Type V (juvenile, atypical) - The familial form is often of this type and can overlap clinically with ichthyosis and erythrokeratoderma. Patients present erythema and hyperkeratosis at birth or in the first years of life. Follicular plugs and erythema suggest the diagnosis of PRP but keratoderma is common³.

PRP type VI (PRP and immunodeficiency) - A PRP-like rash associated with HIV infection, which responds to antiretroviral therapy, is recognized⁹. The clinical manifestations are similar to those of type I but have increased severity and additional manifestations of acne conglobate, hidradenitis suppurative and lichen spinulosus³. Some authors still preferred the term follicular syndrome associated with HIV infection¹⁰.

Differential diagnosis is made especially with psoriasis, from which it is clinically differentiated by:

1. the general condition of patients with PRP remains good in contrast to that of those who have psoriasis,
2. the "islands" of unaffected tissue are characteristic,
3. scarlet or orange color of the skin,
4. the absence of infiltration, lichenification and profuse lamellar squamous that are characteristic of psoriasis,
5. absence of oncolysis typical of psoriasis,
6. palmoplantar hyperkeratosis of yellow-orange color, without infiltration,
7. ineffective antihistamine and hormonal treatment¹¹.

Other differential diagnoses are follicular ichthyosis, variable erythrokeratoderma, follicular eczema, hair keratosis, chronic lichenoid pityriasis, nonbullous congenital ichthyosiform erythroderma, and for treatment-resistant cases - with HIV infection, T-cell lymphomas³.

⁹ M.R. Judge, W.H.I. McLean, C.S. Munro. Disorders of Keratinization, in Rook's Textbook of Dermatology, Vol. 1, 19.77-19.79.

¹⁰ M.R. Judge, W.H.I. McLean, C.S. Munro. Disorders of Keratinization, in Rook's Textbook of Dermatology, Vol. 1, 19.77-19.79

¹¹ Kubanov A., Gallyamova Y. Diagnosis and Treatment of Pityriasis Rubra Pilaris, Serbian Journal of Dermatology and Venerology, 2011, Volume 6 (4): 167-173. DOI: 10.2478/sjdv-2014-0014.

Associated diseases

Associations with paraneoplastic dermatomyositis, inflammatory arthritis, viral hepatitis A have been described, and recently a case associated with lichen planus, universal alopecia, vitiligo and viral hepatitis C has been described^{3,12,13}.

Some authors consider PRP as paraneoplastic syndrome being cited associations with liver carcinoma, cholangiocarcinoma^{14,15}.

Treatment

Early treatment with retinoids seems to provide the greatest chance of cure for PRP. If treatment with retinoids does not give results, treatment with methotrexate should be considered.

The effectiveness of retinoids and methotrexate is supported by numerous studies compared to other forms of treatment, including corticosteroids, vitamin A and cyclosporine, which were ineffective¹⁶.

The most effective retinoid for the treatment of PRP is acitretin at a dose of 0.5-0.75 mg/kg/day, with the average daily dose varying between 25-50 mg/day. The improvement of the symptomatology is observed from the first month of treatment, but substantial improvements or even healing occur during the first 4-6 months. According to certain studies, the average duration of treatment is about 4 years^{3,5}.

Methotrexate can be a therapeutic alternative at a dose of 15-25 mg/week. The associating methotrexate (5-30 mg/week) with oral retinoids over a period of 16 weeks increases the therapeutic response but the combination may lead to increased hepatotoxicity.

The use of phototherapy (UVA) is controversial, with some cases evolving favorably, others worsening, no UVB is indicated.

In severe cases, an effective treatment option are immunomodulators: fumaric acid, TNF α antagonists, apremilast^{3,5}. Recently, very good results have been reported with ustekinumab and secukinumab in cases with familial PRP, but also the appearance of follicular lymphoma in a case treated with adalimumab and methotrexate^{17,18,19}.

Used only as an adjunct, topical treatment during retinoid therapy increases the quality of life of patients. Emollient creams, ointments with salicylic acid 2-5 %, urea 10 %, calcipotriol, malic acid 1-20 % are used in the treatment of palmoplantar hyperkeratosis.

¹² Erdem T, Atasoy M, Aliagaoglu C, Melikoglu M, Yildirim U. Pityriasis rubra pilaris in association with hepatitis A. Saudi Med J. 2006 Sep;27(9):1421-2.

¹³ Cecchi R, Giomi A, Tuci F, Bartoli L, Seghieri G. Pityriasis rubra pilaris, lichen planus, alopecia universalis and vitiligo in a patient with chronic viral hepatitis C. Dermatology. 1994;188(3):239-40. PubMed PMID: 8186518.

¹⁴ Sharma S, Weiss GR, Paulger B. Pityriasis rubra pilaris as an initial presentation of hepatocellular carcinoma. Dermatology. 1997;194(2):166-7. PubMed

¹⁵ Bar-Ilan E, Gat A, Sprecher E, Zeeli T. Paraneoplastic pityriasis rubra pilaris: case report and literature review. Clin Exp Dermatol. 2017 Jan; 42(1):54-57. doi: 10.1111/ced.13009. Epub 2016 Nov 29.

¹⁶ Dicken CH. Treatment of classic Pityriasis Rubra Pilaris. J Am Acad Dermatol. 1994 Dec; 31(6): 997-9.

¹⁷ Lwin SM, Hsu CK, Liu L, Huang HY, Levell NJ, McGrath JA. Beneficial effect of ustekinumab in familial pityriasis rubra pilaris with a new missense mutation in CARD14. Br J Dermatol. 2017 Mar 16. doi: 10.1111/bjd.15462.

¹⁸ Gauci ML, Jachiet M, Gottlieb J, Madeleine-Chambrin I, Rybojad M, Bagot M, Bouaziz JD. Successful treatment of type II pityriasis rubra pilaris with secukinumab. JAAD Case Rep. 2016 Dec 5;2(6):462-464.

¹⁹ Dhonncha N.E, Fadalla K, Moriarty B, Gibbons D, Collins CD, Fabre A, Collins P. High grade follicular lymphoma in a patient receiving adalimumab and methotrexate for pityriasis rubra pilaris. J Dermatolog Treat. 2017 Mar 7:1-7. doi: 10.1080/09546634.2017.1303572

CONCLUSIONS

PRP remains a condition that causes problems of diagnosis and treatment, with an important impact on the quality of life regardless of the clinical form. Retinoids remain an effective therapeutic option but require precautions in the presence of liver pathology.

The occurrence of PRP in an elderly patient requires further explorations to exclude an internal neoplasia or other inflammatory diseases.

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